

UNIVERSITI TEKNOLOGI MARA

**GENOMIC ADAPTATION IN
ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE:
ELUCIDATING THE ROUTE AND
EFFECTS IN *Acinetobacter baumannii***

MOHAMAD IZWAN BIN ISMAIL

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MOHAMAD IZWAN BIN ISMAIL

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of the requirements for the degree of
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CONFIRMATION BY PANEL OF EXAMINERS

I certify that a panel of examiners has met on 12th October 2015 to conduct the final examination of Mohamad Izwan Bin Ismail on his Doctor of Philosophy thesis entitled “Genomic Adaptation in Antimicrobial Resistance: Elucidating the Route and Effects in *Acinetobacter baumannii*” in accordance with Universiti Teknologi MARA Act 1976 (Akta 173). The Panel of Examiners recommends that the student be awarded the relevant degree. The Panel of Examiners was as follows:

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AUTHOR'S DECLARATION

I declare that the work in this thesis was carried out in accordance with the regulations of Universiti Teknologi MARA. It is original and is the result of my own work, unless otherwise indicated of knowledge as reference work. This thesis has not been submitted to any other academic institution or non-academic institution for any other degree or qualification.

I, hereby, acknowledge that I have been supplied with the Academic Rules and Regulations for Postgraduate, Universiti Teknologi MARA, regulating the conduct of my study and research.

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ABSTRACT

Antimicrobial resistance has been a looming threat ever since its conception and it has become one of the greatest global problems of the current era. Although various studies have been conducted to better understand the mutational triggers leading to antimicrobial resistance, the specific genomic path towards it have yet to be discerned. Here, we aim to elucidate the pathway of genomic evolution throughout the resistance induction of an *A. baumannii* strain towards ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem, as well as comparing the mutations acquired clinically versus *in vitro*. Twenty-five (25) local clinical *A. baumannii* strains were isolated and screened for antimicrobial susceptibility, and their genome were sequenced using the Illumina GAIIx genome sequencer. The susceptible parent was then challenged with ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem separately until growth is still possible beyond the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) as defined by EUCAST standards. Once the resistance stability was confirmed, another sequencing run was done on the isogenic. Variant analysis was carried out using CLC Bio, and primers were designed to target the mutations of interest. PCR was then carried out on aliquots of the resistant mutants, each taken at increasing levels of antimicrobial tolerance throughout the challenging process. Phylogenomics and wgMLST analyses were carried out between the parent and resistant strain, as also the remaining isolates. Stable low and high-level resistant strains were successfully generated. Several genomic variants were identified in the high-level resistant strains. Validation of variant calling via PCR removed all miscalled variants. Comparative genome annotation revealed a high consistency in the genome structures of the clinical strains, despite non-consistent phylogenetic and synteny profiles. The mutation validation revealed several variations arising in genes responsible for signaling (*yihG*, *bvgS* and *srrA*), metabolic activities (*atpD*, *ribonuclease I*, and *epsL*) and cell structure maintenance (*ftsI* and *yceG*) in addition to targeted mutations (*mexB*, *acrB* and *gyrA*). Analysis of the mutation chronology shows that when exposed to erythromycin, *A. baumannii* incurs modifications to genes *bvgS* and *srrA*, on days 4, 6, and to *ftsI* and its ribonuclease I encoding gene on day 67. When exposed to ciprofloxacin, mutations developed in *gyrA* and *yihG* on days 28 and 48. Meropenem exposure on the other hand has led to variations in *epsL*, *mexB*, and *atpD* on days 4, 10 and 70. In contrast, meropenem exposure resulted in mutations to *acrB* on day 38, and two mutations in *ftsI* occurred on day 19 and 67. From the results it is deduced that the chronology of intrinsic mutations is dependent on the types and intensity of selective pressures enacted, even on the same bacteria. Antibiotic pressure under *in vitro* and *in vivo* conditions has also resulted in development of different mutations leading to similar resistance profiles. It was also found that a prolonged exposure to the drugs used in this study plays as much of a role as the sub-inhibitory concentration.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations

- GEM** - Gentamycin
- ERY** - Erythromycin
- CIP** - Ciprofloxacin
- MEM** - Meropenem
- IMI** - Imipenem
- ZOI** - Zone of Inhibition
- MIC** - Minimum inhibitory concentration
- Ab00** - *A. baumannii* susceptible parent strain
- AbRC** - Ciprofloxacin-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant
- AbRE** - Erythromycin-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant
- AbRM** - Meropenem-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant
- AbRI** - Imipenem-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant
- PCR** - Polymerase Chain Reaction
- Conc.** - Concentration

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Acinetobacter consists of groups of Gram negative coccobacilli that falls under the class of gammaproteobacteria. However, due to its tendency to occasionally change its morphology based on its growth phase and conditions, it is often mistaken as Gram negative coccus (Madigan & Martinko, 2006; Alsan & Klompas, 2010). It has been noted that it is capable of becoming thicker and more electron-dense when exposed to desiccation (Marti, 2008). This suggests an increased expression of proteins involved in maintaining its cellular morphology and/or integrity during such harsh conditions (King, Stansfield, & Mulligan, 2006). *Acinetobacter* also develops a shorter and rounder form during its stationary phase, making it less distinctive from regular Gram negative cocci (Marti, 2008). As up to date no research has been done to pinpoint the exact reason why this species undergoes such changes. The reduction in size could be due to the need to conserve the amount of nutrients that is being consumed in order to maintain its survivability. Bacteria are known to increase in size whenever they are metabolically active, and it can be postulated that when under arid, nutrient deprived conditions, their metabolic activity would decrease; and by extension, their size would undergo a reduction as well (Corona & Martinez, 2013).

Acinetobacter tends to come in pairs or form groups of four or more, similar to the grouping properties of the common *Staphylococcus aureus*. However, single cells can be observed as well (Marti, 2008). Even between the different species of *Acinetobacter*, the clustering or orientation of the individual bacteria may vary. Members of this genus are strictly aerobic, limiting their survival only on surfaces that it is exposed to oxygen. Although it lacks flagella and potential for motility, which is a trait that would otherwise contribute to its virulence, it is still recognized as one of the more threatening nosocomial microorganisms (Kindt et al., 2007). It is noteworthy that its name was actually based on its lack of mobility. The term “Acineto” was derived from the Greek word “Akineto,”

which means akinetic or motionless. Biochemical tests have confirmed that members of the genus *Acinetobacter* are generally non-fermenting, catalase positive and oxidase negative. However, certain species may attribute different biochemical properties. There have been reports stating that the *baumannii* is capable of fermenting lactose when cultured on MacConkey agar. Molecular studies on the other hand have identified that its DNA G+C content generally ranges between 39 and 47 mol% (Bergogne-Bérézen & Towner, 1996; Marti, 2008).

A. baumannii is known for its promiscuity in acquiring resistance determinants from foreign cells (Peleg et al., 2008). Along with other pathogens, *A. baumannii* is capable of bacterial transformation, where it essentially reaches into cells of the same species or otherwise, in an attempt to take up potentially useful genes (King et al., 2006). Moreover, this method also applies to non-living cells, whereby an intact, soluble DNA is salvaged from the “deceased” microorganism; a method appropriately termed as “funeral grab” (Griffith, 1928; Redfield, 1988; Klose, 2013). In addition, *A. baumannii* has also shown an impressive propensity for acquiring resistance on its own as well. Its genomic plasticity makes it capable of mutating specific regions in its genome, allowing it to adapt to the selective pressure brought on by various types of antimicrobials (Francesco et al., 2011). This property is what makes *A. baumannii* and others like it a serious matter.

In the recent years, antimicrobial resistance has been deemed a global issue. In 2014, the Longitude Prize, a global competition run by Nesta, the UK’s innovation foundation was launched. The competition promises a sum of £10 million to participants capable of solving the “problem of the century”; which by a majority vote was decided to be the yet unsolved issue of antimicrobial resistance. Evidently, among the current global issues such as dementia, food and water shortage, paralysis and green flight technology, the global community has decided that drug resistance takes precedence (<https://longitudeprize.org/>).

Moreover, on September 2014, a report entitled “Combating Antibiotic Resistance” was addressed to the US President, by the co-chairpersons of the President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology (PCAST) Antibiotic Resistance Working Group. The report emphasizes on several recommendations, among which includes recommendations for more fundamental research and the improvement of public

health infrastructure for surveillance and response towards antibiotic resistance (President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology, 2014). Following this, several fact sheets were published by the White House Office of the Press Secretary, the latest of which is dated 27th March 2015. These statements, as well as a few presidential addresses are a further indication of the seriousness of the matter (Office of the Press Secretary, 2014; Burwell et al., 2015; Office of the Press Secretary, 2015; Office of the Press Secretary, 2015).

In the past few years, the use of whole-genome sequencing (WGS) has proven to be a great asset in uncovering new information on antimicrobial resistance in clinical pathogens (Gordon et al., 2014; Köser et al., 2014). This global approach allows for the screening of the pathogen's entire genome, providing a broader view of any and all changes occurring due to treatment or intervention. Through the use of the updated WGS technologies, it is now possible to acquire whole-genome data at a relatively faster pace, with a lower cost compared to earlier iterations (Illumina, 2012).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Infections caused by *A. baumannii* can be deadly and has been further complicated by the widespread and uncontrolled use of antibiotics, resulting in a rapid increase of multi-drug resistant pathogens, especially in hospitals. This is due to the various genetic modifications that the pathogen has undergone throughout the years of exposure to antimicrobials. Hence, there is an increasing need to identify the genetic elements involved in drug resistance acquisition in order to curb these rampant mutations. In addition, elucidating these adaptation mechanisms will add to the development of new measures to reduce the cases of mortality due to *A. baumannii*. Therefore, we took steps to identify the genetic elements involved in drug resistance via whole-genome sequencing approach.

1.3 GENERAL OBJECTIVES

To generate an *A. baumannii* strain resistant to ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem, and track the mutation time points throughout the process.

1.4 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- 1.4.1** To understand the genomic composition of a susceptible parent *A. baumannii* strain by;
- i. Determining the antimicrobial susceptibility profile of 25 local clinical *A. baumannii* isolates, and
 - ii. Sequencing and annotating the genome of the susceptible parent strain.
- 1.4.2** To elucidate the genomic variations that arise from an *in vitro* resistance induction by;
- i. Inducing antimicrobial resistance towards ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem in the susceptible parent strain,
 - ii. Sequencing the genome of the isogenic mutants and identify the variants detected in each genome, and
 - iii. Validating the variants detected in the isogenic mutants via PCR.
- 1.4.3** To clarify the chain of mutation events leading to a stable resistance in the resistant isogenic *A. baumannii* variants by;
- i. Confirming the time point and order of mutation events in each isogenic variant via PCR,
 - ii. Identifying the heterogeneity of each mutation throughout the induction period, and
 - iii. Determining the stability of the acquired resistance in various storage conditions.
- 1.4.4** To compare the genomic mutations between the *in vitro* resistant strains with the clinical resistant isolates.
- i. Sequencing the genome of the remaining 24 clinical *A. baumannii* isolates,
 - ii. Annotating the gene functions and genome layout of each sequenced genome,
 - iii. Identifying patterns of resistance and virulence profiles in the 25 annotated genomes, and
 - iv. Comparing the genomes of the *in vitro* isogenic mutant with the clinically resistant isolates.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 TWO MAIN SOURCES OF *Acinetobacter*

Different species of *Acinetobacter* are isolated from clinical and environmental samples. Their dissimilar properties in terms of growth conditions and pathogenicity had been noted. Studies have identified that environmental samples are normally composed of single species such as *A. johnsonii*, *A. lwoffii*, and of certain genotypes that lack a proper taxonomic designation (e.g. *Acinetobacter* genospecies 9). These species are relatively common in water, soil and fecal samples, especially *A. johnsonii* (Marti, 2008).

Clinical isolates on the other hand are composed of mostly *Acinetobacter baumannii-calcoaceticus* (ABC) complexes. *A. baumannii* would be the second most commonly found isolates other than the *Acinetobacter* complexes. The taxonomic status of the ABC complex was established due to difficulties in discerning between *A. baumannii* and *A. calcoaceticus*, as these two species possess phenotypic properties that are very similar to one another. That, coupled with the aforementioned fact that *Acinetobacter* is capable of undergoing morphological changes, adds to the problem of discriminating between the two species.

Certain clinical isolates also possess capabilities that are not found in environmental samples. For example *A. haemolyticus*, as the name suggests, is able to cause haemolysis (i.e. lysis of red blood cells) when grown on sheep blood agar, a property that is unique even among clinical isolates. In 2008, a research done by Peleg *et al.* reported that the capacity for haemolysis has never been seen in any other clinical isolates, not even in ABC complexes (Peleg *et al.*, 2008).

3.2 Ubiquity of *Acinetobacter*

Most studies claim that *Acinetobacter* are a group of commonly occurring bacteria, whether as environmental microorganisms, or as microflora in (or on) humans. However, in a conference held by The Lancet in 2008, it was stated that the ubiquity of *Acinetobacter* has been heavily misjudged. Reports from various studies consistently

state that *Acinetobacter* are ubiquitous on humans. However in truth, *Acinetobacter* is actually only prevalent during outbreaks and reports of the microorganism occurring as nosocomial pathogens are otherwise minute (Towner, 2008)

3.3 SURVIVAL UNDER DRY CONDITIONS

What makes the genus *Acinetobacter* interesting albeit frightening organism are basically two things; its ability to survive in arid conditions, and its infamous potential for obtaining resistance against antimicrobials (Eveillard et al., 2013; Chen & Huang, 2014). Normally, it isn't strange to find bacteria on reservoirs such as door knobs, pillow cases or any common surfaces. However, these bacteria tend to die out after 24 hours, give or take a few hours depending on the general moisture of the environment. *Acinetobacter* on the other hand, is capable of surviving up to three to four weeks in an environment that is devoid of moisture (Jawad et al., 1998; Jawad et al., 1996; Espinal et al., 2012). This is most evident in the soils of Iraq, where the strain *Acinetobacter baumannii* is affectionately referred to as *Iraqibacter* (Love & Davidson, 2008; Kirt, 2008). This was inadvertently proven during a research done by militants stationed in Iraq when they were attempting to identify the origin of a series of lethal *Acinetobacter* infections that their wounded soldiers have contracted.

It was suggested in 1996 by Jawad *et al.* that *Acinetobacter* may react the same way as *S. aureus* when exposed to dry conditions. This is supported by the near similar survival times observed in both the ABC complex and in *S. aureus* when exposed to the designated level of aridity. As shown in **Figure 2.1**, the group of *Acinetobacter* under the ABC complex group seems to exhibit a range of survival time close to that of *S. aureus*, with the exception of a few American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) strains. By comparison, *A. baumannii* strains 16/48 and 16/49 demonstrated a survival capacity ranging approximately between 25 and 35 days when suspended in either distilled water or bovine serum albumin, which is somewhat akin to the survival length of *S. aureus* strain 186/9079 under the same conditions (Jawad et al., 1996).

Also, it was observed that environmental or clinical isolates of *Acinetobacter* were much more capable of surviving when exposed to desiccation as opposed to ATCC strains. The maximum survival time of the isolates was observed to be up to 60 days, and the lowest was 10 days. As opposed to the survival time of the ATCC strains ranging

between 24 hours and 10 days (Jawad et al., 1996). This was probably due to the continuous subculturing of the ATCC strains, which reduced their pressure for maintaining growth in harsh conditions, leading to their decreased resistance (Marti, 2008).

Figure 2.1: Survival Times of Different Species of Bacteria Suspended in Distilled Water or Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) (Jawad et al., 1996)

The rate of reproduction of *Acinetobacter* strains also contributes to the survival of the species. A documentary by Nova ScienceNow mentioned that a single *Acinetobacter baumannii* can continuously undergo binary fission until approximately 5×10^{21} daughter cells are produced, all in a single day (<http://www.pbs.org/wgbh/nova/sciencenow/>

[0303/04.html](#)). Rapid reproduction coupled with antimicrobial resistance and resilience in arid environments would easily make *Acinetobacter* a significant pathogenic threat. This was based on the growth of clinical isolates from wounded soldiers serving in Iraq (<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JSnB2HJnuOY>).

3.4 ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

In addition to its hardiness, *Acinetobacter* possesses an evident ability to obtain resistance against antimicrobials, which are contributed by the following factors;

i) Resistance islands

Although the potential for adaptation to antibiotics is not uncommon in bacteria, *Acinetobacter* takes this to a completely new level. It is believed that the microorganism has developed a powerful molecular system that would enable it to gain completely new resistance exceedingly faster than the average microbe. In a study by Fournier and colleagues, it was discovered that certain strains of *Acinetobacter* possess a genomic island (clusters of genes that are suspected to be obtained via horizontal transfer) that contained genes involved in motility but lack resistance markers (Fournier et al., 2006). By comparing the genome of those strains with other *Acinetobacter* strains, it was determined that the genomic island was not conserved, and considered to be a “coincidental genetic insertion”, as its presence (or absence) does not seem to affect the strain’s capacity for antimicrobial resistance (Langille & Brinkman, 2009). This finding supports the idea that *Acinetobacter* does indeed possess a flexible genome, in a sense that it is able to relatively easily uptake new genetic information for its benefit (Fournier et al., 2006).

One of the main methods by which *Acinetobacter* gains novel resistance is by genetic exchange between itself and other microorganisms. *Acinetobacter* is referred to as “naturally transformable” and is therefore much more likely to obtain new genetic material in comparison to other microbes (Marti, 2008). It is common for *Acinetobacter* to undergo horizontal gene transfer, enabling it to copy any resistance genes present in other microbes it has come in contact with. It is believed that the continuation of this “promiscuous” lifestyle for several decades is what grants the *Acinetobacter* the multitude of resistance genes in its genome.

ii) **Antibiotic-degrading enzymes**

There are several different mechanisms in which the *Acinetobacter* employs in order to become resistant to antibiotics. A direct method would be by producing enzymes that degrade the antimicrobials, as observed in *A. baumannii* when exposed to β -lactam, where it produces β -lactamases to immediately destroy the compound. The bacteria may also employ a series of different mechanisms in order to produce the same effect as β -lactamase, i.e. degradation of β -lactam (Shaikh et al., 2015; Sinha et al., 2007).

iii) **Outer membrane proteins**

A different approach that the microbe applies in order to obtain resistance is by a few non-enzymatic mechanisms. This normally infers alterations to its genetic expressions, which would ultimately result in changes in its structure and activity. An example of this is by exerting different outer membrane proteins (Siroy et al., 2005; Bonomo & Szabo, 2006). Understandably, in order for antimicrobials to affect its target, they need to first make contact with microbes. And when the compound recognizes its target, it will bind to it, normally via proteins or receptors available on the surface membrane of the microorganism of interest, and basically bring about changes in the activities of the microbe, such as inhibition of biochemical functions, inhibition of reproduction, increase in susceptibility towards the host's immune system, or ideally immediate destruction of the bacteria (Madigan et al., 2011).

By altering the expression of proteins available on its outer membrane, the *Acinetobacter* can avoid interaction with antimicrobials, as it no longer has the receptors necessary for the drugs to target and bind to. This mechanism is similar to the method used by most viruses when avoiding detection by the host immune system (Kindt et al., 2007; Boll et al., 2015). The difference is that viruses will take up the host's proteins to construct an envelope which acts as a disguise, hiding it from the host immune system, while *Acinetobacter* takes up the genetic information needed to generate a different set of outer membrane proteins from an already resistant microorganism (provided that the microbe is within its proximity). An example of this is the switching of an *Acinetobacter* outer membrane protein (CarO to OMP25) in the attempt to avoid CarO-specific antibiotics (Peleg et al., 2008; Eijkelkamp et al., 2014).

An alternative to this is the reduction in the expression of the CarO outer membrane proteins, by which the bacteria would successfully reduce its susceptibility and sensitivity towards the same type of drug. Specific insertion elements in the *Acinetobacter* genome have been reported to result in the loss of the CarO genes (Peleg et al., 2008). This indicates that different genes such as down-regulators may be taken up in order to decrease susceptibility, instead of simply inserting specific resistance genes. Mutations that change gene regulation may even be able to affect how the bacteria interact with other antibiotics as well (Peleg et al., 2008; Händel et al., 2014).

It is well understood that as a safety measure, the outer membrane of microorganisms are generally not permeable to any harmful substances. This in itself is actually a system that ensures safety of some pathogens from antibiotics. The more complex the structure of the outer layer of these microorganisms, the harder it is to design drugs that would penetrate them. And essentially, the low permeability of the outer membrane also ensures that little to none of such harmful compounds be taken up (Vila et al., 2007; Chusri, Na-Phatthalung et al., 2014)..

iv) Efflux pump

Another mechanism adapted by *Acinetobacter* in maintaining its antimicrobial resistance is through the use of an efflux pump, which can be defined as any particular cellular mechanism that enables a microorganism to expel any unwanted toxins or drugs (in this case, antibiotics) from its internal environment (King et al., 2006). The efflux pump is a common mechanism that exists in all living cells (Vila et al., 2007). The efflux pump basically, is a transporter protein that actively pushes out distinct molecular structures or classes of antibiotics. Of course, energy in the form of adenosine-triphosphate (ATP) is required in order to carry out this task. Normally, an efflux system is specific to a particular type of toxin or molecular structure. However, some pathogens, including certain *Acinetobacter* strains have developed a multidrug efflux system that would extrude a variety of antibiotics, and granting it multidrug resistance (Shafer et al., 2001; Nikaido, 2012). In order to achieve this, these *Acinetobacter* strains over-express the efflux pump mechanism, either by increasing the number of active carrier proteins involved in the mechanism or by increasing the activity of those proteins (Yoon et al., 2013).

The efflux system works in tandem with the low permeability of the pathogen's outer membrane. This intricate mechanism allows the bacteria to first prevent unnecessary entry of antibiotics. Should any make its way into the cellular matrix, the efflux pump would immediately remove those structures, ensuring its survival. The molecules that were expunged from the cell's interior would then have to make their way past the outer membrane again. This, at the very least, would allow the *Acinetobacter* to prevent a continuous barrage of antibiotics, and by extension disabling them from playing their role (Vila et al., 2007; Yoon et al., 2015).

There are six families of multidrug efflux systems; the major facilitator superfamily (MFS), the resistance-nodulation-division (RND) family, the ATP binding cassette (ABC) family, the SMR family, the multidrug and toxic compound extrusion (MATE) family, and the drug/metabolite transporter (DMT) family. However, only the first three have been reported to be associated with *A. baumannii*, specifically (Perez et al., 2007; Rumbo et al., 2013). Most of the genes responsible for conferring this type of resistance to the pathogen were reported to be from other pathogens; *Salmonella*, *Pseudomonas* or *E. coli* (Fournier et al., 2006). The genes were found to be clustered together in a single genomic island of approximately 86 kb in length, which includes a few genes responsible for resistance against some types of heavy metals (Vila et al., 2007).

Although major facilitator superfamily does not normally in itself confer multidrug-resistance in *Acinetobacter*, it is especially useful in ribosomal protection. For example, the *TetA*, *TetB* and *TetM* resistance determinants present in *A. baumannii* grants the pathogen a tetracycline-specific efflux pump that would immediately remove traces of tetracycline and homologs. Tetracycline normally binds to the 30S ribosomal subunit of prokaryotes, which prevents the binding of aminoacyl-tRNA, and by extension prevents the synthesis of peptides (<http://pharmaxchange.info/press/2011/05/mechanism-of-action-of-tetracyclines/>).

A study on a 79 non-related strains has confirmed that only *TetA* and *TetB* efflux pump genes are expressed in *A. baumannii*, with occurrences of each gene being mutually exclusive from one another. *TetA* was identified to confer resistance against tetracycline, whereas *TetB* against minocycline (Guardabassi et al., 2000).

v) Biofilm-production

Efforts to better understand the survivability and extensive antimicrobial resistance found in *A. baumannii* have revealed a particular characteristic that is present in some strains of the species. Reports have frequently stated that certain clinically-associated pathogens are capable of generating a layer of protective material which substantially boosts not only their survivability, but also improves their pathogenicity. This biological defensive coating allows the bacteria to aggregate together, and is referred to as a biofilm, which guards them from the harsh surrounding environment (Tomaras et al., 2003; Kaliterna & Barisic-Goic, 2013; Longo et al., 2014). Biofilms have been defined as a collection of bacterial cells held together by an extracellular polymeric matrix composed of polysaccharides, proteins, DNA or a combination of any of the aforementioned materials (O'Toole et al., 2000; Donlan, 2002). Currently, the understanding towards the nature of biofilms is still lacking. Researchers have found that the population of bacteria that exist within the sheath of protective matrix acts as if a single multicellular organism. The mass of microorganisms encased within the matrix can be regarded as “highly social” and exhibit cell to cell communication (Gloag et al., 2012; Li & Tian, 2012; Boyle et al., 2013). It has been discovered that the bacterial population within the biofilm possess maximal nutrient acquisition capacity, as well as waste dispersal (Aswathanarayan & Vittal, 2013; Vasudevan, 2014).

Espinal *et al.* (2011) supports the claim that certain classes of *A. baumannii* that are capable of producing biofilm possess a higher survivability rate when exposed to prolonged periods of desiccation. This is especially true for *Acinetobacter baumannii*, which has been discovered to have the highest rate of survivability when cultured on dry surfaces.

As shown in **Figure 2.2**, it is evident that the production of biofilm by the bacteria significantly enhances its survivability under arid conditions. The non-biofilm-forming strains were only capable of maintaining viability for up to a maximum of approximately 18 days, whereas the biofilm-forming strains managed to survive twice as long (approximately 36 days) before the colony forming units diminish completely. It can also be observed that the rate of loss of viability differs between the two biofilm-forming and non-biofilm-forming strains.

Espinal et al. (2011) has also pointed out that the biofilm functions as a hydration barrier, isolating the interior of the matrix from the humidity variations in the surrounding environment. The biofilm itself was noted to be well hydrated, providing a level of humidity that is suitable to maintain the growth and viability of the cells present within it. This ensures prolonged survivability even in arid environments. There are also claims that the presence of the extracellular polysaccharide matrix is responsible for the enhanced acquisition of antimicrobial resistance (Espinal et al., 2012; Panesyan et al., 2015).

Figure 2.2: Survival Curve Comparison Between Biofilm-Forming (Ab033, ■; Ab053, ▲); and non-Biofilming-Forming (Ab001, ◆; Ab144, ●) Strains (Espinal et al., 2012)

vi) Quorum sensing

In addition to the aforementioned mechanisms, pathogens have also been reported to employ quorum sensing to both ensure survivability as well as exert virulence and pathogenic properties (Rutherford & Bassler, 2012). This mechanism employs the use of chemical signaling molecules known as autoinducers, which play a role in several activities including virulence regulation, exo-enzyme synthesis, biofilm formation, conjugation, cross-species symbiosis, motility, bioluminescence and antibiotic production (Kievit & Iglewski, 2000; Reading & Sperandio, 2005; Verma & Miyashiro, 2013).

Quorum sensing is essentially a two-component system, requiring a means of signal-production and a signal-reception and response (Eldar, 2011; González et al., 2001).

These autoinducers are typically divided into three classes; i) acylated homoserine lactose (AHLs), ii) peptides and, iii) furanosyl borate diester. Reports have indicated that Gram negative bacteria primarily rely on the first of these three classes. The AHLs are composed of a homoserine-lactone ring and an acyl chain of varying lengths, depending on the bacterial species. The specificity of these molecules is dictated by the length of the side-chain, resulting in a varied signaling system (Kang & Park, 2010; Taga & Bassler, 2003).

It was reported that Gram-negative Proteobacteria, typically possess highly conserved *luxI* and *luxR* homologs. In some cases, pathogens have evolved a more complex virulence mechanism through the use of these LasI/LasR homologs, as well as RhlI/RhlR homologs (Ivanova et al., 2013).

Figure 2.3: General Model of Acyl-Homoserine Lactone Signal Transduction in Gram-Negative Bacteria

The AHL signaling class is generally composed of LuxI/LuxR homologs. The LuxI-like homolog is an autoinducer synthase responsible for the production of AHL signaling molecules, which are then diffused to the outer extremities of the cell (**Figure 2.3**). The concentration of the signal increases with the cell density; the higher the bacterial population grows, the more concentrated the signal becomes. Once the AHL has reached a threshold concentration, they begin to diffuse back into the cell. Upon reentry, the signal will form a complex with the regulator protein synthesized by the LuxR-like homolog, and will subsequently bind to the target gene promoters. This effectively activates the target gene (Prashanth et al., 2012; Li & Tian, 2012).

3.5 INFECTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH *Acinetobacter baumannii*

Despite the various studies carried out all around the world, our understanding of the nature of the *A. baumannii* within the clinical as well as community setting has yet to be properly established. The collective clinical data from these studies shows that *A. baumannii* may exhibit not only the potential for an extended spectrum of resistance, but also a wide array of pathogenicity depending on the strain and site of infection. *A. baumannii* has been associated with many hospitals and community acquired infectious diseases as listed in **Table 2.1**. Skin and soft-tissue infection (SSTI) which is also known as necrotizing soft tissue infections (NSTI) and necrotizing fasciitis is caused by colonization of the *A. baumannii* on the host's skin. To date, the exact role of the pathogen in causing the SSTI is not well defined. However, a study by Guerrero *et al.* (2010) has revealed four unique factors of *A. baumannii* SSTI infections; i) the disease is commonly associated with bacteremia, ii) the host is usually experiencing co-morbidities (e.g. trauma, cirrhosis) , iii) complications may occur due to emergence of multidrug resistance as well as co-infection by different pathogens , and iv) a majority of cases have led to the requirement of debridement, following an approximate 30% rate of mortality (Guerrero et al., 2010). NSTI are infrequent but are highly lethal, resulting in necrotizing changes of the soft tissue compartment (i.e. muscle, deep fascia, superficial fascia, subcutaneous tissue and dermis) (Falade-Nwulia & O'Grady, 2011). Although extremely deadly, infection leading to SSTI/NSTI is relatively rare as it is normally associated with trauma (e.g. gunshot wounds and blunt abdominal trauma). However, it is possible for

SSTI to become commonplace within the clinical environment if left unchecked. On the other hand, gastrointestinal tract infection due to colonization of *A. baumannii* within the host's stomach is relatively common. The other *A. baumannii* associated infections include meningitis and pseudomeningitis, pneumonia, bacteremia and septicemia and urinary tract infection (Gusten et al., 2002; Spence et al., 2004; Cunha, 2010; Coyne et al., 2011; Pour et al., 2011).

A few studies have noted that the rate of infections caused by *A. baumannii* has been increasing in the past few years. And although most of the strains were observed to be of low virulence, the potential for infection is still present and should not be taken lightly. A study in Bosnia by Sisirak and Hukic that began in 2003 through 2010 has revealed an increase in the rate of infection and septicemic potential of *A. baumannii* (Sisirak & Hukic, 2012). Drug resistant microorganisms have also been reported in Iran in early 2012, and were reported to cause meningitis and ventriculitis (Aminzadeh & Yaghubi, 2012). Also, recently in Bangkok, Thailand, Sujinda and Pisud reported a fatal case of community-acquired bacteremic pneumonia caused by *A. baumannii*, despite exhibiting susceptibility *to in vitro* tests (Ruangchan & Siripaitoon, 2012). Indirectly, this indicates that the likelihood of virulence and pathogenesis does not necessarily require the initial acquisition of resistance. This also opens the possibility that virulent and infectious strains may arise in the community without warning.

Table 2.1
Diseases Caused by A. baumannii

Disease	References
Skin and soft-tissue infection (SSTI)	(Sebeny et al., 2008)
	(Guerrero et al., 2010)
	(Falade-Nwulia & O'Grady, 2011)
Necrotizing fasciitis	(Charnot-Katsikas et al., 2009)
	(Corradino et al., 2010)
Meningitis	(Jimenez-Mejias et al., 1997)
	(Chang, Lu, & Chuang, 2000)
	(Sacar et al., 2007)
	(Lowman et al., 2008)
	(Guardado et al., 2008)
Pseudomeningitis	(Cascio et al., 2010)
	(Gusten et al., 2002)
	(Jeong et al., 2011)

Pneumonia (VAP/HAP/CAP)	(Garnacho-Montero et al., 2005) (Leung et al., 2006) (Sebeny et al., 2008) (Ong et al., 2009) (Lee et al., 2013) (Al-Dabaibah et al., 2012)
Bacteremia	(Chen et al., 2003) (Sebeny et al., 2008) (Thom et al., 2010) (Guerrero et al., 2010) (Lee et al., 2013)
Gastrointestinal tract infection	(Shelburn III et al., 2008) (Roy et al., 2010) (Thom et al., 2010)
Urinary tract infection	(Spence et al., 2004) (Cunha, 2010) (Pour et al., 2011) (Coyne et al., 2011)

3.6 *A. baumannii* CASES IN MALAYSIA

In 2012, the Institute for Medical Research (IMR), Malaysia initiated the National Surveillance of Antibiotic Resistance (NSAR) for the purpose of improving and standardizing data field entry. Although, the NSAR archive incorporates antimicrobial resistance reports from 2002 to 2013 thus far, information preceding 2007 is less extensive in comparison to later data. At the time of this study, the NSAR 2014 report has yet to be finalized. Moreover, the report for 2006 is missing from the archive. As such, for the purpose of this study, only data from 2007 onwards was put into consideration.

Figure 2.4: Total Number of Bacterial Isolates from Hospitals in Malaysia

The total number of hospitals included in the NSAR report between 2007 and 2010 was only between 12 and 16, but the number has increased in later years. In 2011, a total of 36 hospitals were included in the final report, which subsequently increased to 37 and 38 hospitals in the following years (**Figure 2.4**). Evidently the number of isolates tested has also increased.

Figure 2.5: Percent of Antimicrobial Resistance in Malaysian Clinical *A. baumannii* Samples Reported from 2007 to 2013

In years 2007 and 2009, the percentage of antimicrobial resistance in *A. baumannii* isolates was recorded to be below 50% with regards to resistance to ciprofloxacin, imipenem and meropenem. Upwards of 2010 however, the percentage was reported to be well above the 50% (**Figure 2.5**). In 2013, the resistances towards the aforementioned drugs had reached 55.1%, 57.1% and 58.3%, respectively (**Table 2.2**), which were the highest reported percentages for each resistance thus far. This observed uptrend is an indication that in addition to the increasing number of cases involving *A. baumannii*, the number of resistant isolates is increasing in tandem.

Table 2.2.

A List of the Percentage of Resistance Observed Against the Antimicrobials and the Number of Clinical A. baumannii Samples Tested

Antimicrobial	2007		2008		2009		2010		2011		2012		2013	
	(%)	n	(%)	n	(%)	n								
Amikacin	29.2	4298	40.6	9283	39.3	8727	48.2	9238	49.9	16106	45.8	15892	46.1	15981
Amoxiclav	62.3	871	67.5	2336	63.6	1284	78.9	1335	72.7	3628	70.1	2631	71.4	2549
Ampicillin	94.7	890	90.6	1586	91.1	1226	70.7	1469	91.6	2262	90.8	2339	91.8	1733
Ampi/sulb	38.3	4241	43.2	8716	44.2	8618	51.7	8834	55.0	15813	53.2	14996	54.6	15202
cefepime	53.2	4302	53.6	4929	48.5	3758	58.8	4034	59.0	7236	60.1	7035	57.2	7261
cefoperazone	77.8	1448	74.5	2057	65.8	1306	77.5	1540	67.5	2717	72.5	2659	72.7	2166
sulperazone	14.4	3236	12.7	6581	33.4	7539	40.4	8461	42.3	14883	42.6	13119	41.0	13346
cefotaxime	75.4	921	68.8	2179	71.7	1794	74.2	1514	73.4	3579	78.8	4062	67.1	3561
ceftazidime	46.8	3987	49.8	9253	46.2	9144	55.7	9614	57.0	16196	55.4	16015	57.0	16033
ceftriaxone	83.2	802	72.1	2063	74.5	1704	73.9	1041	74.7	1653	72.1	2253	60.9	1742
cefuroxime	85.5	874	73.6	1428	72.3	1115	61.4	251	77.2	2166	78.8	2149	77.4	1667
Cephalexin	94.1	34	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a							
chloramph	79.6	54	86.9	526	85.5	934	78.4	190	61.1	211	85.5	1956	86.2	2788
ciprofloxacin	43.9	3880	48.9	9101	44.9	8758	53.9	9482	54.8	15532	52.9	15560	55.1	15916
gentamicin	36.4	4176	43.6	9265	42.4	8893	50.6	9540	53.4	16005	50.1	15507	51.2	15237
imipenem	46.6	4916	52.9	9242	47.0	8845	56.5	9351	56.6	15974	54.9	15837	57.1	16092
meropenem	47.7	2593	54.3	8185	47.9	9068	56.8	9481	57.4	15711	55.7	15555	58.3	15443
netilmicin	19.3	2093	36.1	4136	39.3	4448	48.6	5504	50.3	7871	50.4	9220	35.4	8597
nitrofurantoin	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	90.2	133	85.5	214	94.6	184	94.6	369
piperacillin	53.9	1685	54.2	3133	48.6	4678	59.0	5027	57.2	6992	59.2	4877	52.6	4104
pip tazo	47.5	2333	55.4	6993	n/a	7213	58.0	8448	58.2	14545	55.5	14358	51.6	14500
tetracycline	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	37.6	1241	26.2	545	49.6	839	46.6	1156	60.5	986
Trimeth/sulf	37.8	1446	44.9	2649	43.9	1673	57.6	1999	47.8	3882	40.2	6431	38.4	6714

n = number of clinical *A. baumannii* samples tested for antimicrobial resistance

% = percent of antimicrobial resistance reported in *A. baumannii*

Antimicrobials of interest in this study is highlighted in yellow

CHAPTER THREE

GENERAL MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1 OVERVIEW OF STUDY

Figure 3.1: Flow Chart of the Study Design

3.2 CHEMICAL, REAGENTS AND INSTRUMENTS

All chemicals, reagents and instruments used in this study are listed in **Table 3.1**.

Table 3.1
List of Chemicals, Reagents and Instruments Used

Bacterial culture	
Chemical/Reagents	Supplier
Mueller-Hinton broth	Merck Millipore, Massachusetts, USA
Mueller-Hinton agar	Merck Millipore, Massachusetts, USA
Glycerol	AMRESCO, Ohio, USA
0.5 McFarland standard	Becton Dickinson, New Jersey, USA
DNA extraction	
Chemical/Reagents	Supplier
DNA purification kit	PROMEGA, Wisconsin, USA
Gel cleanup kit	PROMEGA, Wisconsin, USA
DNA sequencing	
Chemical/Reagents	Supplier
TruSeq PE Cluster Kit v5-CS-GA	Illumina, California, USA
TruSeq RNA and DNA Sample Preparation Kits V2	Illumina, California, USA
TruSeq SBS Kit v5-GA	Illumina, California, USA
MiSeq Reagent Kit v3	Illumina, California, USA
PCR, gel electrophoresis and purification	
Chemical/Reagents	Supplier
Taq DNA polymerase 1U/μl	InvitrogenCorp., California, USA
10x PCR Buffer minus Mg	InvitrogenCorp., California, USA
50 mM magnesium chloride	InvitrogenCorp., California, USA
dNTP mix (10 mM)	RBC Bioscience Corp., Taiwan
Primers	Integrated DNA Technologies, Iowa, USA
Wizard SV Gel and PCR Clean-Up System	Promega Corp, Wisconsin, USA
Agarose LE analytical grade	Promega Corp, Wisconsin, USA
Gel loading dye blue (6x concentrated)	New England Biolabs Inc, USA
Ethidium bromide (10 mg/ml)	Promega Corp, Wisconsin, USA
100 bp DNA ladder	New England Biolabs Inc, USA
1 kb DNA ladder	New England Biolabs Inc, USA
EDTA, Disodium salt (Dihydrate)	Promega Corp, Wisconsin, USA
Tris-Base	Promega Corp, Wisconsin, USA
AMPure XP	Beckmen Coulter, California, USA
Spin Column (purification)	BioEasy Sdn. Bhd., Selangor, Malaysia
Instrument	
Instrument	Supplier
POLARstar Omega	BMG Labtech, Offenburg, Germany
TaKaRa PCR Thermal Cycler Dice™ (Gradient Model)	TaKaRa Bio Inc., Shiga, Japan
Sonicator	Sonoswiss SW12H, Ramsen, Switzerland
Qubit Fluorometer	Life Technologies, New York, USA
Bioanalyzer	Agilent Technologies, California, USA
GEL ELECTROPHORESIS	GEL ELECTROPHORESIS
Power PacBasic Power Supply	Biorad-Rad Laboratories, California, USA
Geliance 600 imaging system	PerkinElmer, Massachusetts, USA
Analytical balance TE2145	Sartorius AG, Goettingen, Germany
Centrifuge 5804 R	Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany
Centrifuge bench top refrigerated ALC	ALC, Heartfordshire, UK
Biophotometer	Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany
Autoclave (HVE-50)	Hirayama, Japan
NanoDrop Spectrophotometer	Thermo Scientific, Wilmington, USA

3.3 ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS

The list of antimicrobial discs used throughout the study is listed in **Table 3.2**.

Table 3.2

List of Antimicrobial Discs Used

Antimicrobial (concentration)	Supplier
Amikacin (30 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Gentamicin (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Netilmicin (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Streptomycin (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Azithromycin (15 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Clarithromycin (2 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Erythromycin (15 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Linezolid (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Chloramphenicol (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Nitrofurantoin (50 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Co-trimoxazole (25 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Rifampicin (2 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Levofloxacin (1 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Clindamycin (2 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Vancomycin (5 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Nalidixic acid (30 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Oxacillin (1 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Penicillin G (1 unit µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Piperacillin (30 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Cephalothin (30 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Cephazolin (30 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Imipenem (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Meropenem (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Ampicillin (25 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Cefotaxime (5 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Ceftazidime (10 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England
Ceftriaxone (5 µg)	MAST GROUP ltd, United Kingdom, England

The list of antimicrobial agents used throughout the study is listed in **Table 3.3**.

Table 3.3

List of Antimicrobials Used

Antimicrobial	Supplier
Ciproflo	Siu Guan Chem. Ind. Co., Ltd, Chia Yi, Taiwan
Imipenem (Tienam)	Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp, New Jersey, USA
Meropenem	Hospira Pty Ltd, Melbourne, Australia
Erythromycin lactobionate	Fisiopharma S.r.L, Salerno, Italy

3.4 PREPARATION OF CULTURE MEDIA

All broths and agars were obtained from Merck Millipore (Massachusetts, USA). Broths were prepared by dissolving the powder in distilled water according to the manufacturer's instructions. For ease of future use, broths meant for culture use were transferred into a clean universal bottle before sterilization by autoclaving. Broth

solutions meant for antimicrobial dilutions were prepared, sterilized and stored in Schott bottles. Agars were heated via either microwave or water bath prior to autoclaving to ensure a complete and even dissolution of the powder. All media are stored at 4°C after sterilization and adjusted to 37°C before use. The list of media used is as shown in **Table 3.1**.

3.5 ANTIBIOGRAM

The protocol for antibiogram assay is as shown in **Figure 3.2**.

Figure 3.2: Protocol Overview for Antibiogram Assay

3.5.1 Storage and Usage of Discs

All antimicrobial discs were stored at 4°C when not in use. Prior to usage, the discs were allowed to adjust to room temperature for about 2 hours. To reduce the risk of contamination, the disc tubes were removed from their cylindrical container via clean, sterile forceps.

3.5.2 Culture Preparation for Antibigram

Prior to inoculation, a fresh overnight (18 hours) culture was prepared, followed by a two-hour incubation in sterile MHB until an OD₆₀₀ of between 0.6 and 1.0 has been achieved. A sterile MHB was used as a blank, and a 0.5 MacFarland standard was used for QC. If the culture has not achieved the desired OD after two hours, the incubation was continued until its growth has reached a sufficient turbidity.

3.5.3 Inoculation Procedure

Before inoculation, the MHA intended for use was dried at 37°C for at least three hours or at 60°C for one hour. The prepared culture was briefly swirled to ensure an even distribution, and a sterile cotton swab was dipped into the culture. The tip of the swab was then pressed firmly against the dry inner wall of the bottle to remove excess broth. The surface of the MHA was swabbed three times, while the plate was rotated approximately 60° between each swabbing to ensure that the inoculum has been evenly distributed. The plate was allowed to dry briefly before applying the antimicrobial discs.

3.5.4 Application of Antimicrobial Discs

The MHA plates were first labeled accordingly, whereby an “x” was drawn at the back of the plate as a guide. The antimicrobial discs were carefully dropped onto the surface of the inoculated MHA using a pair of sterile forceps, and very lightly pressed down to ensure proper placement. The procedure was carried out under aseptic conditions.

3.5.5 Culture Conditions for Antibigram

All antibiogram plates were incubated at 37°C for a minimum of 18 hours.

3.5.6 Measurement of Antibiogram Results

All antibiogram were measured computationally. Images of the plates were taken, whereby the plates were placed on the lab bench, and an image-capturing device was placed on a platform constructed from two retort stands. The platform was leveled using a clinometer to avoid any skewing in the final image, and a ruler was placed on the bench as a reference scale. Once the image was taken, the zone of inhibitions (ZOI) were measured using a standardized “measurement ring” generated via Photoshop (**Figure 3.3**). The accuracy of the ring was cross-checked with the reference scale prior to each ZOI measurement.

Figure 3.3: A Screenshot of the ZOI “Measurement Ring” Generated via Photoshop

3.6 STORAGE OF ANTIMICROBIALS

All sealed/unopened antimicrobials were stored at room temperature until use. Antimicrobials that have been opened were sealed with parafilm and stored at 4°C in between use. The opened antimicrobials were kept on ice whenever taken out of the 4°C storage.

3.7 PREPARATION OF 60% GLYCEROL STOCK

Undiluted glycerol was first transferred to a clean universal bottle and heated to 60°C in a water bath in order to reduce its viscosity. Once heated, 6 ml of the glycerol

was then transferred into a clean universal bottle containing 4 ml of distilled water to make a stock 60% glycerol solution. The solution was then sterilized via autoclaving.

3.8 STORAGE OF SAMPLES

For long term storage at -80°C , a fresh overnight culture of the sample was first prepared. A total of 500 μl of the sample was transferred into a clean, sterile microcentrifuge tube, followed by an addition of 500 μl of sterile 60% glycerol. The mixture was then gently pipetted a few times to ensure an even distribution, and was slowly adjusted to its storage temperature by incubation at 4°C for one hour, followed by another hour at -20°C , and finally transferred to -80°C .

3.9 REVIVAL OF STORED ISOLATES

Isolates stored at -80°C were revived by first slowly adjusting the stock cultures to room temperature by incubation at -20°C for one hour, 4°C for one hour and at room temperature for another hour. Using a micropipette, 50 μl of the stock culture was then inoculated into a sterile MHB that was previously adjusted to 37°C . The inoculum was then incubated at 37°C overnight.

3.10 EXTRACTION OF DNA FROM BACTERIAL CULTURES

An overnight culture was prepared in MHB. One ml was transferred into a 1.5 μl microcentrifuge tube, which was then centrifuged at 14,000 xg for 2 minutes. The supernatant was removed, and 600 μl of nuclei lysis solution was added. The pellet was gently pipetted until the cells have resuspended. The solution was then incubated at 80°C for five minutes in a pre-heated water bath, following a cool down to room temperature. Three microliters of RNase solution was added to the sample, and was inverted five times to ensure an even mixture. The sample was then incubated at 37°C for 60 minutes, after which it was allowed to cool down to room temperature again. Two hundred microliters of protein precipitation solution was then transferred to the sample, and was vigorously vortexed for 20 seconds. The mixture was incubated on ice for five minutes, followed by a centrifugation at 14,000 xg for three minutes. The supernatant was transferred to a clean, sterile 1.5 μl microcentrifuge tube containing 600 μl of isopropanol. The mixture was then inverted until the DNA strand was visible. Upon which the DNA has been made observable by the naked eye, the mixture was centrifuged at 14,000 xg for 2 minutes.

After which, the supernatant was carefully poured out. Any excess supernatant remaining in the tube was carefully pipette out. Six hundred microliters of freshly prepared 70% alcohol was then added to the DNA pellet, and the tube was inverted several times. The sample was then centrifuged at 14,000 xg for 2 minutes, followed by a careful aspiration of the ethanol. The DNA pellet was allowed to air-dry for a maximum of 15 minutes. Any excess ethanol droplets were pipetted out to facilitate the drying process. One hundred microliters of DNA rehydration solution was then added to the dried DNA pellet, and was stored at 4°C overnight. The final product was stored at -80°C until use.

3.11 DETERMINATION OF DNA CONCENTRATION AND PURITY

The NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, Wilmington, USA) was first primed before use. Nuclease-free water was used to wash the pedestal, and wiped dry accordingly. The DNA rehydration solution was used as blank, and the initial readings were recorded at 260 nm and 280 nm. The undiluted samples were measured in triplicates at the same wavelength. The average value of the triplicate readings was calculated and recorded accordingly.

3.12 RECONSTITUTION OF PRIMERS AND PREPARATION OF WORKING STOCK

All primers were reconstituted according to the manufacturer's instructions. Once received, the lyophilized primers were briefly centrifuged. Nuclease-free water was then added to each tube as directed by the manufacturer (OD x 10) resulting in a final concentration of 100 µM (100 picomoles). The solution was then pipetted gently to ensure a proper dissolution, followed by an overnight incubation at -20°C. Once reconstituted, the primers were then diluted into their working stock of five (5) picomoles using the standard $M_1V_1=M_2V_2$ formula.

3.13 PCR MIX AND PARAMETERS

All PCR reactions were prepared according to **Table 3.4**. A 1x reaction was used for visualization in gel electrophoresis with no further downstream applications, while samples intended for amplicon sequencing were run using the 4x reaction.

Table 3.4
Master Mix Formula for PCR Reactions

Reagent	Concentration		Volume (μ l)	
	Stock	Final	1x reaction	4x reaction
Sterile dH ₂ O	n/a	n/a	17.0	68.0
Buffer	10 x	1 x	2.5	10.0
MgCl ₂	50 mM	1.5 - 4 μ M	1.0	4.0
dNTP	10 mM	200 μ M	0.5	2.0
Forward primer	100 μ M	5 μ M	1.0	4.0
Reverse primer	100 μ M	5 μ M	1.0	4.0
Taq polymerase	5U/ μ l	0.1 - 0.4 μ l	1.0	4.0
DNA Template	50-100 ng/ μ l	50-100ng/ μ l	1.0	1.0
Total			25.0	100.0

All PCR runs were performed using the parameters described in **Table 3.5**. Primers were all designed to accommodate a PCR run at an annealing temperature of 60°C for ease of performing PCR runs with varying primers.

Table 3.5
Thermalcycler Settings for All PCR Runs Performed in the Study

Step	Temperature (°C)	Time (seconds)	Number of cycles
Initial denaturation	95	30	1
Denaturation	94	30	30
Annealing	59	30	
Extension	72	30	
Final extension	72	180	1 Hold
	25	30	

All PCR products were immediately visualized via gel electrophoresis after completion of PCR cycle. Otherwise, the amplicons were stored at 4°C until further use.

3.14 GEL ELECTROPHORESIS

All gel electrophoresis runs were performed using a 0.8% agarose gel, prepared using 1x TBE. One microliter of the DNA sample was loaded after mixing with two microliters of the loading dye, and six microliters of the DNA ladder used in each run. The gel runs were set to 130 volts for 45 minutes. Once completed, the gel was viewed using the Geliance 600 imaging system (Perkin Elmer, Massachusetts, USA) accordingly.

CHAPTER FOUR
SELECTION AND GENOME SEQUENCING ANALYSIS OF A SUSCEPTIBLE
***Acinetobacter baumannii* ISOLATE**

4.1 INTRODUCTION

A. baumannii has long been included in numerous reports as a nosocomial agent that thrives despite employment of preventive measures (Chang et al., 2014; José-Luis et al., 2001; Bergogne-Bérézen & Towner, 1996). Moreover, this is currently true for hospitals on a global scale, making this pathogen relevant throughout the world (Güven et al., 2014; Evans et al., 2013; Hakyemez et al., 2013). Under normal circumstances, it is understood that most *A. baumannii* strains are not inherently pathogenic, with several reports stating that they can be found even on the human skin (Peleg et al., 2008). Their pathogenic nature is usually observed in immunocompromised patients, typically in Intensive Care Units (ICUs). This is exacerbated by its innate ability to acquire drug resistance through several means (Camp & Tatum, 2010).

For decades, researchers have attempted to understand the key factors that allow this pathogen to proficiently attain antibiotic resistance (Manchanda et al., 2010). Apart from protein and expression studies, the genomics approach has proven to give detailed insight on the basis of this ability. Several reports have covered the genomic modifications that the pathogen undergoes in several strains under either *in vitro* or *in vivo* settings (Fournier et al., 2006; Honsey et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2014). Though the results are plentiful, several questions still remain unanswered. These studies often only cover the final stages of the genomic modifications, which are then compared with the susceptible variant. Studies covering the day-by-day changes in susceptible strains are scarce, and even more so in *A. baumannii* specifically.

It is true that the final changes observed within a resistant variant can give enough data on the adaptation mechanisms leading to resistance. However, due to the unstable nature of natural genetic modifications, it is unlikely that the bacterial genome can undergo multiple mutations at a single instance (Adams et al., 2008; Snitkin et al., 2013). As such, theoretically, the various mutations observed in the resistant genomes in

previous reports have occurred in stages. Highlighting these step-by-step mutations elucidate a key factor in further understanding the mechanism in which these genetic adaptations take place. Such information would then possibly reveal new targets to halt the adaptation mechanism leading towards resistance.

The genome is a blueprint containing all the factors necessary for the bacterial phenotype to manifest. And under situations of stress, either slight modification would be made to the blueprint, or new genetic elements would be incorporated in order to better endure the new condition (Valenzuela et al., 2007). It stands to reason that the genome of a susceptible strain would be a suitable blueprint for studying genomic adaptation under stress as it increases the likelihood of new adaptive mechanisms to be discovered under controlled conditions (Teo et al., 2015).

It is understood that the adaptive modifications vary under different stressful conditions. The selective pressures brought on by different antibiotics would in theory incite drug-specific stress responses. Presence of fluoroquinolones for example would induce DNA-related selective pressure, which would in turn stimulate modifications specifically towards any DNA-maintenance mechanisms (Chopra & Galande, 2011; Park et al., 2011). There is also the potential of drug expulsion activity to combat this pressure, as it requires the more simplistic mechanism of over expressing antibiotic efflux pumps (Okusu et al., 1996; Vila et al., 2007). This may or may not result in mutations in the genome of the challenged pathogen. On the other hand, the presence of genes encoding drug-metabolizing enzymes would be particularly beneficial in combating specific drug classes. The blaOXA genes for example express beta-lactamase which specifically targets carbapenems (Dalla-Costa et al., 2003; Santillana et al., 2007; Barin et al., 2013). Acquisition of these genes will undoubtedly be crucial in allowing survivability in the presence of these last resort drugs, effectively improving the pathogen's virulence.

These varying mechanisms indicate that a single pathogen is able to shift its genomic or metabolic activity in order to ensure survivability. As such, it would be prudent to observe and analyze the changes undergone in a given sample under different conditions to better understand its varying mechanisms. Here we aim to acquire a susceptible strain with the potential for adapting to stresses brought on by three different

classes of antimicrobials resulting in; i) DNA modification, ii) efflux activity, and iii) utilization of a drug-metabolizing gene.

The aims here were; i) to acquire an *A. baumannii* isolate susceptible to three different classes of antimicrobials; ii) to sequence and annotate the genome of the susceptible parent strain; and iii) to determine the presence of inherent resistance determinants in the parent strain.

4.2 METHODS

Figure 4.1: Overview of Methodology

4.2.1 Revival of Stored Isolates

Twenty-five clinical *A. baumannii* isolates stored in -80°C (and in 30% glycerol) were slowly adapted to room temperature by incubating at -20°C (1 hour), 4°C (1 hour) and room temperature (1 hour). A loopful of the stock culture was then inoculated in clean, sterile Mueller Hinton Broths (MHB) and incubated overnight at 37°C in a shaking incubator.

4.2.2 Confirmation of Purity

The purity of the cultures was tested via dilution streaking on Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA). Colony formation was observed, and Gram staining was performed to confirm a uniform morphology.

4.2.3 Antimicrobial Resistance Profiling of 25 *A. baumannii* Isolates

Upon confirmation of purity, the samples were then tested for antimicrobial susceptibility. Fresh overnight cultures of all 25 samples were prepared. After which, a 2-hour culture was prepared for the antimicrobial susceptibility assay. The OD_{600} of the cultures were measured and confirmed to be between values 0.6 and 1.0. Each sample was then swabbed onto seven freshly prepared MHA plates. Once the excess moisture in the swabbed culture has dried, the antibiotic discs were carefully placed onto the plates according to **Figure 4.2**. The plates were then incubated overnight at 37°C . The image-capture procedure is as described in chapter 2. The platform used for the image capture was maintained at the same height and position throughout the entire process to reduce error.

Figure 4.2: List and Orientation of the Antibiotic Discs Used in the Antibiogram Assay for the 25 *A. baumannii* Clinical Isolates

4.2.4 Preparation of Genomic DNA

The genomic DNA (gDNA) of the susceptible *A. baumannii* isolate was extracted from an overnight culture grown in Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB). The DNA extraction was performed using the Wizard[®] Genomic DNA Purification Kit Protocol (Promega, USA).

4.2.5 Preparation of DNA Library

The DNA was then fragmented via sonication using the sonicator (Sonoswiss SW12H, Ramsen, Switzerland) at 38 kHz for 6 minutes, with the 'boost' setting on. A gel electrophoresis was then carried out on the fragmented DNA. Once the DNA was confirmed to be of highest concentration at the target regions (400-600 bp), the fragmented DNA was subjected to downstream protocol. Using the kits and instructions provided by Illumina (California, USA), the sample was then subjected to end-repair, A-tailing, adapter ligation, and amplification via PCR. A quality check of the sample was performed via Qubit Fluorometer (Life Technologies Corporation, New York, USA) and Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, USA) to ensure the amount of DNA available is sufficient for the following procedures.

The cluster generation of the sample was performed based on the TruSeq Cluster Generation Reagent Preparation Guide (Illumina, California, USA). PhiX was used as the control, as suggested by the supplier (Illumina, California, USA).

4.2.6 Genome Sequencing via Illumina GA IIx

Genome sequencing was performed following the Standard Operation Protocol developed in the Integrative Pharmacogenomics Institute (iPROMISE), as well as the general procedure provided by Illumina (California, USA).

4.2.7 Quality Check of Sequencing Output

The quality of the sequencing output was analyzed using the FastQC and SolexaQA software (Cox et al., 2010; Andrews, 2012). Once the quality has been confirmed, the Ab00 sequencing output was assembled and annotated as described in the following procedure.

4.2.8 *De novo* Assembly of Sequencing Output

The licensed software, CLCbio and two third-party software; VelvetOptimiser-2.2.5 and SOAPdenovo V2.04 were used in the *de novo* assembly of the sequencing reads (Zerbino & Birney, 2008; Chu et al., 12). In the VelvetOptimiser assembly, the kmer range was determined to be between 19 (the lowest possible value) and 99 (the highest possible value). A total of four threads were allowed to run simultaneously to optimize the runtime. The optimal kmer was selected based on the output given by the algorithm. The SOAPdenovo assembly was run using a kmer range between 31 and 99. The optimal kmer was decided by comparing the assembly output, and selecting the file yielding the lowest contig number and highest N₅₀. The outputs from both software were compared and the optimally assembled output was used in downstream analysis (Beijing Genomics Institute, 2010; Victorian Bioinformatics Consortium, 2012).

4.2.9 OSLay Ordering Comparisons

In order to generate the syntenic layout via OSLay, coordinate files (*.coords) necessary were first generated using nucmer. The coordinates were generated using four *A. baumannii* references; ACICU, AYE, ATCC 17978 and SDF.

Once completed, the assembly output (*.scafseq) generated via SOAPdenovo and coordinate files (*.coords) were fed into OSLay. The visual output generated using each *A. baumannii* reference was compared. The efficiency of the OSLay ordering and orienting capacity was measured based on the number of supercontigs, scaffolds, and contigs that were aligned in the syntenic layout. The assembly returning the optimal synteny, defined by the minimal amount of gaps and inverted sequences visible was prioritized (Richter et al., 2007).

4.2.10 Annotation of the Optimally Ordered Sequence

Once the optimal layout was determined, the output (*.supercontigs) was exported and stitched together into a single pseudomolecule by adding 150 ambiguous nucleotides (N's) between each contig (Munoz et al., 2010; Roodt et al., 2012; Cai et al., 2011). The pseudomolecules were then submitted to RAST and BASys for annotation. Upon completion, the annotation data from both sites were exported and stored locally for ease of downstream analysis and backup purposes. The data from the RAST

annotation service was used to determine the virulence and resistance determinants present in Ab00, whereas the BASys visual output was used to examine the genes within proximity of the selected determinants.

4.2.11 Submission of Genome Data to NCBI

The assembled reads were submitted to the NCBI database under the BioProject ID; PRJNA185400. The accession number for this submission is listed in **Appendix C**.

4.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.3.1 Confirmation of Purity

Upon confirmation of sample viability after an overnight culture in MHB, the samples were cultured on Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) overnight. The plates were observed, and uniform colonies were detected in all 25 samples. For further confirmation, colonies were randomly selected from each plate, and Gram staining was performed. All colonies exhibited the same morphology; Gram negative coccobacillus, as shown in the representative image in **Figure 4.3**.

Figure 4.3: Representative Gram Staining Results of the 25 Isolates (100 x Magnification)

4.3.2 Antimicrobial Resistance Profiling of 25 Isolates

The results of the antibiogram revealed that several *A. baumannii* strains are extensively resistant, showing a lack of zone of inhibition when exposed to all of the antibiotic discs. Samples H.Ab3, H.Ab15, H.Ab17, and H.Ab21-24 exhibited 100% resistance (27 out of 27 discs) where no visible Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) was observed, with the exception of sample H.Ab24 showing a 7 mm ZOI diameter when exposed to rifampicin. Six isolates show an extended resistance, with some susceptibilities in more than 50% of the discs used, whereas 11 isolates show the least amount of resistance profiles observed, at less than 50% of the discs used.

Among the list of antibiotics used, there was a lack of reported standards for ampicillin, cefotaxime, ceftazidime, ceftriaxone, azithromycin, clarithromycin and cotrimoxazole. As such, for these discs, only samples showing complete lack of zone of inhibitions was considered as resistant, whereas any interpretations were withheld in samples showing any visible ZOI. Complete resistance against chloramphenicol, linezolid, nitrofurantoin, vancomycin, penicillin G and cephalosporin was observed in all of the *A. baumannii* isolates.

From the antibiogram results, several samples were noted to be suitable as the susceptible parent strain for the whole genome sequencing. Sample Ab00 was selected due to its notable susceptibility towards erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem. This confirms potential resistance induction targets for two mechanisms; efflux and beta-lactam activity. For the third induction target, susceptibility towards ciprofloxacin (10 µg) was tested using the same antibiogram method, only on sample Ab00. The results (not shown) show a ZOI of 29 mm, indicating susceptibility. This confirms the third resistance induction target.

Table 4.1

Antimicrobial Resistance Profile of the 25 A. baumannii Isolates Using Disc Diffusion

Antibiotic	Disc	Ab00		H.Ab1		H.Ab2		H.Ab3		H.Ab4		H.Ab5		H.Ab6		H.Ab7		H.Ab8		H.Ab9		H.Ab10		H.Ab11	
Amikacin	AK30C	2.18	S	2.3	S	2.3	S	-	R	2	S	1.8	S	2.1	S	0.8	R	2	S	2.1	S	1.8	S	1.8	S
Gentamicin	GM10C	2	S	1.9	S	2.2	S	-	R	1.9	S	1.8	S	2	S	0.8	R	1.8	S	1.8	S	1.8	S	1.6	R
Netilmicin	NET10	1.93	S	1.8	S	2.2	S	-	R	1.8	S	1.8	S	2	S	0.8	R	1.7	S	1.8	S	1.6	S	1.5	R
Streptomycin	S10C	1.7	S	-	R	1.4	S	-	R	1.2	S	1.1	I	1.5	S	0.9	R	1.8	S	1.6	S	0.7	R	1.4	S
Azithromycin	ATH15C	2.43	x	-	R	2.4	x	-	R	2.1	x	2	x	2	x	2	x	2.3	x	2.1	x	1.9	x	1.7	x
Clarithromycin	CLA2C	1.5	x	-	R	1.2	x	-	R	1.4	x	1.2	x	1.1	x	1	x	1.3	x	1.1	x	1.1	x	1	x
Erythromycin	E15C	2.4	S	-	R	1.6	I	-	R	2	S	1.4	I	1.5	I	1.3	R	1.6	I	1.6	I	1.5	I	1.5	I
Linezolid	LZD10C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Chloramphenicol	C10C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Nitrofurantoin	NI50C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Co-trimoxazole	TS25C	2.3	x	-	x	1.8	x	-	R	1.8	x	2.1	x	1.2	x	1.3	x	1.3	x	1.6	x	1.6	x	1.4	x
Rifampicin	RP2C	-	R	1	x	0.8	x	-	R	0.7	x	0.8	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	0.7	x	-	R
Levofloxacin	LEV1C	1.87	I	1.6	x	2.3	x	-	R	2.4	x	2.6	x	1.8	x	2	x	2	x	1.8	x	1.8	x	1.6	x
Clindamycin	CD2C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Vancomycin	VA5C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Nalidixic acid	NA30C	1.6	I	1.5	x	2	x	-	R	1.8	x	2.1	x	1.7	x	1.6	x	1.8	x	1.6	x	1.6	x	1.4	x
Oxacillin	OX1C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Penicillin G	PG1C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Piperacillin	PRL30C	1.32	U	-	R	2.6	x	-	R	1.4	x	1.6	x	1.4	x	1.2	x	1.2	x	1.1	x	1.2	x	1.3	x
Cephalothin	KF30C	-	R	-	R	1.1	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Cephazolin	CZ30C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Imipenem	IMI10C	2.73	S	1.3	R	1.7	R	-	R	2.7	S	2.4	S	3	S	3	S	2.8	S	2.8	S	3	S	3.1	S
Meropenem	MEM10C	2.37	S	0.7	R	1.2	R	-	R	2.6	S	2.5	S	2	I	2.3	S	2.3	S	2.2	S	2	I	2.2	S
Ampicillin	AP25C	1.7	x	-	R	2.1	x	-	R	1.4	x	1.4	x	1.4	x	1.6	x	1.2	x	1.2	x	1.3	x	1.3	x
Cefotaxime	CTX5C	0.75	x	-	R	1.2	x	-	R	1.1	x	1	x	0.9	x	1	x	0.9	x	1	x	0.9	x	1	x
Ceftazidime	CAZ10C	1.52	x	-	R	1.6	x	-	R	1.6	x	1.3	x	1.3	x	1.4	x	1.4	x	1.3	x	1.2	x	1.6	x
Ceftriaxone	CRO5C	0.7	x	-	R	1.1	x	-	R	1	x	1	x	0.7	x	1	x	0.7	x	0.7	x	0.7	x	0.8	x

Antibiotic	Disc	H.Ab13		H.Ab14		H.Ab15		H.Ab16		H.Ab17		H.Ab18		H.Ab19		H.Ab20		H.Ab21		H.Ab22		H.Ab23		H.Ab24		H.Ab25	
Amikacin	AK30C	1.8	S	2.1	S	-	R	2.3	S	-	R	1.9	S	1.9	S	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Gentamicin	GM10C	1.6	R	-	R	-	R	2.2	S	-	R	-	R	-	R	1.6	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Netilmicin	NET10	1.4	R	1.3	R	-	R	2.1	S	-	R	1.2	R	1.4	R	1.3	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Streptomycin	S10C	1.5	S	-	R	-	R	1	I	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Azithromycin	ATH15C	2	x	-	R	-	R	2.3	x	-	R	1.8	x	1.8	x	2.1	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Clarithromycin	CLA2C	1	x	-	R	-	R	1.1	x	-	R	1.3	x	1.1	x	1.3	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Erythromycin	E15C	1.3	R	-	R	-	R	2.6	S	-	R	1.7	I	1.5	I	1.8	S	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Linezolid	LZD10C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Chloramphenicol	C10C	-	R	-	R	-	R	1.9	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	0.8	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Nitrofurantoin	NI50C	-	R	-	R	-	R	1.2	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Co-trimoxazole	TS25C	1.3	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Rifampicin	RP2C	-	R	0.8	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	0.7	x	-	R	0.9	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	0.7	x
Levofloxacin	LEV1C	1.6	x	-	R	-	R	2.2	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	0.7	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Clindamycin	CD2C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Vancomycin	VA5C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Nalidixic acid	NA30C	1.4	x	-	R	-	R	2.2	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Oxacillin	OX1C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Penicillin G	PG1C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Piperacillin	PRL30C	1.2	x	-	R	-	R	1.9	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Cephalothin	KF30C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Cephazolin	CZ30C	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Imipenem	IMI10C	3	S	1.2	R	-	R	3.3	S	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Meropenem	MEM10C	2.3	S	1	R	-	R	1.8	I	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Ampicillin	AP25C	1.2	x	-	R	-	R	2	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Cefotaxime	CTX5C	0.8	x	-	R	-	R	1.6	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Ceftazidime	CAZ10C	1.5	x	-	R	-	R	2	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R
Ceftriaxone	CRO5C	0.7	x	-	R	-	R	1.6	x	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R	-	R

S - Susceptible **U** - Undetermined
I - Intermediate - - No ZOI observed
R - Resistant **x** - No interpretation available

The antimicrobials of interest in this study is highlighted in red

4.3.3 Whole-Genome Sequencing Output of the Susceptible Ab00 Isolate

The sequencing data of the samples were converted from the basecall format (*.bcl) to the fastq format (*.fastq) using the CASAVA software and following the user manual. The quality of the fastq (*.Fastq) output of the sequencing run was checked using FastQC. In order to remove the low quality reads, the sequences were trimmed using DynamicTrim under the default settings. The quality of the reads before and after the process is as shown in (Figure 4.4). The overview of the sequencing output is as shown in Table 4.2.

Figure 4.4: Sequencing Quality of the Susceptible *A. baumannii* Isolate. (a) and (b) Show the raw, Untrimmed Quality of the Sequencing Reads, While (c) and (d) Show the Read Qualities after Processing Using DynamicTrim

Table 4.2.
Sequencing Output of the Susceptible A. baumannii Isolate

	Read 1			Read2		
	Total sequences	Sequence length	%GC	Total sequences	Sequence length	%GC
Untrimmed	1956000	101	41	1956000	101	41
Trimmed	1928919	25-101	41	1923669	25-101	41

4.3.4 *De novo* Assembly output of Susceptible Isolate

Upon confirmation of trimmed read qualities, the sequences were assembled using the SOAPdenovo software. Individual assembly runs were done using kmer values of 31 and 99. The N50 and number of contigs in the assembly output were then compiled in **Table 4.3**. From the output, the optimal kmer was determined to be 53, with an N50 of 104215 and a total of 467 contigs. It should be noted that the trough at kmer 61 is due to a “segmentation fault” encountered by SOAPdenovo as shown in the same figure. But due to the value being within a downtrend of N50, this discrepancy was disregarded (**Figure 4.5**).

Figure 4.5: The N50 and Total Contigs Produced by the SOAPdenovo Assembler

Table 4.3
The Final Output of the Optimal Kmer Assembly

Output	value
Scaffold number	64
In-scaffold contig number	467
Total scaffold length	3169664
Average scaffold length	49526
Filled gap number	5
Longest scaffold	216702
Scaffold and singleton number	294
Scaffold and singleton length	3647795
Average length	12407
N50	104215
N90	25763
Weak points	0

4.3.5 Ordering and Reorienting of assembled sequences

Once the optimal kmer has been determined, and the assembly has been completed, the scaffold file generated (*.scafseq) was aligned with four references; *A.baumannii* strains ACICU, ATCC 17978, AYE and SDF. An added parameter (-coords) was included in the command line to generate the *.coords file necessary for the OSLay run. The output of the OSLay run is as shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6: Syntenic Layout of Sample Ab00 Against Reference Strains ACICU, ATCC 17978, AYE and SDF

Based on the dotplot generated by OSLay, it can be deduced that Ab00 has the highest synteny to references *A. baumannii* ACICU, ATCC 17978 and SDF. While the first three shows a relatively distinct diagonal line, the layout generated using reference SDF resulted in a dispersed dotplot, indicating low synteny with said reference. Moreover, the dotplot generated is shorter than the former three, suggesting that a significant number of reads were unmatched. This is likely due to the absence of virulence and/or resistance-related genes present in the other strains. The ACICU and AYE layout, although of good quality, still presents discrepancies in the form of large translocations and inversions, respectively. The alignment with ATCC 17978 appears to be the most optimal as it has the least disparity in the dotplot. However, as the ATCC strain lacks the resistance and virulence determinants present in either ACICU or AYE, it was decided that the layout using reference AYE be used in the downstream analysis instead, as it lacks the large breakpoint present in the layout using ACICU.

4.3.6 Overview of Genome Annotation

Once the ordering and orienting of the Ab00 contigs have been completed, the supercontig sequences were exported. The multiFASTA file was then merged into a single FASTA file by manually removing the individual headers, and replacing them with 150 ambiguous nucleotides using a text editor. The merged file was submitted to RAST and BASys for annotation. The output of the annotations is summarized in **Table 4.4**. The number of genes annotated by RAST and BASys are 3369 and 3954, respectively. RAST has also identified the number of RNA's (67) and categorized the annotated genes under 445 subsystems. However, that number covers only 51% of the entire set of determinants, leaving 49% uncategorized in any subsystems (**Figure 4.7**).

Table 4.4
Ab00 RAST and BASys Annotation output overview

Sample	Annotation overview					
	RAST			BASys		
	Genome length	# of genes annotated	# of RNAs	# of Subsystems	Genome length	# of genes annotated
Ab00	3937175	3369	67	445	3937175	3954

A brief overview of the annotations reported by RAST reveals that a majority of the genes reported are grouped under the “Amino Acids and Derivatives” feature, adding up to 412 out of the 2634 features. A total of 282, 255 and 218 determinants classified under the “carbohydrates”, “cofactors, vitamins, prosthetic, groups, pigments”, and “protein metabolism” were identified in the genome, signifying an emphasis in the utilization of those factors in the Ab00. There were no determinants categorized under the “motility and chemotaxis” and “photosynthesis” features. This, tallies with the well-documented non-motile phenotype. However, several reports have also stated that the pathogen is capable of “twitching motility” attributed by the type IV pili (Mattick, 2002; Harding et al., 2013). To confirm this, the RAST SEED viewer was further scrutinized. Under the “Browse Genome” page, the term “type IV” was selected in the “Function” filter.

From the search, 20 genes associated with type IV pilus production were identified. Three copies of pilA genes were detected, whereas the other pil genes do not

have duplicates. The same search was done under the “Features in Subsystems” tab under the “Subsystems Information” in order to determine the Category and Subcategory of the listed genes. The search returned 23 features listed under the “Membrane Transport” category, “Protein and nucleoprotein secretion system, Type IV” Subcategory and “Type IV pilus” Subsystem. A total of 17 “Roles” were identified by RAST, where four “Roles” contain two features, and a single “Role” (Type IV pilin PilA) contains three features. The results of the search are as shown in **Table 4.5**.

Figure 4.7.: RAST SEED Viewer Overview of Ab00

Table 4.5

The List of “Roles” and “Features” Identified by RAST Categorized Under the “Membrane Transport” Category, “Protein and Nucleoprotein Secretion System” Subcategory, and “Type IV” Subsystem

Role	Features
Type IV fimbrial assembly, ATPase PilB	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1001
Type IV pilus biogenesis protein PilQ	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1489
Type IV fimbrial biogenesis protein PilX	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1511
Type IV fimbrial biogenesis protein FimT	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1508, fig 6666666.98826.peg.1800
N-methyltransferase (EC 2.1.1.-)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1003
3-dehydroquinate synthase (EC 4.2.3.4)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1491
Type IV pilus biogenesis protein PilO	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1487
Type IV fimbrial biogenesis protein PilY1	fig 6666666.98826.peg.608, fig 6666666.98826.peg.1512
Type IV fimbrial assembly protein PilC	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1002
Type IV pilus biogenesis protein PilP	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1488
Twitching motility protein PilT	fig 6666666.98826.peg.510, fig 6666666.98826.peg.511
Type IV fimbrial biogenesis protein PilV	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1509
Type IV pilin PilA	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1499, fig 6666666.98826.peg.1513, fig 6666666.98826.peg.1514
Leader peptidase (Prepilin peptidase) (EC 3.4.23.43)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1003
Type IV fimbrial biogenesis protein PilW	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1510
Multimodular transpeptidase-transglycosylase (EC 2.4.1.129) (EC 3.4.-.-)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1483, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2375
Type IV pilus biogenesis protein PilM	fig 6666666.98826.peg.148

The 23 different pilin-related determinants detected in the Ab00 genome suggest that the RAST categorization method might require some curation before coming to a conclusion. The fact that the “Twitching motility protein PilT” role in feature “fig|6666666.98826.peg.1002” was not listed under the motility subsystems further supports the theory that gene functions are more complicated than initially thought.

From the annotation report also listed 25 determinants as “Phages, Prophages, Transposable elements, Plasmids”. Out of which are 15 phages and prophage components (tail proteins, packaging machinery, tail proteins 2, tail fiber proteins and capsid proteins), and 11 transposable elements (CBSS-203122.12.peg.188).

Based on the information available in a webpage provided by The SEED the CBSS-203122.12.peg.188 subsystem includes set of 18 functional roles abbreviated as R1-R8 (http://www.nmpdr.org/FIG/subsys.cgi?user=&ssa_name=CBSS-203122.12.peg.188&request=show_ssa). Within the subsystem, only two *Acinetobacter* strains is listed; *A. baumannii* ATCC 17978 (Genome ID 400667.4) and *Acinetobacter*

sp. ADP1 (Genome ID 62977.3). Between the two, the former lists 11 features, which tallies with the features accounted in the Ab00 CBSS-203122.12.peg.188 subsystem. The functional roles reported in the Ab00 RAST annotation is as shown in **Table 4.6**

Table 4.6.

The Functional Roles Included Under the CBSS-203122.12.peg.188 Subsystem as Reported in the Ab00 RAST Annotation Details

Abbrev.	Feature	Functional Role
R1	fig 400667.4.peg.223 fig 400667.4.peg.697	TniB NTP-binding protein
R2	fig 400667.4.peg.221 fig 400667.4.peg.222	TniA putative transposase
R3	n/a	FIGfam050825
R4	n/a	Resolvase/Integrase TinR protein
R5	n/a	ISPsy4, transposition helper protein
R6	fig 400667.4.peg.224 fig 400667.4.peg.696	MII9366 protein
R7	n/a	TniQ
R8	fig 400667.4.peg.219 fig 400667.4.peg.231	ComM-related protein
R9	fig 400667.4.peg.219	MG(2+) CHELATASE FAMILY PROTEIN
R10	fig 400667.4.peg.231 fig 400667.4.peg.695	Transposase OrfAB, subunit B
R11	fig 400667.4.peg.225 fig 400667.4.peg.693	FIGfam110555
R12	n/a	ISPsy4, transposase
R13	n/a	Plasmid replication protein RepA
R14	n/a	Integrase/recombinase clustered with segregation and condensation protein B
R15	n/a	protein of unknown function DUF1612
R16	n/a	Predicted nucleotidyltransferases
R17	fig 400667.4.peg.837	Segregation and condensation protein B
R18	n/a	protein of unknown function DUF1403

The List of Functional Roles is According to the *A. baumannii* ATCC 17978 [B] (Genome ID 400667.4, Variant Code 1)

From the CBSS-203122.12.peg.188 subsystem information, the 11 features listed in the “Transposable elements” Subcategory includes TniB NYP-binding protein (R1), TniA putative transposase (R2), MII9366 protein (R6), ComM-related protein (R8), MG(2+) CHELATASE FAMILY PROTEIN (R9), Transposase OrfAB, subunit B (R10), FIGfam110555 (R11), and Segregation and condensation protein B (R17). At this stage, it is difficult to assume the relevance of these determinants in the virulence and/or

pathogenicity of Ab00. Further inspection of the location of these transposable elements in the Ab00 genome may reveal their importance in procuring higher level of survivability in the clinical setting.

In addition to the RAST annotation report, the BASys report was also analyzed. Unlike RAST, BASys lacks the ability to group the identified determinants into categories and functions. However, it emphasizes on individual gene reporting which is sorted based on their order on the genome, making it easier to screen through the genetic determinants. BASys also produces simple overview reports highlighting the amino acid compositions, protein functions, locations, and length distribution, as well as nucleotide composition.

Figure 4.8: Amino Acid Composition Generated by BASys

Based on the amino acid composition report, the Ab00 genome is concentrated with Leucine and Alanine. On the other hand, cysteine and tryptophan is of lower abundance (**Figure 4.8**). Cysteine, a relatively small amino acid, functions to stabilize protein structures by forming a covalent bond. Its role is however dependant on the protein localization. It is theorized that the abundance of cysteine is correlated with organism complexity, where less complex life forms harbor a lower amount of the amino acid in its genome. It stands to reason that the genome of *A. baumannii*, a single-celled organism would contain only a small fraction of it (Miseta & Csutora, 2000).

The low abundance of tryptophan in the Ab00 genome is unclear. It is possible that due to its nature as an aromatic residue, it is replaceable by other aromatic amino

acids such as phenylalanine and tyrosine. However, due to its inherently large structure, its interchangeability with other amino acids is questionable. Moreover, its reactivity varies slightly between the two other amino acids due to the presence of a nitrogen atom in its ring system (Betts & Russel, 2003). In addition, the abundance of phenylalanine and tyrosine are moderate, suggesting that their roles are of near equivalent significance. It is also possible that the production of tryptophan is heavily controlled by expression, lowering the intrinsic abundance and reducing unnecessary interactions (Yanofsky, 2007).

Figure 4.9: Ab00 Protein Function Distribution Generated by BASys

BASys also provided the “protein function distribution” as shown in **Figure 4.9**. From the chart, a large fraction of the annotated protein functions is unknown. The BASys annotation table for Ab00 lists 1203 hypothetical genes, 82 of which are annotated as “Hypothetical”, 493 “Conserved Hypothetical Proteins”, and 532 “Hypothetical Protein BASYS[X]”, where [X] is the designated BASys ID. There doesn’t seem to be a particular bias in the naming of the CDS. A brief comparative screening of the BASys and RAST annotation shows that both annotation systems produced “hypothetical” genes for the unknown determinants. Additionally, 4.8% of the annotations also consist of “COG of unknown function”, however this is a failure to assign annotated genes to a specific cluster. The source file for the protein function annotation also seems to be missing COG categories for RNA processing and modification (A), chromatin structure and dynamics (B), energy production and conversion (C), nuclear structure (Y) and cytoskeleton (Z). It is likely that these missing COGs might have been grouped under the unknown (U) category, which would explain its high percentage (34.2%).

Excluding the proteins of unknown function, the majority of the proteins (7.0%) were annotated under “general function prediction (R)”. BASys however does not provide the specifics of these “general functions”, making it difficult to further clarify the annotations. Transcription (K), and amino acid transport and metabolism (E) follows at 6.0% and 5.8% respectively, signifying emphasis on gene regulation in the Ab00 genome.

Alternatively, the least abundant protein functions are noted to be under cell division and chromosome partitioning (D); 0.7%, and cell motility (N); 1.1%. Interestingly, the BASys annotation reports the presence of “cell motility” genes, which is in contrast with the RAST annotation mentioned earlier. Theoretically, genes that confer twitching motility and certain pili-related determinants might have been grouped under this category. Again, due to the lack of detailed information in the protein function assignments selected by BASys, it is difficult to determine the exact genes that were categorized under this COG.

4.3.7 Potential Virulence Determinants

Once the genome annotation overview was analyzed, the reports from both BASys and RAST were screened for potential virulence determinants. The RAST subsystems annotation was used to narrow down the list of genes. By selecting the “Virulence, disease and defense” category in the RAST Subsystem Information, a total of 58 features were identified. From there, subsystems that are not of interest, such as copper homeostasis, cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance, arsenic resistance were removed. Antibiotic resistance-related determinants were also removed in this screening and were instead used in the antibiotic resistance analysis. The final list of virulence determinants is as shown in **Table 4.7**.

The list includes four subsystems pertaining to *Mycobacterium* virulence elements and one *Listeria*-related element. The latter however, is putative. A pairwise alignment using MAUVE revealed that the same sequence is reported by BASys to be a “hypothetical protein ABSDF” (BASYS01790). To confirm this, a blastx search was performed on the BASYS01790 nucleotide sequence. Among the hits included an *A. baumannii* internalin at 96% identity. The surface protein internalin is involved in the invasion of mammalian cell. This forms a consensus with the annotation reported by RAST.

The aforementioned four subsystems in relevance to *Mycobacterium* virulence elements are composed of “virulence operons”. Despite the nomenclature, a BLAST search using the nucleotide sequences of these features revealed hits to *A. baumannii* sequences with identity above 95%. From the nine operons, four of which encode ribosomal proteins; 2 small subunits (SSU) and 2 large subunits (LSU). The s7p functions as the primary rRNA binding protein and is responsible for the assembly of the 30S subunit head domain, while the s12p stabilizes the rRNA selection between the A site and mRNA backbone. The large ribosomal subunits L35p and L20p on the other hand are responsible for S50 ribosomal subunit assembly.

Mutations in S12 have been reported to confer streptomycin resistance at the expense of decreased translation rate (Stelzl et al., 2001; Wilcox et al., 2001). Mutations on the S7 on the other hand have been indicated to reduce susceptibility towards tetracycline (Ross et al., 1998). The large subunits L25 and L30 have a role in the

regulation of protease production as well as the production of the antibiotic syringomycin in *Pseudomonas syringae* (Kitten & Willis, 1996). It is possible that the categorization of these elements under the virulence determinants by RAST is due to these potential antibiotic resistance activities. The same can be said for the inclusion of the DNA maintenance genes *gyrA*, *gyrB*, *parE* and *parC* under the fluoroquinolone resistance category (**Table 4.9**), regardless of the sample's susceptible nature towards ciprofloxacin. This denotes a probable flaw in the RAST subsystems. However, its detailed cataloging of “potential” virulence elements is still useful, as it provides a list of elements that may result in an acquisition of resistance should the necessary selective pressures be exerted on the pathogen.

Apart from the above determinants, the presence of bacteriocin-producing elements was also detected in the Ab00 genome (**Table 4.8**). These compounds function to antagonize the growth of competing organism, which in theory effectively improves the survivability and growth of the *A. baumannii* (Ehler et al., 2012). In the context of a human host environment, the secretion of these antagonizing molecules would be beneficial when competing for nutrients in a host gut or any other sites thriving with normal flora.

Table 4.7

Ab00 Virulence Determinants Detected in RAST Subsystems

Subsystem	Role	Features
Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	SSU ribosomal protein S7p (S5e)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.539
	Translation elongation factor G	fig 6666666.98826.peg.538
	Translation elongation factor Tu	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1045
	SSU ribosomal protein S12p (S23e)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.540
Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	DNA-directed RNA polymerase beta' subunit (EC 2.7.7.6)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1037
	DNA-directed RNA polymerase beta subunit (EC 2.7.7.6)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1038
Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	Quinolinate synthetase (EC 2.5.1.72)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.686
	Quinolinate phosphoribosyltransferase [decarboxylating] (EC 2.4.2.19)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.171
	L-aspartate oxidase (EC 1.4.3.16)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.2162
Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	internalin, putative	fig 6666666.98826.peg.2754
Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	LSU ribosomal protein L35p	fig 6666666.98826.peg.740
	Translation initiation factor 3	fig 6666666.98826.peg.744
	LSU ribosomal protein L20p	fig 6666666.98826.peg.7

The virulence determinants were selected based on the “Virulence, Disease and Defense” category, and the “Invasion and intracellular resistance” subcategory.

Table 4.8

Ab00 Bacteriocin-Producing Genes Under the “Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster “ Subsystem Detected in RAST Subsystems

Role	Features	Gene	Protein Function
Dihydrofolate synthase (EC 6.3.2.12)	peg.1775	<i>folC</i> [H]	Bifunctional protein folC [H]
Folypolyglutamate synthase (EC 6.3.2.17)	peg.1775		
Amidophosphoribosyltransferase (EC 2.4.2.14)	peg.2408	<i>purF</i> [H]	Amidophosphoribosyltransferase [H]
Acetyl-coenzyme A carboxyl transferase beta chain (EC 6.4.1.2)	peg.1774	<i>accD</i> [H]	Acetyl-coenzyme A carboxylase carboxyl transferase subunit beta [H]
DedA protein	peg.1084, peg.1558	<i>dedA</i> [H] <i>dedA</i> [H]	Protein dedA [H] Protein dedA [H]
Colicin V production protein	peg.2407	<i>cvpA</i> [C]	Colicin V Production Protein
tRNA pseudouridine synthase A (EC 4.2.1.70)	peg.913, peg.2208	<i>truA</i> [H] <i>rluE</i> [H]	tRNA pseudouridine synthase A [H] Ribosomal large subunit pseudouridine synthase E [H]

The genes were selected based on the “Virulence, Disease and Defense” category, and the “Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides” subcategory.

4.3.8 Potential Resistance Determinants

As mentioned previously, under the “virulence, disease and defense” is also the list of elements that confer “Resistance to antibiotic and toxic compounds”. Out of the 62 determinants listed by RAST, 12 are responsible for copper homeostasis, two for copper tolerance, 13 for cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance, and three for chromium resistance. Since these compounds do not fall under the “antibiotics” definition, they have been removed from the final list, as shown in **Table 4.9**. From the table, it is predicted that Ab00 has the potential for resisting aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones, and beta-lactamases. The feature “fig|6666666.98826.peg.1554” categorized under the aminoglycosides resistance plays a role in the production of streptomycin 3"-O-adenylyltransferase, and coincides with the BASys annotation. This, coupled with the above virulence operon S12 SSU ribosomal protein explains the phenotypic resistance towards streptomycin as shown in **Table 4.1**.

The list of genes conferring resistance to fluoroquinolones however is questionable. The four determinants listed are generally present in prokaryotes and function as housekeeping genes responsible for DNA maintenance. Although several reports have stated that mutations in varying regions within these elements may confer resistance, these mutations only need to occur in one out of four determinants to do so (Jaktaji & Mohiti, 2010; Vila et al., 1995). Moreover, the ciprofloxacin microdilution assay performed on Ab00 has shown susceptibility towards the antibiotic. This suggests that the four elements listed by RAST are “potential” resistance determinants, as in the previously discussed virulence determinants.

The list also includes two genes conferring beta-lactam resistance; Beta-lactamase class C and Beta-lactamase (EC 3.5.2.6). But despite this, Ab00 shows susceptibility towards both imipenem and meropenem in the antibiogram results. In theory, this could be due to an under-expression of the aforementioned genes (Evans et al., 2013). A prolonged and sub-lethal exposure towards these antibiotics may be able to improve the beta-lactamase production, and result in resistance towards the listed carbapenems (Ehler et al., 2012; Liao et al., 2014; Tiwari & Tiwari, 2014).

Table 4.9
Virulence Determinants Detected in Ab00 Genome as Presented by RAST

Subsystem	Role	Features
Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	Streptomycin 3'-O-adenylyltransferase (EC 2.7.7.47)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1554
	Spectinomycin 9-O-adenylyltransferase	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1554
Resistance to fluoroquinolones	DNA gyrase subunit B (EC 5.99.1.3)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1082
	DNA gyrase subunit A (EC 5.99.1.3)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.2094
	Topoisomerase IV subunit B (EC 5.99.1.-)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1281
	Topoisomerase IV subunit A (EC 5.99.1.-)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.14
Beta-lactamase	Beta-lactamase class C and other penicillin binding proteins	fig 6666666.98826.peg.975
	Beta-lactamase (EC 3.5.2.6)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.101, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2297, fig 6666666.98826.peg.3186
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	RND efflux system, membrane fusion protein CmeA	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1972, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2354, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2901
	RND efflux system, outer membrane lipoprotein CmeC	fig 6666666.98826.peg.821, fig 6666666.98826.peg.1970, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2352
	Multidrug and toxin extrusion (MATE) family efflux pump YdhE/NorM	fig 6666666.98826.peg.941
	Multi antimicrobial extrusion protein (Na ⁺)/drug antiporter, MATE family of MDR efflux pumps	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1272
	RND efflux system, inner membrane transporter CmeB	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1971, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2045, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2353
	Probable transcription regulator protein of MDR efflux pump cluster	fig 6666666.98826.peg.2355
	Macrolide export ATP-binding/permease protein MacB (EC 3.6.3.-)	fig 6666666.98826.peg.820
	Acriflavin resistance protein	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1857, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2902
	Macrolide-specific efflux protein MacA	fig 6666666.98826.peg.819
	Type I secretion outer membrane protein, TolC precursor	fig 6666666.98826.peg.1104, fig 6666666.98826.peg.2880

Eighteen multidrug efflux pump components were listed among the resistance determinants detected by RAS, which are grouped into 10 different roles. Of the 10, three are RND efflux systems functioning as RND efflux systems; CmeA, CmeB and CmeC. To identify the genes in each membrane fusion set, both the RAST and BASys genbank annotations were aligned and compared, as shown in **Table 4.10**. Under CmeA, BASys annotated genes encoding acriflavine resistance protein *acrA*, multidrug resistance protein *mdtA* and membrane fusion protein *mtrC* were identified to align with RAST annotated features 1972, 2354 and 2901 respectively. The CmeB set revealed matches between two non-identical copies of genes encoding multidrug resistance protein *mexB* and one encoding an efflux membrane transporter *bepE* with RAST features 1971, 2045 and 2353. The third set, CmeC is an outer membrane lipoprotein component consisting of genes encoding an uncharacterized protein HI-1462 *cusC*, an outer membrane protein *oprM* and an antibiotic efflux outer membrane protein *arpC* matching to features 821, 1970 and 2352.

By viewing the position of the listed genes using the BASys CGView map, their grouping into functional sets can be hypothesized (**Figure 4.10**). On the negative strand, between positions 998125 bp and 994939 bp, genes *acrA*, *mexB* and *oprM* is observed to be clustered together in that order. The *mexB* gene encodes the multidrug efflux protein situated on the inner membrane, form a gate on the internal side of the bilipid layer. On the other hand, OprM, an antibiotic/solvent efflux protein is located on the outer membrane, forming a gate facing the external side of the lipid bilayer. The AcrA, a broad-spectrum drug efflux protein is anchored to the inner membrane, but the majority of its structure is situated within the periplasm. It connects and stabilizes both OprM and MexB (Yoneyama et al., 2000; Husain et al., 2004).

The second cluster is also located on the negative strand, between the 1443151 bp and 1439955 bp. In this region, the *mdtA*, *bepE* and *arpC* genes can be observed. Similarly with the previous cluster, this group of genes also includes three genes necessary for the construction of a working tripartite efflux pump. The *bepE* gene is responsible for encoding the efflux pump membrane transporter BepE, which is positioned in the inner membrane of the lipid bilayer. Immediately downstream is the *arpC* element, encoding the antibiotic efflux pump outer membrane protein ArpC

positioned on the outer membrane. The third gene, the *mdtA* gene located immediately upstream of the *bepE* gene and encodes the MdtA multidrug resistance protein *mdtA* positioned in the inner membrane. Literature describes this gene as a part of the MdtABC tripartite complex. However, the genes encoding the remaining components of the complex, *mdtB* and *mdtC* could not be identified in the annotated Ab00 genome. Based on the BASys annotation gene card, this structure may confer resistance to a broad spectrum of antibiotics, regardless of structure, e.g. carbenicillin, erythromycin, streptomycin, chloramphenicol, novobiocin and tetracycline. Furthermore, this component is not involved in organic solvent efflux, suggesting a function specifically tied to drug efflux.

The third cluster is located on the positive strand between positions 3411722 bp and 3409798 bp. The genes *cusC*, *macB* and *macA* is observed within this region, in this respective order. The *cusC* gene encodes an uncharacterized protein HI_1462, which BASys reports to function as an invasion mechanism akin to *Haemophilus influenzae*. However, a quick BLAST search reveals several bacterial homologues which mostly functions as either a cation, antibiotic or macrolide efflux protein. The latter of which is the sole hit to a *Acinetobacter sp.* ADP1. Although its designation as invasion protein is unlikely, its annotated position on the outer membrane tallies with the remaining genes in the cluster, *macA* and *macB*. According to the NCBI BLAST results, the *cusC* homologue forms a tripartite system with proteins MacA and MacB. The NCBI BLAST results also states that the *cusC* protein functions as an outer membrane efflux protein locked in place by a lipid anchor. This coincides with the MacA and MacB functions to form a complete tripartite efflux structure. Moreover, according to the information retrieved from the KEGG website, the CusC protein also plays a role in copper/silver efflux (http://www.genome.jp/kegg-bin/show_pathway?ko02020). Its replacement to the typically employed TolC protein as the outer membrane structure may be attributed to the chimeric properties of Gram negative efflux systems (Yoneyama et al., 2000; Husain et al., 2004).

It was noted that the genes within all three clusters are positioned in such a way that the periplasmic component is read first, followed by the inner component, lastly the outer membrane protein. This arrangement of genes based on function has been reported

in several studies, suggesting that it is either the most optimal or stable order (Marchand et al., 2004; Coyne et al., 2010; Coyne et al., 2011).

Although there appears to be several other genes encoding efflux components present within the annotated Ab00 genome, they were not included by RAST as potential virulence determinants. As such, these remaining elements were not incorporated in the analysis. It is considered that the discounting of these elements may be due to the limitations of the RAST subsystem. But at the time of the analysis, there was no method to verify this.

Figure 4.10: Efflux Gene Clusters Categorized Under the “Resistance Determinants” Identified by RAST and Visualized Using the CGView Map by BASys

Table 4.10
Comparison of Virulence Determinants as Annotated by RAST and BASys

Subsystem	RAST		BASys	
	Role	gene	product	
Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	Streptomycin 3"-O-adenylyltransferase (EC 2.7.7.47)	<i>(antI</i>	Streptomycin 3"-adenylyltransferase [H]	
Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	Spectinomycin 9-O-adenylyltransferase			
Resistance to fluoroquinolones	DNA gyrase subunit B (EC 5.99.1.3)	<i>gyrB</i> [H]	DNA gyrase subunit B [H]	
Resistance to fluoroquinolones	DNA gyrase subunit A (EC 5.99.1.3)	<i>gyrA</i> [H]	DNA gyrase subunit A [H]	
Resistance to fluoroquinolones	Topoisomerase IV subunit B (EC 5.99.1.-)	<i>parE</i> [H]	DNA topoisomerase 4 subunit B [H]	
Resistance to fluoroquinolones	Topoisomerase IV subunit A (EC 5.99.1.-)	<i>parC</i> [H]	DNA topoisomerase 4 subunit A [H]	
Beta-lactamase	Beta-lactamase class C and other penicillin binding proteins	<i>yfeW</i>	UPFO214 protein yfeW	
Beta-lactamase	Beta-lactamase (EC 3.5.2.6)	-	Beta-Lactamase	
		<i>ampC</i> [H]	Beta-lactamase [H]	
		<i>bla</i> [H]	Beta-lactamase OXA-10 [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	RND efflux system, membrane fusion protein CmeA	<i>acrA</i> [H]	Acriflavine resistance protein A [H]	
		<i>mdtA</i> [H]	Multidrug resistance protein mdtA [H]	
		<i>mtrC</i> [H]	Membrane fusion protein mtrC [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	RND efflux system, outer membrane lipoprotein CmeC	<i>cusC</i> [C]	Uncharacterized protein HI_1462 [H]	
		<i>oprM</i> [H]	Outer membrane protein oprM [H]	
		<i>arpC</i> [H]	Antibiotic efflux pump outer membrane protein ArpC [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	Multidrug and toxin extrusion (MATE) family efflux pump YdhE/NorM	<i>norM</i> [H]	Probable multidrug resistance protein norM [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	Multi antimicrobial extrusion protein (Na ⁺)/drug antiporter), MATE family of MDR efflux pumps	<i>yoeA</i> [H]	Probable multidrug resistance protein yoeA [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	RND efflux system, inner membrane transporter CmeB	<i>mexB</i> [H]	Multidrug resistance protein MexB [H]	
		<i>mexB</i> [H]	Multidrug resistance protein MexB [H]	
		<i>bepE</i> [H]	Efflux pump membrane transporter BepE [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	Probable transcription regulator protein of MDR efflux pump cluster	<i>yhjC</i> [H]	Uncharacterized HTH-type transcriptional regulator yhjC [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	Macrolide export ATP-binding/permease protein MacB (EC 3.6.3.-)	<i>macB</i> [H]	Macrolide export ATP-binding/permease protein MacB [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	Acriflavin resistance protein	<i>nolG</i> [H]	Nodulation protein nolG [H]	
		<i>acrB</i> [H]	Acriflavine resistance protein B [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	Macrolide-specific efflux protein MacA	<i>macA</i> [H]	Macrolide-specific efflux protein macA [H]	
Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	Type I secretion outer membrane protein, TolC precursor	<i>tolC</i> [H]	Outer membrane protein tolC [H]	
		<i>bepC</i> [H]	Outer membrane efflux protein BepC [H]	

Based on the sets of data analyzed thus far, it can be deduced that Ab00 possesses potential for antimicrobial resistance that is not currently portrayed by its phenotype. The presence of the beta-lactamase producing genes for instance is a clear indicator that there exists a latent ability for combating carbapenems within the Ab00 genome. It is possible that its current susceptibility towards both imipenem and meropenem may be an indication of an under expression of the relevant genes. It should be noted that apart from the expression of the beta-lactamase genes themselves, the upregulation of RND efflux pumps has also been reported to contribute to an increased beta-lactam resistance (Tiwari & Tiwari, 2014).

The presence of several efflux pump components within the genome also indicates the potential for resistance acquisition to antibiotics other than beta-lactam. This is true for both the antibiotic-specific pumps, e.g. macrolide-specific and acriflavine-specific components, as well as the broad-spectrum systems. However, whether or not these components are capable of modifying the phenotypic characteristics of the antimicrobial susceptibility can only be determined through a series of resistance inductions.

4.4 CONCLUSION

The Ab00 strain was confirmed via phenotypic and genomic methods to be a viable susceptible parent strain for the resistance induction process. The genomic analysis however revealed that despite the observed susceptibility, the parent strain still possesses several innate resistance determinants. It is likely that these elements are either currently inactive or under expressed, and can be triggered through exposure to specific stimuli.

CHAPTER FIVE
IN VITRO RESISTANCE INDUCTION OF A SUSCEPTIBLE
***Acinetobacter baumannii* ISOLATE**

5.1 INTRODUCTION

A. baumannii has been well documented as a clinical pathogen capable of acquiring resistance at an alarming rate (Peleg et al., 2008). Several mitigating and exacerbating factors have been hypothesized to cause this. The combination of inadvertent transmission to and from patients, especially in ICUs has exacerbated the prevalence of this pathogen in the hospital setting. The adaptive mechanism in these Gram negative nosocomial agents vary, and although studies have well documented the various adaptations towards specific drugs, the full spectrum of the pathogen's adaptation potential is yet to be clarified.

Studies have reported that a fluoroquinolone resistance in *A. baumannii* was attributed to high *adeB* expression as well as several point mutations in housekeeping genes *gyrA* and *parC* (Chiu et al., 2010). However, it was also stated that isolates with intermediately-resistant strains lack the point mutations and only exhibit high *adeABC* efflux expression alone (Ardebili et al., 2013). Mutations in *topoisomerase IV* genes have also been reported to enable high-level resistance against the drug, indicating multiple resistance mechanisms to the same drug (Hamouda & Amyes, 2005).

Unlike the mechanisms leading to fluoroquinolone-resistance, *A. baumannii* has been reported to exhibit several macrolide-specific resistance genes. The intrinsic nature of this resistance is of course not the sole mechanism identified. The presence of plasmid-borne macrolide tolerance has also been reported. Though the most common method for macrolide resistance is by removal via macrolide-specific efflux pumps, the presence of macrolide-altering enzyme is also possible. This adds an extra level of depth to macrolide resistance in *A. baumannii* (Poirel et al., 2011).

Resistance against carbapenems on the other hand has long been attributed to the production of beta-lactamase. Hence, this trait is typically intrinsic or acquired via

horizontal gene transfer. However, pathogens that lack the genes necessary for beta-lactamase production have also developed different methods employing biofilm-producing genes in order to compensate (Prashanth et al., 2012). In addition, when pressured, the pathogen may also revert to a non-active state in order to prevent the drug activity from taking place (Corona & Martinez, 2013).

Although the genetic and molecular bases of these mechanisms have been well recorded, several questions still remain unanswered. The conflicting reports stating several resistance profiles which contribute to a single fluoroquinolone resistance for instance suggests a more complex mechanism at play. This is also true for the strains exhibiting macrolide and carbapenem resistance. In addition, these profiles were generated using different strains under different selective pressures. Detailed information on the mechanisms of a single strain against a different set of selective pressures has therefore yet to be thoroughly scrutinized.

When subjected to selective pressure, bacteria typically become susceptible to mutations, whereby its genome sequence is permanently altered. Beneficial variations are passed down to their daughter cells upon replication, and subsequently result in a new mutant population (Foster, 1993). The various types of mutations such as point mutations or single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP), inversions, translocations and duplications can be very effective in conferring antimicrobial resistance, if successful (Madigan & Martinko, 2006). These mutations are capable of modifying the proteins which the nucleotides are translated into. The altered protein sequence or structure may cause a change in its function as well. A correct modification for example, may disable a drug from binding to its intended target, effectively conferring resistance. SNPs are, in effect the simplest type of mutation, as it only requires a single nucleotide change (as the name suggests) in order to produce an alternate phenotype. In theory, this would be the most favored mode of mutation, as it simply requires a "misreading" of a single nucleotide, rather than the use of supplementary molecules (Chopra & Galande, 2011).

The aims here were; to generate four *A. baumannii* isogenic variants that are singularly resistant to ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem, respectively; to sequence the genome of the resistant mutants and identify the variants present; and to validate the variants detected in the isogenic mutants.

5.2 METHODS

Figure 5.1: Overview of Methodology

5.2.1 Preparation of Culture

Acinetobacter baumannii strain Ab00 was used in this study. The isolate was cultured overnight in MHB, as mentioned in chapter 3.4.

5.2.2 Selection of Susceptible Parent Strain

The selection of suitable parent strain is as mentioned in chapter 4.2.3.

5.2.3 Preparation of Antibiotic Stock Solution

Antimicrobial powders (imipenem, meropenem (tienem) and erythromycin lactobionate) were dissolved in 1 ml sterile MHB in sterile microcentrifuge tubes. The MHB was first heated to 37°C in order to facilitate the dissolution of the drugs. The tubes were vigorously shaken until the powder has completely dissolved. The solutions were then diluted to 80 µg/ml in 10 ml sterile MHB. The same was done for a ciprofloxacin solution (2 mg/ml). It was determined that 1.4882 grams of erythromycin lactobionate is equivalent to one gram of erythromycin (Sweetman, 2009). As such, the calculated final volume was adjusted accordingly; the final volume of the diluted erythromycin lactobionate was multiplied by 1.4882 to achieve the equivalent concentration of “erythromycin” as shown in the formula below;

$$M_1V_1 = M_2V_2 \times 1.4882$$

- M_1 = Dissolved erythromycin lactobionate concentration
- V_1 = Amount of erythromycin lactobionate to be diluted (Volume)
- M_2 = Desired concentration of the erythromycin lactobionate
- V_2 = Final volume of the erythromycin lactobionate

The dissolved and diluted antimicrobials were stored at 4°C for a maximum of three days, after which new antimicrobial solutions were prepared. The solutions were sealed with parafilm and were kept on ice throughout use.

5.2.4 MIC Screening via Broth Microdilution

In order to determine the sub-lethal concentration needed for the resistance induction, the MIC of the susceptible parent strain was determined via broth microdilution. The selected antimicrobial solutions were diluted to 8 µg/ml in 1 ml of freshly prepared 2-hour cultures (OD₆₀₀ was comparable to 0.5 McFarland standard) in

1.5 ml sterile microcentrifuge tubes, as described in chapter 3.5.2. A two-fold dilution was then performed in microcentrifuge tubes (containing the same 2 hour cultures) to achieve final concentrations of 8, 4, 2, 1, and 0.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. A total of 200 μl of the solutions were then transferred to a 96-well plate. Replicates were prepared for each concentration. The antimicrobial solutions (8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) diluted in sterile MHB was used as the negative control. The 2 hour culture was used as the positive control. The plate was incubated at 37°C, shaking over 24 hours.

The results of the MIC were observed at 18 and 24 hours of incubation. The OD_{600} was measured using the POLARstar Omega spectrophotometer (BMG Labtech, Offenburg, Germany).

5.2.5 *In vitro* Antimicrobial Resistance Induction

A batch of antimicrobial working stocks (with a concentration that is 2-fold higher than their respective MIC) was prepared and diluted in MHB accordingly. A total of 50 μl of overnight *A. baumannii* culture was transferred into each broth, and incubated at 37°C, shaking for a minimum of 18 hours. The OD_{600} of the cultures were measured via biophotometer (Eppendorf AG, Hamburg, Germany). Upon confirmation of growth (OD_{600} of at least 0.3), the cultures were passaged into a fresh broth containing the antimicrobial of the same concentration, and another with an antimicrobial concentration that is 2-fold higher. A 1 ml aliquot of each culture was centrifuged and the supernatant was separated from the pellet. Both were then stored at -80°C. Replicates were prepared and stored for future genomics analysis. This process was iterated until growth beyond the resistance threshold has been achieved (EUCAST, 2014). Upon acquisition of resistance, the sample was passaged daily in MHB containing the antimicrobial that is 2-fold higher than the resistance threshold. The resistance induction was continued for all drugs until a relatively high resistance was acquired in addition to the threshold resistant samples.

The development of each resistant variant was monitored via daily OD_{600} measurement. The samples were first shaken to ensure an even distribution of the culture. Cultures that produced thick biofilm/slime were first mechanically sheared by gentle pumping using the one milliliter pipette. Once an even dispersal has been achieved, 200 μl of each sample was measured. The OD was taken between 18-24 hours of cultivation.

After the OD has been measured and a new inoculate has started incubating, the previous culture was stored for a minimum of 1 day as a backup. Under circumstances where growth was not observed, the stored culture was adjusted to 37°C and used in starting a new inoculate to continue the induction. At the same time, the stunted culture was cultured for another 24 hours to rule out the possibility of an extended acclimatization period. A culture is considered “stable” once stunted growth no longer occurs in at least three days.

5.2.6 Validation of Acquired Resistance

Once a strain has achieved growth in at least two-fold of a resistance threshold (with the exception of imipenem); ciprofloxacin, 2 µg/ml; erythromycin, 8 µg/ml; meropenem, 16 µg/ml; and imipenem, 8 µg/ml, disc diffusion was performed, using the susceptible strain as the control. The imipenem-resistant variant was acclimatized only to 8 µg/ml (EUCAST resistance threshold) as there was an increasing difficulty to generate a turbid enough culture at 16 µg/ml. Gram staining was performed on all the resistant variants as well as the susceptible control to rule out contaminations.

5.2.7 Generation and Comparison of Growth Curves

Fresh 24-hour cultures of susceptible and resistant variants were prepared in MHB. The samples were grown in 50 ml conical flasks. A growth curve of the cultures was generated by measuring the OD₆₀₀ per hour for a total of 37 hours. The measurement was halted once the plateau stage was confirmed.

5.2.8 Genome Sequencing of Resistant Variants

The genomic DNA (gDNA) of each of the isogenic resistant *A. baumannii* variants was extracted from overnight cultures grown in Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB). The sample preparation was as described in chapter 3.4.

5.2.9 Genome Analysis of Resistant Variants

The quality of the sequencing output was analyzed using the FastQC and SolexaQA software (Cox et al, 2010; Andrews, 2012). Once the quality was confirmed, trimming of low quality reads was performed using DynamicTrim. The trimmed reads

were then used as the input for the variant calling using CLCbio under default parameters.

5.2.10 Primer design for validation of variants

All primers were designed using the PerlPrimer software (Marshall, 2004). The design parameters used were standardized in all primers. The primer melting temperature (T_m) was set to 58-60°C, with a maximum difference in T_m allowed between primers was set to 2°C. The primer length parameter was set to 18-25 bases. The “amplified range” was set so that the mutation target site was at 50 bp downstream of the forward primer and 50 bp upstream of the reverse primer. The “external dimer dG” and “Full dimer dG” was selected to be as close to zero as possible. The maximum allowed range is between “-3” and “3” kcal/mol. The GC content of both forward and reverse primers was not allowed to exceed 50%.

Due to a lack in quality of the *ahpF* gene(s) detected in the AbRM isogenic mutant genome whereby the assembled reads failed to form a complete gene sequence, the primers AbY32a and AbY32b pairs were designed using the *ahpF* gene from an *A. baumannii* strain AYE reference sequence. The gene sequence was downloaded from the BioCyc database collection (<http://www.biocyc.org/ABAU509173/sequence?type=GENE&object=GJXF-2472>). The primers were designed to target; i) the entirety of the *ahpF* gene, ii) the first half of the gene, and iii) the second half of the gene. The primer combinations used to achieve these three targets are as listed in **Figure 5.2**.

Figure 5.2: Primer Combinations for The Three Target Regions in the *ahpF* Gene

Once the primers have been designed, adhering to the above parameters, the potential for dimerization was confirmed first via the PerlPrimer dimer prediction section. The same parameters were used, where the dG between dimers was not allowed to exceed the range between “-3” and “3” kcal/mol. The dimerization potential was then validated using the Oligo Analyzer software using the same parameters CITATION. Once the validation is completed, the primers were purchased accordingly. The list of primers is as shown in **Table 5.1**.

Table 5.1
List of Primers Used in the Validation of the Variants

Variant	Target Gene	Gene Name	Primer	Sequence (5'-3')	Primer Length (bp)	Annealing Temp. °C (Perlprimer)	GC Content (%)	Amplicon size (bp)	Primers used for sequencing
AbRC	BASYS01425	<i>gyrA</i>	AbY20_F	AAATCCGACCGATTGCCA	18	59.78	50	667	F
			AbUG_R	TTACCGTAAATAATACCGCCTG	22	58.5	40		
	BASYS03415	<i>recB</i>	AbY27_F	AAACCAGCCTAATCCGCA	18	59.37	50	313	F
			AbY27_R	GAAGAATCGCAGTGAGTAAGG	21	58.93	47		
	BASYS03416	<i>recC</i>	AbY28_F	ACTTTACTGGATTTACCACCCA	22	59.53	40	330	F
			AbY28_R	CTTCACCTGTAGATAAGTTTGAGAG	25	59.15	40		
	BASYS01118	Group A Colicins Tolerance Protein	AbY29_F	TAGAGGAAGCACAGAAGCA	19	58.4	47	944	F+R
			AbY29_R	CAGACAGGGTAAATCTAACGC	21	58.93	47		
	BASYS00190	<i>mtnN</i> [H]	AbY38_F	TATGGACGTTTCACCTTTAGGA	22	59.33	40	165	F
			AbY38_R	GACTACATCACAAGCGACCT	20	59.94	50		
BASYS01104	<i>purM</i> [H]	AbY39_F	GACGGTGTAGGTACTAAATTACG	23	58.9	43	184	F/R	
		AbY39_R	ATACCAGTAACTACGTTTGCAG	22	58.64	40			
BASYS02180	<i>xcpX</i> [X]	AbY40_F	ATACTGCTTCGCCATTGGT	19	59.86	47	258	R	
		AbY40_R	AAAGCACTAGTAAACTGTTCGC	21	59.07	42			
BASYS02940	<i>yihG</i> [H]	AbY41_F	ATTAACCCGTATGCCGCT	18	59.22	50	399	F	
		AbY41_R	CCAGAAATCGCCATAACCTG	20	59.16	50			
AbRE	BASYS00519	<i>ftsI</i> [H]	AbY1_F	GGCTTAAATGCGACAATCCT	20	59.08	45	342	F
			AbY1_R	CCACTACAATAACGGCTAAACG	22	59.88	45		
	BASYS00705	Ribonuclease I	AbY2_F	GATCATCTGTGCAAGCGT	20	58.23	50	271	F
			AbY2_R	CATTATTGTCGGGCATCACC	20	59.52	50		
	BASYS00775	<i>bvgS</i> [H]	AbY3_F	GGTTTGAGCTTATGTAAGCGT	21	59.13	42	124	F
			AbY3_R	TGATGTTTCAGGAACCTTCTTGAG	22	58.49	40		
BASYS03268	<i>rlmN</i>	AbY4_F	TGTATTCTTTCACAAGTGGGC	21	58.98	42	181	F	
		AbY4_R	ATCATCACGACATTGGTTACTG	22	58.96	40			
BASYS01945	<i>srrA</i> [H]	AbY5_F	CATGAATGGAAAGCAAGCGA	20	59.66	45	387	F	
		AbY5_R	AGTCAGCGTCAGATTAAGCA	20	59.58	45			
AbRM	BASYS00954	<i>mexB</i>	AbY22_F	CAAATGAATGGTCTTGATGGC	21	58.31	42	799	F
			AbY22_R	CGGATAAATGGAGTCGTGTC	20	58.61	50		
	BASYS01459	-	AbY23_F	ATTTACCAATGCTCAGACCG	20	58.43	45	741	F
			AbY23_R	CGTATCTTGATAAGTTCCCCG	21	59.07	47		
	BASYS00149	<i>epsL</i>	AbY24_F	CTTTAATAGCTCTAACCGTACTGTC	25	59.31	40	461	F
			AbY24_R	CAACCCAAACACTATGATTGTC	22	58.05	40		
	BASYS00049	<i>atpD</i>	AbY25_F	GAACAAGCAGTTCTACTGAC	21	59.41	47	344	F
			AbY25_R	ATCACGGAAGTATTCAGCCA	20	59.28	45		
BASYS03487	<i>tufI</i>	AbY26_F	TACTCACAAATCGACTCAGCA	21	59.6	42	296	F	
		AbY26_R	TTCTTCGTCATCAACAAGGTC	21	58.72	42			

	BASYS02818	<i>irlR</i> [H]	AbY30_F	TCTAAAGCAAGGTCTTTCTGAG	22	58.22	40	299	F
			AbY30_R	ATCATCAGCTCCTAGTTCCA	20	58	45		
	AbAYE_ahpF	<i>ahpF</i>	AbY32a_F	TGCTGCTTTAGATGAATCAGAC	22	58.96	40	1407	F+R
			AbY32a_R	TACAGTGGTACAGTCACCTG	20	58.85	50		
	AbAYE_ahpF	<i>ahpF</i>	AbY32b_F	GCACGTAAAGGCATTAACAC	20	58.2	45	788	F+R
			AbY32b_R	ACGATACCTGTGTTAATGCC	20	58.15	45	647	
	BASYS03639	-	AbY33_F	CCCTCATACTGATATTCAACTGTG	24	59.21	41	255	F
			AbY33_R	ATGACGTATTTCCGGCTGGA	19	59.26	47		
	BASYS03910	-	AbY34_F	ACTGGTTTAAAGTTTCTGGGTG	22	59.21	40	203	F
			AbY34_R	GTCAATCTGCTCATCTTGTGG	21	59.47	47		
AbRI	BASYS01149	<i>yceG</i> [C]	AbY35_F	CCTCGATAGCGAACTTACAC	20	58.34	40	208	F
			AbY35_R	TGTTACCCCTTATAGTTTGCACC	22	58.54	40		
	BASYS01947	<i>acrB</i> [H]	AbY36_F	CAATGAAAGAGATTACCAGCCC	22	59.55	45	221	F
			AbY36_R	CCTTCTTCTGATGATGCCCA	20	59.94	50		
	BASYS00519	<i>ftsI</i> [H] 1	AbY37_F	CTTGCATAAACTAGATCAGCCAC	23	59.94	43	362	F
		<i>ftsI</i> [H] 2	AbY37_R	AGCGGCACATTCATTAAGC	19	59.35	47		R

F = Forward primer

R = Reverse primer

5.2.11 Validation of Variants in Resistant Isogenic Mutants

Prior to the validation process, the primers were first reconstituted according to the manufacturer's instructions. The primers were then diluted into a working stock for continuous use. All primers were stored at -20°C when not in use, and kept on ice during use. The PCR conditions and primer concentration used are as detailed in chapter 3.13. DNA extracted from overnight cultures of the resistant isolates AbRC, AbRE, AbRM and AbRI were used in the variant validation.

5.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.3.1 MIC Screening via Broth Microdilution

The result of the antimicrobial MIC screening is as shown in **Table 5.2**. The MIC for CIP, ERY, MEM and IMI were determined to be 0.5 µg/ml, 2.0 µg/ml, 0.5 µg/ml and 0.5 µg/ml, respectively. These values were used as the starting concentrations for the following resistance induction process. As shown in the table, the threshold concentration for resistance was as determined by EUCAST standards. The “storage” column represents the variant that was selected for storage. The resistance limit indicates the highest concentration of antibiotics that the variants were exposed to.

Table 5.2
Results of the MIC Screening via Broth Microdilution

Variant label	Drug	Drug concentration (µg/ml)			
		MIC	Threshold	Storage	Resistance limit
AbRC	Ciprofloxacin	0.5	2.0	4.0	64.0
AbRE	Erythromycin	2.0	4.0	8.0	1024.0
AbRM	Meropenem	0.5	8.0	16.0	32.0
AbRI	Imipenem	0.5	8.0	8.0	n/a

- MIC - Minimum inhibitory concentration observed in Ab00
 Threshold - The minimum concentration of antimicrobial with observable bacterial growth that is deemed to be resistant by EUCAST standards.
 AbRC - Ciprofloxacin-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant
 AbRE - Erythromycin-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant
 AbRM - Meropenem-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant
 AbRI - Imipenem-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant

5.3.2 Resistance Induction

The results (OD) of the 73-day antibiotic exposure were recorded on a daily basis.

Table 5.3

The Amount of Time of Exposure (Day) for Each Variant in Each Drug Concentration, as Well as the Cumulative Number of Days of Drug Exposure

Isogenic Variant	Antimicrobial	Antimicrobial Concentration (µg/ml)	Amount of time exposed (day)	Cumulative number of days exposed
AbRC	ciprofloxacin	0.5	1	1
		1.0	3	4
		2.0	1	5
		4.0	1	6
		8.0	1	7
		16.0	3	10
		32.0	6	16
		64.0	37	53
		128.0	no further increment	73
AbRE	erythromycin	2.0	1	1
		4.0	1	2
		8.0	1	3
		16.0	1	4
		32.0	1	5
		64.0	1	6
		128.0	1	7
		256.0	2	9
		512.0	3	12
		1024.0	no further increment	73
AbRM	meropenem	0.125	1	1
		0.25	1	2
		0.5	1	3
		1.0	2	5
		2.0	2	7
		4.0	5	12
		8.0	3	15
		16.0	13	28
		32.0	no further increment	73
AbRI	imipenem	0.125	1	1
		0.25	1	2
		0.5	4	6
		1.0	10	16
		2.0	10	26
		4.0	12	38
		8.0	no further increment	73

AbRC - Ciprofloxacin-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant

AbRE - Erythromycin-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant

AbRM - Meropenem-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant

AbRI - Imipenem-resistant *A. baumannii* isogenic variant

Based on **Table 5.3**, AbRC was exposed to 0.5 µg/ml of ciprofloxacin for one day before being introduced to the MIC of 1.0 µg/ml. The variant was then exposed to 2.0 µg/ml, 4.0 µg/ml and 8.0 µg/ml for a day each in the respective order. The AbRE variant required three days of passaging in 16.0 µg/ml before a stable culture was achieved. Following which it was then introduced to 32.0 µg/ml for six subcultures, and 64.0 µg/ml

for 37 days before being exposed to the highest concentration of 128.0 µg/ml. The 64.0 µg/ml culture was continued along with the 128.0 µg/ml subcultures until the 73 days of resistance induction was completed. The same is for the 2.0 µg/ml subculture.

Variant AbRE showed the most robust adaptation thus far, whereby only a single day of acclimatization was enough to allow the generation of a stable culture in erythromycin. The variant was exposed to each concentration of the drug for a single day until tolerance to 256.0 µg/ml erythromycin was achieved. The variant required two days of adaptation in 256.0 µg/ml and three days in 521.0 µg/ml of the drug before being introduced to the highest erythromycin concentration of 1024.0 µg/ml. The 8.0 µg/ml and 1024.0 µg/ml subcultures were continued until the end of the 73 day induction period.

Variant AbRM and AbRE were each cultured in 0.125 µg/ml and 0.25 µg/ml of meropenem and imipenem respectively. Unlike the AbRM variant that required only a day of acclimatization to 0.5 µg/ml meropenem, the AbRI variant needed four days of daily passaging before being introduced to 1.0 µg/ml of the respective carbapenem. From here, the difference in AbRM and AbRI incubation periods in the same carbapenem concentration begin to differ greatly. Variant AbRM was able to adapt to 1.0 µg/ml and 2.0 µg/ml meropenem in two days time, whereas ABRI requires 10 days of acclimatization in both concentrations. The former also required only another five days of incubation in 4.0 µg/ml before acquiring resistance to the MIC of 8.0 µg/ml, while the latter required 12 days. Furthermore, variant AbRM was able to be further induced in 16.0 µg/ml and 32.0 µg/ml of meropenem, whereas the AbRI variant induction was halted at 8.0 µg/ml.

The red dotted-lines in the graphs indicate the MIC of each drug that the variants were exposed to. The distance between the dotted lines and the highest drug concentration signifies the sample's ability to further tolerate the antibiotic.

Figure 5.3: The Two-Fold Concentration Increment for Each Antibiotic Used in the Study over Time. The Red Dotted Line in Each Chart Represents the EUCAST MIC in *A. baumannii* Against the Respective Drug

As shown in **Figure 5.3**, the ciprofloxacin-challenged sample, AbRC required only 1-2 days to grow within the MIC and 16 days to achieve the high resistant variant, growing at 64 µg/ml ciprofloxacin. The highest tolerable ciprofloxacin resistance tested was 128 µg/ml, which was achieved on the 49th day of exposure; however the **Figure 5.4 (c)** shows a downtrend in its turbidity. The erythromycin-challenged sample also achieved resistant status within three days, and was able to grow at the highest tested concentration (1024 µg/ml) of erythromycin within approximately 13 days as well. The meropenem and imipenem-challenged variants lagged in their resistance acquisition, reaching the threshold on the 14th day, and 32nd day respectively. There was difficulty in acquiring a high-resistance variant for the carbapenem-challenged variants. The resistance induction for that class was halted once a stable culture was obtained at 16 µg/ml (meropenem) and 8 µg/ml (imipenem) concentration (around the 51st day of cultivation).

In AbRC and AbRE, the highest tolerable drug concentration was identified to be 128 µg/ml (128 times higher than the MIC) and 1024 µg/ml (256 times higher than the MIC), respectively. Although there is a possibility for the resistance to be increased further, the process would be superfluous and deemed unnecessary. In contrast to this, the highest tolerable drug concentration in the carbapenem-challenged variants was relatively low, especially in the imipenem-challenged variant, AbRI. The meropenem-challenged variant, AbRM managed to acquire resistance up to 32 µg/ml of meropenem, a concentration that is four times higher than its MIC. AbRI however was only successfully grown to its imipenem MIC as indicated in **Figure 5.3 (d)**.

5.3.3 Growth Tracking of Resistant Variants

Shown in **Figure 5.4** are the results of the resistance cultivation at the MIC (A, C, E, H) and at a concentration that is significantly higher than the threshold (B and D). The imipenem and imipenem-resistant variant was only exposed to a maximum of 8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively due to the difficulty in acquiring a stable culture beyond those points.

a) Resistance induction of AbRC in 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ciprofloxacin

CIP [2] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ ciprofloxacin

b) Resistance induction of AbRC in 64 µg/ml ciprofloxacin

CIP [64] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 64 µg/ml ciprofloxacin

c) Resistance induction of AbRC in 128 µg/ml ciprofloxacin

CIP [128] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 218 µg/ml ciprofloxacin

d) Resistance induction of AbRC in 8 µg/ml erythromycin

ERY [8] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 8 µg/ml erythromycin

e) Resistance induction of AbRC in 1024 µg/ml erythromycin

ERY [1024] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 1024 µg/ml erythromycin

f) Resistance induction of AbRC in 16 µg/ml meropenem

MEM [16] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 16 µg/ml meropenem

g) Resistance induction of AbRC in 32 µg/ml meropenem

MEM [32] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 32 µg/ml meropenem

h) Resistance induction of AbRC in 8 µg/ml imipenem

IMI [8] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 8 µg/ml imipenem

i) Combination of resistance induction tracking graphs A, D, F, and H.

MEM [16] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 16 µg/ml meropenem

ERY [8] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 8 µg/ml erythromycin

IMI [8] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 8 µg/ml imipenem

CIP [2] – *A. baumannii* isogenic variant acclimatized to 2 µg/ml ciprofloxacin

Figure 5.4: Graph of Optical Density (OD) taken per Day Throughout the Resistance Induction of the Isogenic Resistant Variants. The Black Diagonal Line in (a) Through (h) Represents the Logarithmic Trend Line of the Variants' Turbidity

The blue line in **Figure 5.4** indicates the OD of the control (susceptible parent strain) used. The resistance induction against each antibiotic was done simultaneously, hence the identical control in each of the graphs. The fluctuating OD in the control indicates that the irregular spikes and troughs in the resistant variants are not mainly due to the presence of the antibiotics, and may be caused by undetermined variables. Despite these fluctuations, there is an uptrend of OD values as depicted by the black line in graphs **a** through **g**, with the exception of **C**. The downtrend in the variant's growth depicted in **Figure 5.4 (c)** is probably due to the short data range. Despite this, the growth variant AbRC in 128 µg/ml erythromycin was proven to be stable. In **Figure 5.4 (e)**, the AbRE which was exposed to its two-fold erythromycin MIC shows a smaller increase in comparison with the other samples. This is attributed to the large OD variability exhibited between day 51 and day 59, where the value dropped below OD₆₀₀ of 2.0. A near similar pattern can be observed in the AbRI, in which the OD₆₀₀ has dropped below 1.0. However, variants AbRC and AbRM shows no such pattern during the same time range, suggesting that the sudden drop in turbidity is not due to a fault in the prepared media or the handling of the samples. It should be noted that variant AbRE subculture "ERY (46) 8.0" exhibited weak turbidity with strong pellicle (attributed by adherence to the inner wall of the universal bottle) formation on day 49, which resulted in an OD₆₀₀ of 0.407. The following day, subculture "ERY (47) 8.0" exhibited denser turbidity accompanied with "clumps" gathering at the bottom of the culture media and a weakly adhering pellicle. The clumping formation is likely generated by an increase in biofilm formation, allowing the individual cells to amass in a cloud of slime-like material. Both properties would in turn influence the OD₆₀₀, as the turbidity is no longer uniform, resulting in a less consistent reading. This sudden change in biofilm activity is likely due to a fluctuating survival response, resulting from a heterogenous culture of resistant and non-resistant subpopulations. The phenotypic properties in AbRI subcultures however showed no discernible changes, apart from the periodic loss of viscosity in subcultures "IMI (31d) 8.0", "IMI (32d) 8.0" and "IMI (36d) 8.0" in days 48, 49 and 54. The subcultures on days 50 through 53 however exhibited weak turbidity as well as weak viscosity attributed to biofilm production. The sudden loss and recovery of viscosity is unclear. As this phenotype is observed even when the AbRI subcultures were exposed to concentrations

well below the MIC and continues to increase in magnitude in subsequent passages, it is unlikely that this instability is due to the increase in drug concentration. It is possible that during the subculturing of “IMI (31d) 8.0” to “IMI (32d) 8.0”, an insufficient amount of starting material was provided, leading to a stunted growth in the latter. And a similar technical error was performed in “IMI (36d) 8.0” resulting in a recurrence of the loss of viscosity. This error is only unique to the AbRM and AbRI variants as they are the only cultures that produce biofilm under carbapenem exposure. Hence, there is a notable difficulty in shearing the biofilm before the culture can be transferred from these variants, resulting in a higher chance of failed subcultures. Evidently, after several attempts, this error was no longer an issue.

In addition to the periodically inconsistent growth exhibited in AbRM and AbRI variants, several instances of no growth were observed in the isogenic variants, which is indicative of a failure to adapt to the drug introduced. This pattern is mostly detected during the early phases when a variant is being exposed to an increased antimicrobial concentration (data not shown), which is to be expected.

Graph **i** in **Figure 5.4** shows the combined view of all resistant variants exposed to concentrations two-fold higher than their respective MIC for 73 continuous days, with the exception of imipenem. From the graph, it can be observed that AbRC and AbRE had no problems acclimatizing to ciprofloxacin and erythromycin, respectively. These variants were able to achieve stable growth with turbidity comparable to that of the susceptible control immediately after being introduced to the two-fold MIC. Although the same is for the carbapenem-challenged variants AbRM and AbRI, the latter showed unsteady peaks and troughs in the first few days. This however was short-lived.

From **Figure 5.3** and **Figure 5.4**, it can be deduced that the amount of time necessary for Ab00 to acclimatize to these four drugs varies. Ciprofloxacin and erythromycin resistance was achieved within a week of exposure, whereas the carbapenems require at least two weeks. The fact that the starting concentration for both carbapenems used were relatively low in comparison to the other two drugs has very well contributed to this. Surprisingly, of all the variants turbidity shown in **Figure 5.4 (i)**, AbRM shows the least amount of fluctuation when exposed to 16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 31 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ meropenem. This however, may be due to the drug providing a greater selective pressure,

which prevents any significant variations in turbidity. This can also be seen in AbRI to a certain extent, as there is a lack of large fluctuations after the initial exposure period.

5.3.4 Growth Curve of the Resistant Variants

Upon acquisition of stable resistant cultures at MIC, the growth curve of the variants and the susceptible parent was generated as depicted in **Figure 5.5**. An overview of the graph shows that there is a slight difference in growth rate between the susceptible parent, AbRC and AbRE. On the other hand AbRM shows a large difference in growth rate, where the turbidity measured is less than half of the susceptible parent.

Figure 5.5: Growth Curve of the Isogenic Resistant Variants and the Susceptible Parent, Ab00. AbRM was Used To Represent Growth Under Carbapenem Exposure in Both AbRI and AbRM

The results indicate that when the *A. baumannii* is acclimatized to ciprofloxacin and erythromycin, there is little consequence to the growth in the respective isogenic variants. This, in addition to the resistance induction charts shown in **Figure 5.4** indicates that these variants are capable of achieving growth comparable to that of the susceptible parent strain, which supports the earlier statement. Previously reported resistance mechanisms suggests that the acclimatization towards fluoroquinolones would induce a

permanent modification of the nucleic acid-maintenance proteins, GyrA, GyrB, ParC and ParE (Park et al., 2011). The modification effectively disables the drug from binding to the DNA-protein complex but would bear no significant deteriorative effects on the growth of the bacteria. This would explain the relatively stable growth rate despite the increased tolerance towards ciprofloxacin.

The same can be observed in the erythromycin resistant variant, AbRE. The presence of several efflux pumps in the susceptible parent strain has in theory provided the basis necessary for resistance acquisition in Ab00. Modifications in these pumps or in the regulators that would affect their production and assembly would have little consequence to their metabolic activity and growth (Hooper, 2001).

The most interesting development is in the meropenem-challenged variant, AbRM which shows a significantly lowered growth rate upon achieving meropenem resistance. This can be hypothesized to be due to two defense mechanisms in reaction to the carbapenem; i) a lowered activity to reduce the drug activity, ii) a side effect of the biofilm production, or iii) a metabolic cost for beta-lactamase production. Carbapenem efficiency is severely reduced in slow-growing cells, a state that is dubbed as “drug indifference” (Corona & Martinez, 2013). It is possible for some pathogens to opt for a lowered growth rate in order to reduce casualties induced by the drug. The metabolic cost of biofilm and/or beta-lactamase production could play a role in the growth rate reduction as well. Resistance mechanisms are thought to be inherently “expensive” to be maintained by a prokaryote’s metabolic machinery. A trait that is noticeable in some resistant pathogenic strains, where their ability to resume normal cellular activity has been greatly compromised upon manifesting resistant phenotypes (Corona & Martinez, 2013).

5.3.5 Resistance screening of isogenic variants

Once the high-level resistance has been acquired and considered stable, the susceptible and resistant variants (both low and high-level) were tested via antibiogram to validate their resistances. The results of the screening are as shown in **Table 5.4**. The low and high-level resistances for each variant are; 2 µg/ml and 64 µg/ml ciprofloxacin for AbRC, 8 µg/ml and 1024 µg/ml erythromycin for AbRE, 16 µg/ml and 32 µg/ml meropenem for AbRM, and 4 µg/ml and 8 µg/ml imipenem for AbRI, respectively.

Table 5.4
Antimicrobial Resistance Screening and Interpretation of the Resistant Variants

Antimicrobial disc (µg/ml)	Ab00	AbRC		AbRE				AbRM		AbRI								
		[2]	[64]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter (cm) / Interpretation																		
Eythromycin (15)	2.4	S	1.5	I	1.9	S	0	R	0	R	1.5	I	1.2	R	1.2	R	0.9	R
Ciprofloxacin (1)	2.4	U	0	R	0	R	1.5	U	0	R	1.3	U	1.2	U	1.3	U	0	R
Imipenem (10)	3.2	S	3.3	S	3.3	S	3.2	S	3.2	S	3.0	S	3	S	1.5	R	1.4	R
Imipenem (10)	3.2	S	3	S	3.1	S	3	S	2.5	S	0	R	0	R	1.0	R	0	R

R - Resistant, I - Intermediate, S - Susceptible, U - Unconfirmed

The susceptibility of the parent strain remains unchanged throughout the course of the resistance induction. All isogenic variants have acquired a complete resistance against their respective target antibiotics in both low and high-level resistant isolates, with the exception of the imipenem-resistant variants.

The ciprofloxacin-resistant isogenic variants (AbRC) displayed no secondary resistances, although there appears to be a decrease in inhibition zone diameter in erythromycin. The erythromycin-resistant isogenic variants (AbRE) on the other hand exhibit a lack of inhibition zones for erythromycin. Secondary resistances were also observed in the AbRE variants, with the high-level resistance variant, AbRE [1024] exhibiting complete resistance against ciprofloxacin. Both low and high-level AbRE displayed a secondary resistance against gentamycin. In the meropenem-resistant variants (AbRM), a secondary resistance against erythromycin was only observed in the high-level AbRM variant, with the low-level AbRM exhibiting intermediate resistance. The imipenem-resistant variants (AbRI) was observed to exhibit resistance against all of the tested antibiotics, with AbRI [8] showing a complete lack of ZOI when tested against ciprofloxacin and meropenem.

5.3.6 Whole-Genome Sequencing of the Resistant Isogenic *A. baumannii* Variants

The quality of trimmed reads is as shown in **Figure 5.6**. The threshold Phred score for the trimming process was set to 28, i.e. within the green zone. The initial quality ranges of the untrimmed sequences were relatively broad. Trimming however has resulted in a narrow interquartile range (as depicted by the yellow boxes) for all reads. This indicates a successful filtration of good quality reads above the green zone (phred score 28 and above).

Table 5.5
Sequencing Output of the Trimmed Sequencing Reads Generated via FastQC

Sample	Read	Total Sequences	Sequence length	%GC
AbRC	R1	75922	1-151	38
	R2	75922	1-151	37
AbRE	R1	179466	1-301	39
	R2	179466	1-300	39
AbRM	R1	154890	1-301	38
	R2	154890	1-301	38
AbRI	R1	264920	1-301	38
	R2	264920	1-301	38

The **Table 5.5** shows the overview of the sequencing results, where AbRC shows the least amount of total reads, while AbRI produced the highest amount of total sequences. Since AbRC was sequenced in a separate sequencing run than the rest, the read lengths for both reads were different compared to the others. This however should have no significant effect on the downstream analysis, as the quality of the reads has been reassured. It should be noted that the sequence length for AbRC is lower than the rest of the samples as it was run on a separate sequencing run using the 151 bp kit. This however does not significantly affect the downstream analysis. In addition, although the coverage for the AbRC sequencing reads is relatively lower, the downstream analysis using this output will be validated via PCR, which removes any uncertainties.

Figure 5.6: Quality of the Trimmed Sequencing Reads Viewed Using FastQC

5.3.7 Identification of variants in the resistant isogenic mutants

Upon confirmation of quality, the sequencing reads were then submitted to CLCbio for variant calling using the “Probabilistic Variant Detection Caller” tool under the default parameters. The susceptible parent, Ab00 annotated pseudomolecule was used as the reference. The results of each variant calling are as shown in **Table 5.6**, **Table 5.7**, **Table 5.8** and **Table 5.9**. Each of the variant calling produced included several repeated sequences and “insertions” covering the gaps present in the reference genome. It should be noted that variants occurring in non-coding regions were identified to be synonymous in nature and were excluded from the final list.

As shown in **Table 5.6**. A total of 23 variations were detected in AbRC and only one of which is detected in one of the target gene, *gyrA*. The remaining variants were identified in several genes pertaining to nucleotide transport and metabolism (*mtnN* and *purM*), intercellular trafficking, secretion and vesicular transport (*xcpX*), lipid transport and metabolism (I), and translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis (J). A large number of variants were also detected within a gene encoding a Group A colicins tolerance protein. A quick screening of the gene position revealed that it is located upstream of the *tolB* gene within a cluster of *tol* genes including *tolB* encoding a periplasm component of an efflux pump, and *tolR* and *tolQ* which encodes inner membrane components. To confirm the gene, the BASYS01118 sequence was aligned against the NCBI database, and the results returned a hit on an *A.baumannii* *tolA* gene at 99% identity.

Table 5.7 shows the 20 variants identified in the erythromycin-resistant isogenic mutant, AbRE. One variant was detected in genes *ftsI*, *bvgS*, *srrA*, *rlmN* and a gene encoding a ribonuclease I. In **Table 5.8** on the other hand, a single variant was detected in *atpD*, *epsL*, *mexB*, *irlR* and *dmlA* genes encoding an ATP synthase subunit beta, an uncharacterized sugar transferase EpsL, a multidrug resistance protein MexB, a transcriptional activator protein, and a D-malate dehydrogenase, respectively. Lastly, in **Table 5.9**, a single variant was identified in the *yceG* and *acrB* genes which encode a UPF0755 protein HI_0457 and an acriflavine resistance protein B, respectively. Two variants were also detected in the *ftsI* gene encoding a peptidoglycan synthase FtsI.

In addition to the aforementioned predicted mutations, several variants were also detected across multiple isogenic mutants. The CDS annotated to encode a “Spore Coat U Domain-Containing Protein” (BASYS01459), has a single variant present in all four isogenic mutants. The same is for the CDS encoding an “Elongation factor Tu” (BASYS03487), which houses two variants in AbRE, AbRM and AbRI, but only one in AbRC. Variations in two genes *ahpF* and *catF* were also noticed to be unusually common in AbRE, AbRE, and ABRI. Upon further inspection, it was discovered that these genes overlap one another in CDS BASYS0365 and BASYS03604, resulting in repeated variant calls where the sequences overlap. Moreover, *ahpF* and the overlapping *catF* genes were found to be highly fragmented and scattered within the assembled Ab00 genome. This is likely due to a lack of high quality reads covering the gene. As such, a reference *ahpF* gene retrieved from the reference strain *A. baumannii* AYE was used to align the Ab00 sequencing reads and extract the consensus Ab00 *ahpF* gene. This consensus was subsequently used in the downstream analysis.

Table 5.6

Variant Calling Result for the Ciprofloxacin-Resistant Isogenic Variant, AbRC

Reference Position	Ref.	Allele variants	Frequencies (%)	Gene (reference)	Gene name	Annotated protein function
198273	A	T	50	BASYS00190	<i>mtnN</i> [H]	5'-methylthioadenosine/S-adenosylhomocysteine nucleosidase [H]
1124073	C	T	100	BASYS01084	<i>gyrA</i> [H]	DNA gyrase subunit A [H]
1148409	A	C	50	BASYS01104	<i>purM</i> [H]	Phosphoribosylformylglycinamide cyclo-ligase [H]
1162755	C	C/T	60.0/40.0	BASYS01118	-	Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1162778	T	C/T	57.1/42.9			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1162790	T	T/C	55.6/44.4			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1162808	A	A/G	60.0/40.0			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1162817	G	A	66.7			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1162823	T	A	80			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1163162	C	C/A	57.1/42.9			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1163168	A	A/T	55.6/44.4			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1163189	C	C/T	50.0/50.0			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1163198	T	T/G	62.5/37.5			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1163201	T	T/C	62.5/37.5			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1163228	A	T/A	57.1/42.9			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1163249	C	C/T	57.1/42.9			Group A Colicins tolerance Protein
1541190	G	A	100	BASYS01459	-	Spore Coat U Domain-Containing Protein
2325576	A	G	50	BASYS02180	<i>xcpX</i> [H]	General secretion pathway protein K [H]
2526214	G	A	100	BASYS02388	-	Hypothetical Protein BASYS02388
				BASYS02389	-	Hypothetical Protein BASYS02389
3077295	A	T	100	BASYS02940	<i>yihG</i> [H]	Probable acyltransferase yihG [H]
3671030	C	C/T	50.0/50.0	BASYS03487	<i>(tuf1)</i> [H]	Elongation factor Tu [H]
3912266	A	A/C	62.5/37.5	BASYS03910	-	Probable transposase for transposon Tn903 [H]
3927504	C	T	66.7	BASYS03936	-	Conserved Hypothetical Protein

Table 5.7

Variant Calling Result for the Erythromycin-Resistant Isogenic Variant, AbRE

Reference Position	Reference	Allele variants	Frequencies (%)	Gene (reference)	Gene name	Annotated protein function
545942	C	T	100	BASYS00519	<i>ftsI</i> [H]	Peptidoglycan synthase ftsI [H]
728532	C	T	100	BASYS00705	-	Ribonuclease I
799413	C	T	100	BASYS00775	<i>bvgS</i> [H]	Virulence sensor protein BvgS [H]
1541190	G	A	100	BASYS01459	-	Spore Coat U Domain-Containing Protein
	G	A	100	BASYS01945	<i>srrA</i> [H]	Transcriptional regulatory protein srrA [H]
3426708	T	-	93.3	BASYS03268	<i>rlmN</i>	Ribosomal RNA large subunit methyltransferase N
3670873	G	A/G	55.2/44.8	BASYS03487	(<i>tufI</i> [H])	Elongation factor Tu [H]
3671030	C	C/T	52.4/47.6	BASYS03487	(<i>tufI</i> [H])	Elongation factor Tu [H]
3787820	C	T/C	66.7/33.3	BASYS03605	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3787823	C	T/C	66.7/33.3	BASYS03605	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3803402	A	T/A	59.5/40.5	BASYS03639	-	Transposase for insertion sequence element ISRM3 [H]
3803550	G	G/A	75.9/24.1	BASYS03639	-	Transposase for insertion sequence element ISRM3 [H]
3828654	A	T/A	62.5/37.5	BASYS03703	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3828732	C	T/C	56.3/43.8	BASYS03703	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3829780	G	G/A	71.4/28.6	BASYS03707	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3829822	A	A/C	75.0/25.0	BASYS03707	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3832270	C	C/T	63.2/36.8	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3832309	C	C/A	63.6/36.4	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3832351	G	G/T	54.2/45.8	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3912266	A	C/A	52.2/47.8	BASYS03910	-	Probable transposase for transposon Tn903 [H]

Table 5.8

Variant Calling Result for the Meropenem-Resistant Isogenic Variant, AbRM

Reference position	Reference	Allele variants	Frequencies (%)	Gene (reference)	Gene name	Annotated protein function
54216	G	A	100	BASYS00049	<i>atpD</i> [H]	ATP synthase subunit beta [H]
158820	C	A	100	BASYS00149	<i>epsL</i> [H]	Uncharacterized sugar transferase EpsL [H]
997571	G	A	100	BASYS00954	<i>mexB</i> [H]	Multidrug resistance protein MexB [H]
1541190	G	A	100	BASYS01459	-	Spore Coat U Domain-Containing Protein
2975400	C	G/C	62.5/37.5	BASYS02818	<i>irlR</i> [H]	Transcriptional activator protein irlR [H]
3112586	G	T	100	BASYS02973	<i>dmlA</i> [H]	D-malate dehydrogenase [decarboxylating] [H]
3670873	G	A/G	62.5/37.5	BASYS03487	<i>tufI</i> [H]	Elongation factor Tu [H]
3671030	C	C/T	52.4/47.6	BASYS03487	<i>tufI</i> [H]	Elongation factor Tu [H]
3787724	T	C	50	BASYS03604	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	NADH dehydrogenase [H]
				BASYS03605	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3787820	C	C/T	50.0/50.0	BASYS03604	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	NADH dehydrogenase [H]
				BASYS03605	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3787823	C	C/T	50.0/50.0	BASYS03604	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	NADH dehydrogenase [H]
				BASYS03605	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3803402	A	T	65.2	BASYS03639	-	Transposase for insertion sequence element ISRM3 [H]
3832270	C	T/C	60.0/40.0	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3832309	C	A	66.7	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3832351	G	T/G	60.0/40.0	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3912266	A	C/A	54.2/45.8	BASYS03910	-	Probable transposase for transposon Tn903 [H]

Table 5.9

Variant Calling Result for the Imipenem-Resistant Isogenic Variant, AbRI

Reference Position	Reference	Allele variants	Frequencies (%)	Gene (reference)	Gene name	Annotated gene function
545963	C	T	100	BASYS00519	<i>ftsI</i> [H]	Peptidoglycan synthase <i>ftsI</i> [H]
546154	G	A	100	BASYS00519	<i>ftsI</i> [H]	Peptidoglycan synthase <i>ftsI</i> [H]
1191148	T	G	100	BASYS01149	<i>yceG</i> [C]	UPF0755 protein HI_0457 [H]
1541190	G	A	100	BASYS01459	-	Spore Coat U Domain-Containing Protei
2065459	T	G	100	BASYS01947	<i>acrB</i> [H]	Acriflavine resistance protein B [H]
2470208	-	A	90.9			
3670873	G	G/A	55.6/44.4	BASYS03487	<i>(tufI</i> [H]	Elongation factor Tu [H]
3671030	C	T/C	65.9/34.1	BASYS03487	<i>(tufI</i> [H]	Elongation factor Tu [H]
3787820	C	T/C	65.0/35.0	BASYS03605	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3787823	C	T/C	61.9/38.1	BASYS03605	<i>catF</i> [H]	Beta-ketoadipyl-CoA thiolase [H]
3803402	A	T/A	60.0/40.0	BASYS03639	-	Transposase for insertion sequence element ISRM3 [H]
3803550	G	G/A	73.9/26.1	BASYS03639	-	Transposase for insertion sequence element ISRM3 [H]
3825670	C	C/T	80.9/19.1	BASYS03690	-	Conserved Hypothetical Protein
3828654	A	T	81.8	BASYS03703	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3828732	C	T/C	63.6/36.4	BASYS03703	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3832270	C	C/T	58.3/41.7	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3832309	C	C/A	57.7/42.3	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3832351	G	G/T	52.4/47.6	BASYS03710	<i>ahpF</i> [H]	Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F [H]
3912266	A	A/C	53.1/46.9	BASYS03910	-	Probable transposase for transposon Tn903 [H]

5.3.8 Primer Validation

Using the variant calling results, 18 pairs of primers were designed via PerlPrimer. As shown in **Figure 5.7**, all primers were successful in amplifying the correct target size. The amplicons were then purified using the Agencourt AMPure XP PCR purification kit. Once purified, the amplicons were sent for sequencing. The results of the amplicon sequencing were screened for quality and realigned to the reference sequence to confirm specificity.

Figure 5.7: Gel Electrophoresis of the Primer Validation Using Ab00 as the Template

5.3.9 Variant Validation

For the variant validation, one sample from the highest resistance concentration was selected; ciprofloxacin, (128 µg/ml), erythromycin (1024 µg/ml), meropenem (32 µg/ml), and imipenem (8 µg/ml). The latest samples with the highest OD₆₀₀ were opted; ciprofloxacin (day 70), erythromycin (day 67), meropenem (day 67), and imipenem (day 67). After the DNA extraction on these was complete, the PCR, gel electrophoresis and amplicon sequencing was done accordingly. The results of the sequencing are as shown in **Figure 5.8**.

a) Validation of AbRC *gyrA* mutation using AbY20_b primers

Ab00_gyrA_AbY20; susceptible parent strain

C9_20b_cut; Ciprofloxacin-resistant variant, sample C9

b) Validation of AbRC yihG mutation using AbY41 primers

Ab00_gyrA_AbY20; parent strain amplicon
C9_41_AbY41_F; AbRC variant, sample C9 amplicon

c) Validation of AbRE ftsI mutation using AbY1 primers

Ab001_AbY1_F; parent strain amplicon
E10_AbY1_F; AbRC variant, sample E10 amplicon

d) Validation of AbRE ribonuclease I gene using AbY2 primers

Ab00_AbY2_F; parent strain amplicon

E10_AbY2_F; AbRC variant, sample E10 amplicon

e) Validation of AbRE bvgS mutation using AbY3 primers

Ab00_AbY3_F; parent strain amplicon

E10b_AbY3_F; AbRC variant, sample E10 amplicon

f) Validation of AbRE *rlmN* mutation using AbY4 primers

Ab00_AbY4_F; parent strain amplicon

E10_AbY4_F; AbRC variant, sample E10 amplicon

g) Validation of AbRE *srrA* mutation using AbY5 primers

Ab005_AbY5_F; parent strain amplicon

E105_AbY5_F; AbRC variant, sample E10 amplicon

h) Validation of AbRM mexB mutation using AbY22 primers

Ab00_22_AbY22_F; parent strain amplicon
M922_AbY22_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

i) Validation of AbRM spore coat formation gene using AbY23 primers

Ab00_AbY23_F; parent strain amplicon
AbRM_AbY23_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

j) Validation of AbRM epsL mutation using AbY24 primers

Ab00_24_AbY24_F; parent strain amplicon
M924_AbY24_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

k) Validation of AbRM atpD mutation using AbY25 primers

Ab00_25_AbY25_F; parent strain amplicon
M925_AbY25_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

l) Validation of AbRM *tuf1* mutation using AbY26 primers

Ab00_26_AbY26_F; parent strain amplicon
M926_AbY26_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

m) Validation of AbRM *irlR* mutation using AbY30 primers

Ab00_30_AbY30_F; parent strain amplicon
M930_AbY30_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

n) Validation of AbRM *ahpF* mutation using AbY32a, AbY32b1 and AbY32b2 primers

A.baumannii_AYE_ahpF; Reference *ahpF* gene from *A. baumannii* strain AYE
M932a_AbY32a_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon amplified using AbY32a primer set
M932b1_AbY32b1_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon amplified using AbY32b1 primer set
M932b2_AbY32b2_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon amplified using AbY32b2 primer set

o) Validation of AbRM *ISMR3* mutation using AbY33 primers

Ab00_33_AbY33_F; parent strain amplicon
M933_AbY33_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

p) Validation of AbRM Tn903 mutation using AbY34 primers

Ab00_AbY34_F; parent strain amplicon
M9_AbY34_F; AbRC variant, sample M9 amplicon

q) Validation of AbRI yceG mutation using AbY35 primers

Ab00_35_AbY35_F; parent strain amplicon
I7_35_AbY35_F; AbRC variant, sample I7 amplicon

r) Validation of AbRI *acrB* mutation using AbY36 primers

Ab00_acrB; parent strain amplicon
 I7_36_AbY36_F; AbRC variant, sample I7 amplicon

s) Validation of AbRI *ftsI* mutations using AbY37 primers

Ab00_37_AbY37_F; parent strain amplicon
 I7_37_AbY37_F; AbRC variant, sample I7 amplicon

Figure 5.8: Amplicon Sequencing and Alignment Results of the Target Genes

The results of the variant validation confirmed several of the predicted mutations in the resistant isolates as shown in **Figure 5.8**. In isogenic mutant AbRC, only two variants occurring in the *gyrA* and *yihG* genes were confirmed. On the other hand, in sample AbRE, four mutations were verified to occur in genes *ftsI*, *bvgS*, *srrA*, and a ribonuclease I encoding sequence. The carbapenem-challenged isolates, AbRM and AbRI also had four mutations verified. The former was confirmed to carry variants in *mexB*, *epsL*, *ahpF* and *atpD*, whereas in the latter, the *ftsI*, *yceG*, *ahpF* and *acrB* mutations were confirmed.

Table 5.10
Verified Mutations Occurring in the Isogenic Variants

Sample	gene	mutation	A.acid change	Property change	
AbRC	<i>gyrA</i>	242C>T	S81L	P, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
	<i>yihg</i>	574A>T	T192S	SP, Neu	> P, Nue
AbRE	<i>ftsI</i>	1523C>T	P508L	NP, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
	<i>ribonuc. I</i>	178C>T	Q60X	P, Neu	> X
	<i>bvgS</i>	1268C>T	P423L	NP, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
	<i>srrA</i>	272C>T	A91V	HPb, NP, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
AbRM	<i>mexB</i>	542C>T	S181L	P, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
	<i>epsL</i>	207G>T	D92Y	P, Acidic	> Polar, Neutral
	<i>ahpF</i>	Multi	Multi	Multi	> Multi
	<i>atpD</i>	497C>T	A166V	HPb, NP, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
AbRI	<i>ahpF</i>	Multi	Multi	Multi	> Multi
	<i>acrB</i>	1430T>G	V477G	HPb, NP, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
	<i>ftsI</i>	1544C>T	A515V	HPb, NP, Neu	> HPb, NP, Neu
	<i>ftsI</i>	1735G>A	A579T	HPb, NP, Neu	> SP, Neu
P	- Polar	HPb	- Hydrophobic	Multi	- Multiple mutations/properties
NP	- Non-polar	Neu	- Neutral		

Upon further analysis, the mutation sites in each affected gene was identified and summarized in **Table 5.10**. The position of the mutations was determined by aligning the amplicon sequences with the complete gene sequence listed in the BASys report using Clustal Omega (Sievers et al., 2011). The sequencing chromatogram of each mutation site was scrutinized as well, to rule out any false positives. The analysis confirmed that a majority of the mutations are transitions, where cytosines are converted to tyrosine. The only exception was in the AbRM *epsL* gene which is a transversion from guanine to tyrosine. This has been reported to be fairly common due to the high homoplastic nature

of transitions, which carry less detrimental effects as it results in a switch between two pyrimidines of the similar structure (Broughton et al., 2000). The results also coincide with reports stating transition mutation frequency far outnumbers that of transversions (Ochman, 2003).

The majority of the mutations listed have resulted in limited change in properties, whereby most neutral amino acids were swapped for another neutral molecule. However, the changes in the structural properties on these amino acids are perhaps more significant. The mutations in *gyrA*, and *mexB* have both resulted in a change from serine to leucine, theoretically modifying the protein structure. The switch from a relative small to a larger molecule alone is enough to suggest a potential side effect. The additional property change from polar to non-polar would also have an effect on the mutant protein. The switch from proline to leucine was also identified in AbRE *ftsI* and *bvgS* genes. However, since the structural traits of the former are notably similar to serine, the same effects could be hypothesized (Betts & Russel, 2003). Interestingly, both AbRE and AbRI variants have evolved a mutation in the *ftsI* gene, albeit non-identical. Moreover, only a single variation was confirmed in the AbRE *ftsI* gene, while AbRI developed two variants. Perhaps, the least significant modification is in the *srrA* gene in the AbRE variant, where alanine was swapped for valine. Although, even though both of which are hydrophobic and non-polar in nature, valine provides a structural motif similar to the previously discussed leucine. This may modify the final protein structure enough to change its activity. In contrast, mutations identified in the *epsL* and ribonuclease I genes are more notable, whereby the former was swapped from an acidic to a neutral amino acid, while the latter was modified into a stop codon. In the former, the alteration results in a drastic change in the amino acid positional preference. The charged, polar nature of an aspartate normally results in it being exposed in protein surfaces, whereas the opposite is for the hydrophobic tyrosine. The general function of tyrosine has also been reported to be closer to that of the previously discussed serine. On the other hand, the ribonuclease I mutation resulting in an amber stop codon (UAG) is noteworthy as well. The mutation occurred quite early in the amino acid sequence (60 aa), and although the exact ramifications of this change is unclear, two possibilities may be theorized; i) a

deactivation of the RNase I, or ii) a modification of the RNase activity (Subbarayan & Deutscher, 2001).

It was also noted variants AbRM and AbRI have developed completely different mutations despite both being exposed to a carbapenem-class antibiotics. The mutations in AbRM were identified to potentially alter exopolysaccharide production (*epsL*) as well as energy production and/or consumption (*atpD*), while mutations in AbRI seem to emphasize on peptidoglycan synthesis (*ftsI*). However, both AbRM and AbRI have developed a mutation in an efflux pump component; *mexB* and *acrB*, respectively.

The results of the amplicon sequencing using the AbY34 primer pair suggest the presence of varying nucleotide sequences. To confirm this, the Tn903 transposase gene (BASYS03910) was BLASTed against the NCBI database. The results matched to several sequences, two of which belong to a single *A. baumannii* strain AB0057. After confirming via multiple sequence alignment it is likely that Ab00 possesses two similar but non-identical sequences as well, which were simultaneously amplified by the AbY34 primers. In addition this suggests a false mutation as identified during the variant-calling process.

From the analysis, it can be inferred that a single strain is capable of varying mutational modifications in response to selective pressures attributed by different antibiotics. Moreover, exposure to ciprofloxacin was noted to confer only two mutations, while the other drugs have resulted in a higher number of modifications.

5.4 CONCLUSION

Four mutant isogenic variants were successfully generated from a single susceptible parent. The increment in inhibitory concentration for each of the isogenic variants was recorded, revealing a rapid resistance acquisition when exposed to ciprofloxacin and erythromycin. In contrast, the meropenem and imipenem challenged variants showed a delayed resistance acquisition. Sequencing and genomic analysis of the isogenic variants revealed several variations within each of the successor strains. The relevant mutations were screened and the translational effects were analyzed. Significant side effects were hypothesized in the AbRC *gyrA*, AbRE *ribonuclease I*, AbRM *epsL*, and AbRI *ftsI*.

CHAPTER SIX

MUTATION TRACKING AND STABILITY ANALYSIS OF RESISTANT *Acinetobacter baumannii* ISOGENIC VARIANTS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

In the previous chapter, the cumulative variations present in the isogenic mutants emphasize the complexity of mutation acquisition in *A. baumannii* when exposed to different antimicrobials. However, based on several reports, it is likely that these mutations occur at different intervals throughout the resistance induction process; a concept referred to as “Mutation rate” (Martinez & Baquero, 2000). This theory puts into account the various changes that the genome undergoes throughout the selection process, which includes deleterious, non-deleterious and beneficial mutations as a whole. Due to the stochastic nature of mutation events during the selection process, it is difficult to pinpoint every single variation that arises throughout the procedure. However, through the use of whole-genome sequencing (WGS) technology, it has become possible to identify these variants by comparing the genome of the susceptible parent and the isogenic mutant(s). Although, it is not feasible to track these mutations on an almost daily basis due to the high cost of WGS technology (currently), by combining it with the less expensive PCR and amplicon sequencing methods, a more in-depth cumulative mutation study can be carried out (Lynch et al., 1999; Lee et al., 2012; Maharjan et al., 2012).

Mutations in a pathogen are often associated with the perceivable changes in its phenotype. This is especially true in terms of antimicrobial resistance acquisition. However, it is a common misconception that specific phenotypic alterations are a product of the same genotypic modification (Martinez & Baquero, 2000). In some cases, several genes are either directly or indirectly responsible for regulating or conferring antimicrobial resistance. An example of this would be the fluoroquinolone resistance in some *A. baumannii* strains, where an upregulation of efflux activity or a mutation in the quinolone resistance determinant region (QRDR) can both confer resistance to the same drug. Combinatorial mutations in single or several genes have also been reported to be a

result of MDR selection (Davis et al., 2011). However, information on the progression of these mutations is scarce, specifically in *A. baumannii* under the exposure towards fluoroquinolones, macrolides and carbapenems.

In addition, the presence of a pre-existing mutation has also been reported to improve the mutation rate in a particular strain. In combination with high antibiotic concentrations, these previously acquired mutations would boost the generation of new variations in the genome. Moreover, extra stressors such as metabolic cost resulting in slow growth may also contribute to the accumulation of new mutations, whereby the non-growing parent cells generate favorable mutations through stress-induced mutagenesis (Quiñone-Soto et al., 2012). This directed mutation is also responsible for preventing or correcting detrimental variations in the genome (Foster, 1993; Roth & Andersson, 2004).

On top of the accumulation of mutations throughout a selection process, the resistance stability of an isogenic variant should also be put into consideration. Early exposure to antimicrobials may incur an immediate response in a pathogen, which could manifest in a change in expression and even lead to a genetic modification (Depardieu et al., 2007). It is also possible for further alterations in the genome to occur when the pathogen is continually exposed to high antimicrobial concentrations (Davies & Davies, 2010). There is currently a lack of understanding in terms of the sequential mutation events and its correlation with the acquisition and stability of antimicrobial resistance in *A. baumannii*.

The aims here were; i) to confirm the time point and order of mutation events via PCR for all of the *A. baumannii* isogenic variants acquired in the previous chapter; ii) to identify the heterogeneity of the resistance throughout the induction period and; iii) to determine the stability of the acquired resistances in various storage conditions.

6.2 METHODS

Figure 6.1: Overview of Methodology

6.2.1 Mutation Timeframe Establishment

Upon validation of the variants called, an aliquot of the isogenic mutants from each drug concentration is then sampled (**Table 6.1**). The DNA of each sample was extracted and stored at -80°C until further use. PCR runs were performed using samples from the highest to the lowest concentration to discern the first occurrence of mutation. The selection of samples for the PCR was however tailored based on the results received.

For the ciprofloxacin-resistant isogenic variant (AbRC), samples C1 through C8 were all screened for mutations in the *gyrA* gene, to rule out any signs of reverse mutations. The same was applied for the remaining target mutations; *recB* and *tolA*. Following the pattern of results gained from the AbRC mutation screening, the samples selected for the *recC* mutation screening was limited to C2. To discern the first occurrence of the *gyrA* mutation, two more samples (C8a and C8b) were sampled and tested for variations.

For the erythromycin-resistant isogenic variant (AbRE), PCR targeting the *ftsI*, *ribonuclease I*, *bvgS*, *rlmN* and *srrA* genes were run on samples E9, E8 and E7 to determine the initial mutation event. Sample E2 was also tested to rule out or confirm early onset mutations in the target genes. Following the acquisition of results, screening for *bvgS* mutations were carried out on samples E1, E3, and E5. Further *srrA* mutation screening was also done on sample E1.

For the meropenem-resistant isogenic variant (AbRM), samples M8 was first screened for the AbRM variants listed. Following which, samples M7, M4 and M1 were screened for *mexB*, spore coat gene, *ahpF* and *Tn903* mutations. Once results were acquired and analyzed, *mexB* mutations were further screened in samples M5 and M6, whereas *epsL* mutations were screened in all of the remaining samples. Due to the multiple heterogeneous mutations present in the *ahpF* gene tested in the tested samples, no further screening was done on this target gene. For the imipenem-resistant isogenic variant (AbRI), sample I6 was screened for mutations in the AbRI variants listed.

The results of the amplicon sequencing for the mutation timepoint samples were analyzed using the UGENE (Okonechnikov et al., 2012). The relevant genes from the susceptible parent strain Ab00 was used as the wild type reference for the alignment.

6.2.2 Determination of Mutations in Extended Exposure to MIC

In addition to the high drug concentration exposure, the effects of extended exposure at MIC were also tested. Each isogenic variant was passaged daily in their respective antibiotics at their relevant MIC. These cultures were sampled and their DNA was extracted in the same manner described in the mutation timeframe establishment (Table 6.1). The samples were then screened for the relevant mutations.

Table 6.1

Sample Selection for the Establishment of Mutation Time Point

AbRC													Extended
Sample	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8a	C8b	C8	C9	C3x	
[Ciprofloxacin]	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	16.0	32.0	64.0	64.0	64.0	128.0	2.0	
Day#	4	4	5	5	6	10	16	19	26	48	62	70	
Sample OD	0.916	0.916	0.658	0.385	0.418	0.506	0.318	0.294	1.181	1.813	0.845	2.707	

AbRE													Extended
Sample	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10a	E10b	E10	E3x
[Erythromycin]	2.0	4.0	8.0	16.0	32.0	64.0	128.0	256.0	512.0	1024.0	1024.0	1024.0	8.0
Day#	4	5	5	6	7	8	9	12	14	16	19	67	70
Sample OD	1.991	1.634	0.888	1.291	1.851	0.438	0.759	1.054	1.353	0.752	1.568	2.323	2.323

AbRM											Extended
Sample	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M8x	
[Meropenem]	0.125	0.25	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	16.0	32.0	16	
Day#	4	5	6	8	10	15	20	31	63	70	
Sample OD	0.778	0.578	0.712	1.445	0.329	1.192	0.893	1.365	1.476	1.183	

AbRI								Extended
Sample	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	n/a
[Imipenem]	0.125	0.25	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	n/a
Day#	5	8	11	19	27	38	67	n/a
Sample OD	0.874	N/A	1.963	1.777	2.606	1.188	1.46	n/a

*a total of nine samples was selected, labeled C1 through C9, with a 2-fold increase in ciprofloxacin concentration (0.5 µg/ml through 128 µg/ml), respectively.

6.2.3 Preparation of Samples for Stability Tests

Figure 6.2: Flowchart of the Stability Test Performed on the Resistant Isogenic Variants

As illustrated in **Figure 6.2**, once resistance has been acquired, the cultures were passaged daily in MHB containing the relevant antimicrobials for seven days to ensure growth consistency (measured via spectrophotometer, OD_{600}). Upon confirmation of consistent growth, the seventh-day cultures were then inoculated into and cultured overnight in two batches; i) with antimicrobials (acclimatized culture) and, ii) without antimicrobials (unacclimatized culture).

The unacclimatized cultures were then aliquoted into two sets; with antimicrobials (St4+), and without antimicrobials (St4-). The aliquots were then stored in 4°C. The acclimatized cultures were also stored in 4°C (St4b). A second set of samples was prepared and stored in -80°C, where; unacclimatized culture aliquoted with

antimicrobials (St-80+), unacclimatized culture aliquoted without antimicrobials (St-80-), and acclimatized culture aliquots(St-80b). This set of aliquots was prepared with sterile 30% glycerol.

The seventh-day cultures were also inoculated into freshly prepared MHB without antimicrobials. This third set of cultures (St37-) were incubated at 37°C and passaged daily.

6.2.4 Stability at -80°C

The prepared aliquots were stored in 30% glycerol and slowly adjusted to -80°C by first incubating in 4°C for one hour, followed by incubation in -20°C for another hour. The samples were then stored at -80°C for five days. After which, the frozen aliquots were readjusted to room temperature and then revived in MHB overnight. Each of the aliquots were then tested for resistance via disc diffusion; Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin, Gentamicin, Meropenem and Imipenem.

6.2.5 Stability at 4°C

The prepared aliquots were stored in 4°C for five days. After which the samples were then readjusted to room temperature and recultured in MHB overnight. Each of the aliquots were then tested for resistance via disc diffusion; Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin, Gentamicin, Meropenem and Imipenem.

6.2.6 Stability in Absence of Selective Pressure

The samples were passaged into MHB without any antimicrobials daily for a total of seven days. To monitor changes in resistance, each subculture was also passaged into MHB with their respective antimicrobial concentrations. The resistance of these subcultures was then validated using disc diffusion.

6.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.3.1 Identification of Mutation Time Point

The mutation tracking charts below were generated by compiling the amplicon sequencing results from in each isogenic variant. The full chart is shown in **Appendix A**.

Figure 6.3: Mutation Tracking of Ciprofloxacin-Resistant Variant, AbRC

As shown in **Figure 6.3**, the first occurrence of mutation in *gyrA* was initially determined to be in sample C8. However, to further narrow down the time of mutation, samples C8a and C8b were selected on days 19 and 26 for screening. Upon analysis, sample C8b (64 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ciprofloxacin) was determined to be the first resistant variant carrying a mutation. The sample was exposed to the 64 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration for a total of 11 days upon increment from the previous 32 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ exposure period, until the mutation was first identified. A second mutation was noted in the *yhG* gene, occurring in sample C8 (day 48) in 64.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ciprofloxacin.

Figure 6.4: Mutation Tracking of Erythromycin-Resistant Variant, AbRE

In the AbRE variant, the first occurrence of mutation in both *ftsI*, ribonuclease I was identified to be on day 67 (**Figure 6.4**). Mutations in genes *bvgS* and *srrA* on the other hand, were identified on days 4, and 5, respectively. The *rlmN* gene was screened for mutations on days 9, 12, 14, and 67. However, no genetic alterations were detected. A prolonged MIC exposure sample, E3x was also tested, effectively ruling out any potential for back mutation in the *rlmN* in both threshold and high-level erythromycin.

Figure 6.5: Mutation Tracking of Meropenem-Resistant Variant, AbRM

In the AbRM variant, the first mutation was identified in gene *epsL* occurring in sample M1 (day 4) at 0.125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of meropenem (**Figure 6.5**). Another mutation was also detected in the *ahpF* gene on sample M1. Following this, a third was determined in *mexB* in sample M6 (day 15) at 4.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The three mutations were confirmed to be present in the subsequent samples, including the prolonged exposure to MIC (Sample M8x) and high concentrations of meropenem (sample M9).

Figure 6.6: Mutation Tracking of Imipenem-Resistant Variant, AbRI

In variant AbRI, mutations were identified in samples I6 (day 38) and I7 (day 67). The first occurrence of mutation in the *acrB* gene was noted in sample I6, when exposed to 4.0 µg of imipenem (**Figure 6.6**). The same mutation was subsequently noted in sample I7 as well. Two mutations were noted in the *ftsI* gene, whereby the first was noted in sample I4 (day 19) and the second variation in sample I7 (day 67).

The results obtained from the ciprofloxacin resistance are in concordance with reports stating that a mutation in the *gyrA* gene would confer resistance. However, the mutation detected in the AbRC isogenic variant was not present until much later in the induction period. This suggests a primary resistance mechanism present in *A. baumannii* which supports initial resistance prior to mutation. The lack of any other mutations also indicate that any changes allowing the primary resistance was an intrinsic mechanism and did not require any modifications at the genetic level. It is possible that the activation of efflux components as stated by Ardebili et al. could play a role in the primary resistance against ciprofloxacin (Ardebili et al., 2013). Further screening performed also ruled out any mutations in the *recC*, *recB* and *tolA* regions. This in turn strengthens previous hypotheses that a single *gyrA* mutation alone may be sufficient to confer stable ciprofloxacin resistance.

Additionally, AbRC was also confirmed to develop a mutation in a signaling-related gene; *yihG* responsible for encoding the acyltransferase protein located in the cell membrane. Theoretically, this is indicative of a modification in quorum sensing, as one of the major components for such mechanisms in Gram negative bacteria involves the N-acyl homoserine lactones (Reyes-Arellano et al., 2013). This modification is also noted to be in contrast to the AbRE and AbRM mutations, whereby signaling-related genes were altered during the early stages of exposure to antimicrobials.

The number of variants occurring in the AbRE variant was unexpected. However, only two mutations occurred before the MIC, suggesting an early onset genetic alteration due to selective pressure. The genes involved in the early mutations; *bvgS* and *srrA* are associated with signaling, chemotaxis and transcriptional regulation. This implies a change in quorum sensing and/or a gene expression. The modifications in *bvgS* have been stated to result in a constitutive expression of the relevant genes being expressed (Coyne et al., 2010). As the AbRE *srrA* gene is located within close proximity to a signal

transduction histidine-protein kinase, *BaeS* as well as an RND-type efflux gene (BASYS01943) further downstream, it is possible that the *srrA* mutation would lead to the same effect as with the *bvgS* modification as shown in **Figure 6.7** (Nishino et al., 2005). Moreover, the gene is also located within proximity of a set of *acrB* and *mtrC* genes encoding efflux components on the opposite strand. The expression of which may be regulated by a form of pervasive transcription inclusive of the *srrA* gene (Lybecker et al., 2014).

Unlike the *bvgS* and *srrA* genes, the occurrence of late onset mutations in *ftsI* and ribonuclease I were identified only within the later stages of high-level exposure. Upon identification of the mutations in sample E10 (day 67), two more samples on day 16 (E10a) and 19 (E10b) were selected for screening. However, no mutations in either *ftsI* or ribonuclease I were identified in these two newly selected samples. The same screening was then run on the extended MIC exposure samples E3x (8.0 µg/ml at day 70) but the results were no different. It can be deduced that these mutations will only occur under prolonged exposure to high concentrations of erythromycin. Interestingly, mutations in *ftsI* have been associated with beta-lactamase resistance, but no reports have correlated any variations in this gene with macrolide tolerance (Leclercq et al., 2013). The mutation in the ribonuclease I gene, as discussed in the chapter 5.3.9 also has not been reported to have any direct influence on macrolide resistance. It can be theorized that the mutation in the RNase I protein would lead to upregulation in efflux activity, leading to an increased macrolide resistance (Subbarayan & Deutscher, 2001).

Figure 6.7: An *srrA* Gene Positioned Upstream of a Signal Transduction Histidine-Protein Kinase, *BaeS* and an RND-Type Efflux Gene (BASYS01943)

One of the genes exhibiting the first mutation, *epsL* (detected in variant AbRM) encodes an uncharacterized sugar transferase under the bacterial sugar transferase family. The UniProtKB (locus EPSL_BACSU, accession P71062) database suggests that this gene plays a role in exopolysaccharide production involved in biofilm formation. Furthermore, this particular extracellular structure is responsible for establishing adhesion between cells and potentially with other surfaces as well. A brief comparative screening between Ab00 BASys and RAST annotations revealed the product to be a lipid carrier, UDP-N-acetylgalactosaminyltransferase (EC 2.0.1.-). This in turn implies that the *epsL* gene may function as a transporter for the biofilm components in the construction of a working exopolysaccharide layer (Thorne & Kodicek, 1966).

In addition to *epsL*, the *ahpF* gene encoding an Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F was also identified to carry mutations as early as day 4. As denoted by UniProtKB, the protein is responsible for providing protection against DNA damage induced by exposure to alkyl hydroperoxides upon combination with AhpC. This is evidenced by the increased hydrogen peroxide tolerance exhibited upon an upregulated AhpF production in *P. aeruginosa* (Cierniak *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 6.8: F-type ATP Synthase Found in Gram Negative Bacteria. The F_0 Region Generates Conformation Shifts Necessary for ATP Hydrolysis in the F_1 Region (Golizai, 2012)

The *atpD* mutation exhibited in sample AbRM was noted to occur at the late stages of meropenem exposure (day 70). The lack of the same mutation in sample M8x suggests that a combination of both time and concentration is necessary to incite the alteration. The gene encodes the ATP synthase β subunit located within the cell interior, as shown in **Figure 6.8**. The β subunit functions as a part of the F_1 multiprotein cytoplasmic complex responsible for the hydrolysis of ATP. It is possible that the mutation in this subunit may result in a lowered efficiency for nucleotide-binding, which in turn would reduce metabolic activity in response to carbapenem exposure (Golizai, 2012; Corona & Martinez, 2013).

Figure 6.9: Illustration of Mutation in the AtpD Protein Functional Domains in Isogenic Variant AbRM

Moreover, from the amino acid translation analysis, the *atpD* A166V mutation occurs within the P-loop NTPase fold domain responsible for nucleoside triphosphate hydrolase, as denoted by the InterPro database (IPR027417), as shown in **Figure 6.9**. Structurally, the addition of a C β branch may result in a steric hindrance significant enough to infer an alteration in nucleotide-binding.

Figure 6.10: Illustration of Mutations in the FtsI Protein Functional Domains in Isogenic Variant AbRI

As previously noted in the AbRE variant, mutations in the *ftsI* gene was also detected in imipenem-resistant variant, AbRI. Unlike the former however, AbRI exhibited two mutations in a single gene. Further analysis of the mutation sites via InterProScan 5 revealed that the variants occurred in two separate domains in the FtsI

protein, as shown in **Figure 6.10** (Quevillion et al., 2005). The first *ftsI* mutation (day19) was noted to occur in the penicillin binding protein transpeptidase-like functional domain (IPR012338 / IPR0460). According to the annotation provided by the Interpro database, this domain essentially exerts the same function as beta-lactamases in regards to its penicillin-binding properties (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/interpro/entry/IPR012338>). The second mutation (day 67) was detected in the penicillin-binding domain (IPR005311). Information on this domain is currently lacking, but it is theorized to play a role in the polymerization of penicillin-binding proteins, which essentially grants similar function with the previously discussed domain.

Interestingly, it was discovered that the first *ftsI* mutation on the 38th day of exposure to imipenem, another mutation was also detected in the *acrB* gene. The gene encodes the acridine resistant protein B, a component of the acridine resistance efflux pump. When compared with the development of *mexB* mutation in AbRM, it is possible that the alteration in *acrB* occurred before the *ftsI* mutation. However, due to the low abundance of growth in the AbRI samples between samples I5 and I6, it is difficult to acquire sufficient DNA for testing. Regardless, both *ftsI* and *acrB* genes play a role in the removal or deactivation of beta-lactams. This suggests that, in contrast to when exposed to meropenem, AbRI will immediately modify its penicillin-binding proteins when challenged with increasingly higher imipenem concentrations. This also suggests that a modification in signaling genes (e.g. *bvgS* in AbRM) is not always a primary mode of adaptation to carbapenems.

6.3.2 Heterogeneity in Target Genes

The amplicon sequencing of the target genes revealed several discrepancies in the homogeneity of some of the mutations. In the AbRE variant, the *bvGS* and *srrA* genes exhibited brief heterogeneity in samples E1 and E2 respectively (**Table 6.2.**). This state was short-lived and was not observed in the subsequent samples, E2 and E3.

Table 6.2

Heterogeneous Mutations Occurring in AbRE Target Genes

Sample	E1	E2	E3	E3x	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10	
Conc.	2	4	8	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	
Gene	bvgS [H]	M	M	M	n/a	n/a	M	n/a	n/a	M	n/a	M
		het	hom	hom	n/a	n/a	hom	n/a	n/a	hom	n/a	hom
Gene	srrA [H]	WT	WT	M	M	n/a	n/a	n/a	M	M	M	M
		hom	het	hom	hom	n/a	n/a	n/a	hom	hom	hom	hom

Het – heterozygous **M** – Mutant **conc.** – concentration

Hom – homozygous **WT** – Wild type

The same observation was made in the AbRM variant, where *mexB* and *epsL* exhibited temporal heterogeneity (**Table 6.3**). In *mexB*, the state was observed in sample M5, whereas samples M4 and M6 were purely wild type and mutant respectively. It is worth noting that in sample M5, the abundance of wild type alleles outnumber that of the mutant allele, which is why it is categorized as wild type. On the other hand, the *epsL* gene displayed a longer heterogeneous state lasting from samples M1 to M2.

Table 6.3

Heterogeneous Mutations Occurring in AbrM Target Genes

Sample	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M8x	M9	
Conc.	0.125	0.25	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	16.0	16.0	32.0	
Gene	mexB	WT	n/a	n/a	WT	WT	M	M	M	M	M
		hom	n/a	n/a	hom	het	hom	hom	hom	hom	hom
Gene	epsL	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M
		het	het	hom	hom	hom	hom	hom	hom	hom	hom
Gene	ahpF	M	n/a	n/a	M	n/a	n/a	M	M	M	M
		het	n/a	n/a	het	n/a	n/a	het	het	het	het

Het – heterozygous **M** – Mutant **conc.** – concentration

Hom – homozygous **WT** – Wild type **n/a** – no data

In comparison to the short-lived heterogeneity in the previous samples, *ahpF* exhibited an inherent state of bistability lasting from sample M1 through M9, as shown in shown in **Table 6.3**. When screened, the amplicons revealed several heterogeneous alleles present within the *ahpF* gene (**Figure 6.11**). The heterogeneous sites in the AbRM samples were identified, and the dominant alleles are listed in **Table 6.4**.

Table 6.4
*The List of Most Abundant Allele Present in the Heterogeneous Regions in Amplicons
 Generated via AbY32b1 Primer Combination*

Sample / position	Dominant allele								
	73	151	223	226	328	335	436	496	556
Ab00	T	C	T	A	C	C	G	G	C
M1	C	T	G	T	T	T	A	A	T
M4	T	C	T	A	T	C	A	A	C
M7	C	C	G	A	C	C	G	A	C
M8	T	C	T	A	C	C	G	A	C
M8x	T	C	T	A	C	C	G	A	C
M9	C	C	T	A	C	C	G	A	C
Mutation type	TS	TS	TV	TV	TS	TS	TS	TS	TS

*TS = Transition

*TV = Transversion

The allele abundance in each mutation site shifts inconsistently between samples. For example, as shown in **Figure 6.11 (a)**, in position 422, 430 and 454, the peaks indicate a higher abundance of adenosine, guanine, and cytosine, respectively. In the following sample (**Figure 6.11 (b)**), the abundance of the previously dominant allele has dropped, and this state persists throughout the remaining samples. However, due to this lowered abundance, the dominant allele at position 432 in sample M1 (**Figure 6.11 (b)**) has shifted from guanine to adenosine. Even so, it should be noted that the relative abundance of guanine and adenosine at the position is approximately 50/50. Moreover, the abundance of the recessive alleles in each of the three listed positions did not undergo any significant changes between the samples. In addition, the same state was observed in the susceptible parent strain as well, which adds difficulty to the task of identifying the wild type from the mutant allele.

Figure 6.11: Inherent Heterogeneity in the *ahpF* Gene of the AbRM Variant

The temporal heterogeneity in the AbRE and AbRM samples are likely attributed to the mutation selection window of the respective resistance strains. During which, the strain carrying the mutant allele is being “selected”, while the wild type strain is effectively dying out. From the resistance tracking previously shown in **Table 6.2** and **Table 6.3**, the mutation selection window for strains AbRE and AbRM generally lasts a single day, with the exception of *epsL*, lasting two days (M1 and M2). The brief selection window highlights the efficiency of *A. baumannii* in acquiring resistance, requiring a short time to “switch” from a completely wild type bacterial community to a completely resistant mutant community. This is of course in addition to the relatively rapid mutation event mentioned under the “Identification of mutation time point” subchapter, along with rapid resistance acquisition discussed in the previous chapter.

Under normal circumstances, it stands to reason that the wild type allele would overtime reduce in abundance and eventually be replaced by the mutant allele. However, this is not observed in any of the identified *ahpF* mutation sites. Several factors have been considered in explaining the inherent heterogeneity in this gene; i) The wild type allele remains unaffected by the introduction of selective pressure, while the mutant allele reduces in abundance or, ii) the mutant allele remains unaffected, while the wild type allele is reduced. However, both of these theories suggest the emergence of an initially non-intrinsic mutant allele upon introduction to an antimicrobial. Since the second allele(s) is prevalent even in the susceptible parent strain, this makes it unlikely. It was also considered that there is a presence of a duplicate *ahpF* gene within the Ab00 genome, resulting in heterogeneous amplicons. However, if so, the abundance of the alleles would not have shifted at all throughout the resistance induction due to the non-dynamic nature of genes in general. As such, it is hypothesized that Ab00 may in fact be a complex of at least two *A. baumannii* substrains carrying differing *ahpF* genes, which are constantly maintained even without selective pressure (Barin et al., 2013). The abundance of either one of the substrains would then be affected when exposed to the meropenem, but not enough to completely remove either of the strains.

6.3.3 Stability in Absence of Selective Pressure

Table 6.6 shows the retention of primary and secondary antimicrobial resistance after five days of daily passage in MHB devoid of antimicrobials. As a reference, **Table 6.5**, extracted from the previous resistance screening is included as a comparison.

Table 6.5

Summary of the Antimicrobial Resistance Prior to the Stability Test

Disc	(µg)	Ab00	AbRC		AbRE		AbRM		AbRI	
		n/a	[2]	[64]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]
GEM	10	S	S	S	R	R	S	S	R	R
ERY	15	S	I	S	R	R	I	R	R	R
CIP	10	U	R	R	U	R	U	U	U	R
IMI	10	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R
MEM	10	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R

R; Resistant, I; Intermediate, S; Susceptible, U; Unconfirmed

Table 6.6

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Ab00 Variants After Five Days of Daily Passaging at 37°C

Disc	(µg)	AbRC		AbRE		AbRM		AbRI											
		[2]	[64]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter(cm) and interpretation																			
GEM	10	2.4	S	2	S	2.1	S	1.5	R	0.9	R	2.4	S	3	S	1.4	R	1.5	R
ERY	15	1.9	S	2.2	S	2.2	S	0	R	0	R	1.6	I	0.9	R	1	R	1.8	S
CIP	10	0.9	R	0	R	0	R	2.7	S	2.2	S	2.6	S	2.9	S	2.6	S	3	S
IMI	10	3.3	S	2.8	S	3.6	S	3.6	S	3.2	S	3.2	S	4	S	2.4	S	2.4	S
MEM	10	2.2	S	3	S	3	S	2.4	S	1.7	S	0.9	R	1.9	S	1.6	I	1.8	I

R; Resistant, I; Intermediate, S; Susceptible, U; Unconfirmed

AbRC shows retention of primary resistance against ciprofloxacin in both low and high level resistant variants. The same is for AbRE, which show a complete lack of ZOI in both low and high level resistant variants as well. Moreover, its secondary resistance towards gentamycin is also preserved. Variant AbRM on the other hand shows a change in resistance towards meropenem, where a larger ZOI is observed in both isolates cultured in 16 µg/ml and 32 µg/ml of the drug. The former however still retains its resistance as the ZOI is still within range, unlike the latter. No significant change in its secondary resistance is observed. Variant AbRI shows the most substantial change in its resistance profile, whereby its primary resistance towards imipenem has been lost. The sub-MIC variant grown in 4 µg/ml imipenem however has retained its resistance towards erythromycin, unlike the variant cultured in 8 µg/ml imipenem. Similarly with the AbRE variant, AbRI has managed to retain its resistance towards gentamycin.

6.3.4 Stability Under Prolonged Storage

i) Stability in storage at 4°C

Table 6.7

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Isogenic Variants After a 5-day Storage with Antimicrobials in 4°C. Inoculums were Taken from Cultures Without Drugs

Disc	(µg)	AbRC		AbRE		AbRM		AbRI											
		[2]	[64]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter(cm) and interpretation																			
GEM	10	2.4	S	1.4	R	1.5	R	1.2	R	1.2	R	2.4	S	2.8	S	3	S	1.5	R
ERY	15	1.8	S	1.8	S	1.8	S	0	R	0	R	1.6	I	1.8	S	1.8	S	1.4	R
CIP	10	1	R	0	R	0	R	2.4	S	2.1	R	2.8	S	1.8	R	3	S	2.4	S
IMI	10	3.8	S	3.4	S	3.5	S	3.6	S	3.4	S	3.2	S	3.8	S	4	S	0	R
MEM	10	2.4	S	3	S	2.8	S	3	S	2.6	S	0	R	1.2	R	1.2	R	0	R

Table 6.8

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Isogenic Variants After a 5-day Storage Without Antimicrobials in 4°C. Inoculums were Taken from Cultures Without Drugs

Disc	(µg)	AbRC		AbRE		AbRM		AbRI											
		[2]	[64]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter(cm) and interpretation																			
GEM	10	2.2	S	1.6	R	1.8	S	1.2	R	1.2	R	2.3	S	2.8	S	1.4	R	1.4	R
ERY	15	1.8	S	2	S	2	S	0	R	0	R	1.7	I	2.1	S	1.4	R	1.4	R
CIP	10	1	R	0	R	0	R	2.4	S	2	R	2.8	S	3	S	2.8	S	2.4	S
IMI	10	3.6	S	3.4	S	3.6	S	3.4	S	3.5	S	3.3	S	4	S	1.8	S	1	R
MEM	10	2.2	S	3	S	3	S	2.6	S	2.3	S	0	R	0	R	0	R	0	R

Table 6.9

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Isogenic Variants After a 5-day Storage in 4°C. Inoculums were Taken from Cultures with Drugs

Disc	(µg)	AbRC		AbRE		AbRM		AbRI											
		[2]	[64]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter(cm) and interpretation																			
GEM	10	1.9	S	1.5	R	1.6	R	1.3	R	1.3	R	1.3	R	2.6	S	1.6	R	1.4	R
ERY	15	1.4	R	2	S	1.8	S	0	R	0	R	1.4	R	1.2	R	2	S	2.3	S
CIP	10	1.1	R	0	R	0	R	2.6	S	2.3	S	1.2	R	2.4	S	2.5	S	2.8	S
IMI	10	3.4	S	3.8	S	3.6	S	3.8	S	3.5	S	3.2	S	3.2	S	1.6	R	1.5	R
MEM	10	2.2	S	3	S	2.9	S	3	S	2.2	S	0	R	0	R	1.2	R	0	R

ii) Stability in storage at -80°C

Table 6.10

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Isogenic Variants after a 5-day Storage With Antimicrobials in -80°C. Inoculum was Taken from Cultures Without Drugs

Disc	(µg)	AbRC				AbRE				AbRM				AbRI					
		[2]	[64]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter(cm) and interpretation																			
GEM	10	2	S	1.4	R	1.6	R	1.4	R	1.4	R	2.2	S	2.6	S	1.4	R	1.2	R
ERY	15	1.8	S	1.8	S	2	S	0	R	0	R	1.2	R	1.4	R	1.7	I	1.8	S
CIP	10	1	R	0	R	0	R	2.8	S	2.4	S	2.8	S	2.7	S	2.4	S	2.4	S
IMI	10	3.8	S	3.9	S	3.9	S	3.7	S	3.5	S	3.2	S	3.8	S	2	S	1.4	R
MEM	10	2.2	S	2.8	S	3.1	S	3	S	2.2	S	0	R	0	R	0	R	0	R

Table 6.11

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Isogenic Variants after a 5-day Storage Without Antimicrobials in -80°C. Inoculum was Taken from Cultures without Drugs

Disc	(µg)	AbRC				AbRE				AbRM				AbRI					
		[2]	[64]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter(cm) and interpretation																			
GEM	10	2	S	2.6	S	2.8	S	1.4	R	1.4	R	2.2	S	2.7	S	1.3	R	1.2	R
ERY	15	1.8	S	1.8	S	1.8	S	0	R	0	R	1.8	S	2.5	S	1.4	R	1.6	I
CIP	10	1	R	0	R	0	R	2.6	S	2.2	S	1.6	R	2.8	S	2.2	S	2.2	S
IMI	10	3.2	S	3.6	S	3.6	S	3.4	S	3.2	S	3.2	S	3.2	S	1.6	R	1.5	R
MEM	10	2	I	2.8	S	2.8	S	1.9	I	2	I	0	R	0	R	1	R	0	R

Table 6.12

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Isogenic Variants after a 5-day Storage Without Antimicrobials in -80°C. Inoculum was Taken from Cultures with Drugs

Disc	(µg)	CIP				ERY				MEM				IMI					
		[2]	[64]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[4]	[8]									
Diameter (interpretation)																			
GEM	10	2	S	2.6	S	1.7	U	1.2	R	1.2	R	2	S	2	S	1.3	R	1.3	R
ERY	15	1.8	S	1.8	S	1.8	S	0	R	0	R	1.2	R	1.2	R	1.2	R	1.2	R
CIP	10	1.2	R	0	R	0	R	2.6	S	2.2	S	2.2	S	2.6	S	2.2	S	2.4	S
IMI	10	3.5	S	3.6	S	3.6	S	3.6	S	3.2	S	2.5	S	3.2	S	1.6	R	0	R
MEM	10	2.2	S	3	S	2.9	S	3	S	2.3	S	0	R	0	R	0	R	0	R

Table 6.13

Disc Diffusion Test Results of Isogenic Variants after Nine Months of Storage in -80°C. All Samples were Taken from the St-80+ Batch, Except ERY [1024] which was Taken from the St-80b Batch

Disc	(µg)	CIP		ERY		MEM		IMI							
		[2]	[128]	[8]	[1024]	[16]	[32]	[8]							
Diameter(cm) and interpretation															
GEM	10	2.4	S	1.8	S	1.8	S	2	S	2.4	S	2.4	S	1.2	R
ERY	15	1.8	S	2	S	0	R	0	R	1.4	R	1.4	R	1.2	R
CIP	10	1	R	0	R	3	S	2	R	3	S	2.8	S	2.8	S
IMI	10	3	S	3.8	S	4	S	3.4	S	3	S	3.2	S	1.2	R
MEM	10	2.4	S	2.8	S	3	S	2.4	S	0	R	0	R	0	R

From the tables, ciprofloxacin-challenged variants, AbRC is observed to have retained primary resistance towards ciprofloxacin in all conditions. The same is observed in the AbRE variants, where erythromycin resistance is retained across the board. The meropenem-challenged variants on the other hand have been observed to retain its primary resistance under all conditions, except after incubation in absence of selective pressure. Variant AbRI exhibited stable primary resistance in all samples stored/exposed to its MIC (8 µg/ml). Loss of primary resistance is observed in two instances; storage at -80°C with imipenem (**St-80+**), and storage at -4°C without imipenem (**St4-**). Loss of secondary resistance was also observed in the AbRI variant. The daily passage in absence of antimicrobials resulted in a loss of resistance against ciprofloxacin in the AbRI variant cultured in 8 µg/ml imipenem. The 4 µg/ml variant on the other hand exhibited a significantly larger ZOI (2.6 cm in diameter). Erythromycin resistance in AbRI was retained in the 4 µg/ml culture, but was lost in the 8 µg/ml culture. In the resistance retention under 4°C storage (**St4-**, **St4+**, and **St4b**), the 4 µg/ml AbRI variant appears to have a higher likelihood of losing its primary and/or secondary resistance. Although the 8 µg/ml AbRI culture also appears to exhibit loss of resistance, it is mostly observed to be its secondary resistance towards ciprofloxacin and erythromycin (**St-80+**, **St-80-**, and **St-80b**).

Table 6.14

Overview of the Loss of Antimicrobial Resistance in the IMI-Challenged Samples after Five Days of Storage

a) AbRC

Drug	Batch (µg/ml)	Absence		St4+		St4-		St4b		St-80+		St-80-		St-80b		St-80x		resistance retained (%)	
		2	128	2	128	2	128	2	128	2	128	2	128	2	128	2	128		
Drug	GM	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4(28.6)
	ERY	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(7.7)
	CIP	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	14(100)
	IMI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0 (0)
	MEM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	I	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(7.1)

b) AbRE

Drug	Batch (µg/ml)	Absence		St4+		St4-		St4b		St-80+		St-80-		St-80b		St-80x		resistance retained (%)	
		8	1024	8	1024	8	1024	8	1024	8	1024	8	1024	8	1024	8	1024		
Drug	GM	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12(100)	
	ERY	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12(100)	
	CIP	U	U	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	Excluded	
	IMI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0 (0)
	MEM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	I	I	-	-	-	-	-	10(83)

c) AbRM

Drug	Batch [MEM]	Absence		St4+		St4-		St4b		St-80+		St-80-		St-80b		St-80x		resistance retained (%)	
		16	32	16	32	16	32	16	32	16	32	16	32	16	32	16	32		
Drug	GM	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(7.14)	
	ERY	I	+	I	-	I	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	10(71.4)	
	CIP	U	U	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	Excluded	
	IMI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0 (0)
	MEM	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	13(92.9)

d) AbRI

Disc	Batch [IMI]	Absence		St4+		St4-		St4b		St-80+		St-80-		St-80b		St-80x		resistance retained (%)
		4	8	4	8	4	8	4	8	4	8	4	8	4	8	4	8	
Disc	GM	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	/	+	11(78.6)
	ERY	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	/	+	8(57.1)
	CIP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	0(0)
	IMI	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	/	+	9(64.3)
	MEM	-	I	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	/	+	12(85.7)

GM - Gentamycin
 ERY - Erythromycin
 CIP - Ciprofloxacin
 IMI - Imipenem
 MEM - Meropenem

+, resistance retained after storage/incubation
 -, resistance lost after storage/incubation

Absence; Samples passaged daily for five days without drugs, **St4+**; Samples stored in 4°C with drugs, **St4-**; Samples stored in 4°C without drugs, **St4b**; Samples grown from MHB+drugs, stored in 4°C without drugs, **St-80+**; Samples stored in -80°C with drugs, **St-80-**; Samples stored in -80°C without drugs, **St-80b**; Samples grown from MHB+drugs, stored in -80°C without drugs, **St-80x**; Samples stored in -80°C with drugs for nine months.

As shown in **Table 6.14**, variants AbRC and AbRE have retained their resistance against ciprofloxacin and erythromycin respectively in all conditions. In addition, AbRE has also retained its resistance towards gentamycin as well. In contrast, the high level meropenem resistant sample, AbRM (32 µg/ml) shows a loss of resistance when cultured in absence of the target drug. The same is observed when stored in 4°C with selective pressure present (**St4+**), although the detriment is less severe. A complete loss of imipenem resistance was also observed in the AbRM isolates under all conditions. Lastly, isogenic variant AbRI shows inconsistent resistance retention for its target drugs; imipenem (64.3%) and meropenem (85.7%). Its imipenem resistance is reverted when cultured in absence of selective pressure as well as in several storage conditions; **St4+** (4 µg/ml), **St4-** (4 µg/ml), and **St-80+** (4 µg/ml).

The retention of primary resistance in AbRC and AbRE suggests that the modifications underwent by both variants are intrinsic and/or irreversible. Based on the mutation analysis reported in the previous chapter, it is possible that the SNP identified in the *gyrA* gene has conferred a permanent ciprofloxacin resistance in AbRC. The same could be said for the mutations identified in the AbRE isogenic variant. Whether or not this is a combinatorial effect of both the early and late onset mutation is yet to be confirmed. However, the low-level resistance variant (8 µg/ml meropenem) also shows identically stable resistance retention despite lacking the late onset mutations present in *ftsI* and the RNase I genes (**Figure 6.4**). This in turn suggests that the late onset mutations are not crucial for maintaining a stable low resistance, but plays a role in high level resistance maintenance exclusively (Alonso et al., 1999).

The isogenic variant AbRM (32 µg/ml) exhibited failure to retain resistance when cultured in absence of meropenem (**Table 6.14**). The profile suggests that maintenance of meropenem resistance that is several folds beyond the MIC is either difficult to retain, or is not worth maintaining at the cost of its fitness (Ternent et al., 2015). The same deduction can be made for the AbRI variant, whereby a loss of resistance is observed when cultured in absence of the selective pressure. Furthermore, the ciprofloxacin resistance acquired by AbRI was no longer observed following the stability tests. This is most noticeable as there was a complete lack of ZOI in the ciprofloxacin disc during the initial resistance screening shown in the previous chapter. The observation implies that

the secondary resistance towards ciprofloxacin was likely a gene expression that was not inherited by the AbRI daughter cells during the storage and passaging in absence of selective pressure (Adam et al., 2008). It can also be deduced that this secondary resistance mechanism is unique to that of the other drug classes tested (Hooper, 2001).

The loss of primary resistance in several of the AbRI isolates (**S4+**, **St4-** and **St-80+**) indicates that sub-MIC cultures (4 µg/ml imipenem) are less capable of retaining resistance as effectively as the cultures growing at MIC (8 µg/ml imipenem). This is made apparent in **Table 6.7**, where the most substantial reduction in imipenem resistance in AbRI (4 µg/ml) is observed, resulting in a 4.0 cm diameter in its imipenem ZOI. Imipenem resistance is therefore only stable when at least tolerance at its MIC (8 µg/ml imipenem) has been achieved. Additionally, this instability is also indicative of an ineffective mutation in the *mexB* and *epsL* genes, since these variations occur several folds below the 4 µg/ml imipenem tolerance was achieved. Then again, the inefficiency is likely due to the reduced metabolic activity; a common phenotypic resistance mechanism against carbapenems (Wiuiff et al., 2005). Hence, it is deducible that the side effects of a phenotypic tolerance mechanism can outstrip the advantages of beneficial mutations.

6.4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, mutation events in the susceptible *A. baumannii* isolate vary when exposed to different antimicrobials. Heterogeneity during the induction period was observed to be short-lived, lasting between only one to two days, signifying a brief selection window for all of the tested antimicrobials. Mutations involving non-specific resistance mechanisms as observed in the macrolide- and carbapenem-resistant isogenic variants tend to occur early during the resistance induction period, while a specific resistance mechanism as observed in the ciprofloxacin-resistant variant tend to occur late into the induction period. Late onset mutations have also been observed to have no visible effect on the antimicrobial resistance stability when compared to the early onset mutations. Regardless, the antimicrobial resistance acquired in each isogenic variant was confirmed to be stable.

CHAPTER SEVEN

COMPARATIVE GENOMICS ANALYSIS OF *Acinetobacter baumannii in vitro* MUTANT STRAINS AND 24 CLINICAL ISOLATES

7.1 INTRODUCTION

The strength of whole-genome sequencing is that it grants an overview of the entire genetic makeup of a pathogen, allowing for the study of genes that might otherwise be missed. Moreover, through the use of several whole-genome comparison tools, it is now possible to screen for any and all variations that exist between two organisms of the same species. This is especially useful in determining the presence of genomic variations between a parent strain and its isogenic variants (Yap et al., 2014).

When comparing such variants, its growth conditions throughout resistance selection are just as crucial as the antimicrobial selective pressure. In an *in vitro* setting, these conditions are easily manipulated, ensuring a constant and known set of factors which influence the mutations. In an *in vivo* setting however, the host factor can be a great force in driving different mutations to occur (Engering et al., 2013). This is due to the presence of host-derived molecules (e.g. structural proteins, enzymes and antibodies) that trigger responses that would be essentially nonexistent in an *in vitro* setting (McGrath et al., 2013; Papaix et al., 2014). That being said, it is understandable that mutations in these two settings may occur in different, specific regions in a gene or genome. Fluoroquinolone resistance for example, has been reported to incite mutations in the Quinolone Resistance Determinant Region (QRDR) *in vivo*, but this region remains unaffected *in vitro* (Chopra & Galande, 2011).

The applications on multiple whole-genome comparison also extend beyond mutation screening. Over the years, several software and algorithms have been developed to allow more in depth analysis of whole-genome data. The Center for Genomic Epidemiology for instance has developed a single website ([www.http://genomicepidemiology.org/](http://genomicepidemiology.org/)) that caters to several of these analysis needs. Now,

whole-genome data can be used to perform Multi Locus Sequence Typing (MLST), predict acquired resistance genes and predict pathogenicity towards human hosts, and clonality analysis via phylogenomics or phylogenetics approaches. Specifically, in terms of whole genome MLST (wgMLST) analysis, once the whole-genome data is at hand, the pathogen's typing can be performed without the need for further molecular work, as the full battery of genetic information is already at hand (Maiden et al., 2014; Kwong et al., 2015).

Although several studies have been carried out to identify the key differences between *in vitro* and *in vivo* mutations, clinical pathogens have continuously proven to be more versatile than expected. *A. baumannii* is no exception to this rule. Its mutational prowess has been attributed to several factors from shutting down of mutation repair mechanisms to overexpression of specific genes (Nordmann & Poirel, 2008). In this chapter, the aims were; i) to sequence the genome of 25 local, clinical *A. baumannii* isolates, ii) to annotate the gene functions and genome layout using the data from whole-genome sequencing, iii) to compare the 25 annotated genomes and identify patterns of resistance or virulence profiles, and iv) to compare the mutations in the *in vitro* resistant variants with the clinically resistant isolates.

7.2 METHODS

Figure 7.1: Overview of Methodology

7.2.1 Revival of Stored Isolates

The *A. baumannii* sample(s) stored in -80°C (and in 30% glycerol) was slowly adjusted to room temperature by incubating at -20°C (1 hour), 4°C (1 hour) and room temperature (1 hour). A loopful of the stock culture was then transferred into a clean, sterile Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB) and incubated overnight at 37°C in a shaking incubator.

7.2.2 Confirmation of Purity

The purity of the revived culture was tested via dilution streaking on Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA). Colony formation was observed, and Gram staining was performed to confirm a uniform morphology.

7.2.3 Sample Prep for Sequencing

DNA extraction and purification was performed on overnight cultures using a commercial DNA purification kit (PROMEGA, Wisconsin, USA). The DNA was then fragmented via sonication using the sonicator (Sonoswiss SW12H, Ramsen, Switzerland) at 38 kHz for 6 minutes, with the 'boost' setting on. A gel electrophoresis was then carried out on the fragmented DNA. DNA fragments of 500-600 bp (smear) on the gel was cut out and purified using the gel clean-up kit (PROMEGA, Wisconsin, USA). Using the kits and instructions provided by Illumina (California, USA), the sample was then subjected to end-repair, A-tailing, adapter ligation, and amplification via PCR. A quality check of the sample was performed via Qubit Fluorometer (Life Technologies Corporation, New York, USA) and Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, USA) to ensure the amount of DNA available is sufficient for the following procedures.

7.2.4 Cluster Generation via Cluster Station

The cluster generation of the sample was performed based on the TruSeq Cluster Generation Reagent Preparation Guide (Illumina, California, USA). PhiX was used as the control, as directed in the instructions.

7.2.5 Genome Sequencing via Illumina GA IIx

The genome sequencing was performed following the Standard Operation Protocol developed in-house at the Integrative Pharmacogenomics Institute (iPROMISE), as well as the general procedure provided by Illumina (California, USA).

7.2.6 Quality Checkf of Sequencing Output

The quality of the sequencing output was analyzed using the FastQC (Andrews, 2012). Reads with Phred scores below 20 were trimmed using Dynamic Trim under default settings (Cox et al., 2010).

7.2.7 *De novo* Assembly

The sequencing reads were assembled using Velvet Optimiser. The kmer range was set between minimum (19) and maximum (99) possible values. Upon completion, the assembly outputs were screened for quality. Samples that produce greater than 1000 contigs were reassembled using SOAPdenovo with the scaffolding parameter on. The same kmer range was individually run, and the output using the optimal kmer was selected.

7.2.8 Ordering and Orienting of *de novo* Assembled Contigs

The output of the assemblies (contigs.fa for VelvetOptimiser and *.scafseq for SOAPdenovo) were used as an input for ordering and orienting via Optical Syntenic Layout (OSLay) software. The *.coords file necessary for the syntenic layout was generated using “-coords” option in NUCMER. Four *A. baumannii* reference strains available during the time of analysis (ACICU, ATCC 7978, AYE and SDF) were downloaded from the NCBI database, and were used as the reference to generate the *.coords file as well as for the syntenic layout. The OSLay synteny outputs were validated using MAUVE with the same references.

7.2.9 Reference Assembly

Samples that were unsuccessfully ordered via OSLay were instead assembled by reference using BWA. The *.sam output of the reference assembly were then fed to UGENE. Once completely loaded, the consensus sequence was exported, and the gaps were replaced with ambiguous nucleotides using a text editor. The synteny of the

assembled sequences was analyzed using the dotplot generator in UGENE. The same four references were used.

7.2.10 Annotation

The results of the *de novo* assembly were submitted to automated annotation websites; RAST and BASys. Prior to the submission, the assembled contigs were first stitched together into a single pseudomolecule by adding 150 ambiguous nucleotides (N's) between each contig (Munoz et al., 2010; Roodt et al., 2012; Cai et al., 2011). The contigs were merged using the export function in the UGENE software.

7.2.11 Analysis of Annotations

The BASys results were scrutinized in terms of number of coding regions, Blast results, and structural analysis output. The “summary stats” of each of the genome annotations were screened for amino acid composition, protein location, and protein function. Potential virulence and resistance genes were manually screened in the annotation table, and the gene positions were viewed via the map viewer generated by BASys. The RAST results were analyzed in terms of number of features, as well as the Blast results and their subsystem categorization. The subsystems were used to narrow down potential virulence and resistance genes. All of the relevant files were downloaded and stored locally as backup.

7.2.12 Multiple Genome Alignment of BASys and RAST Annotations

Once the annotation process for all 25 *A. baumannii* genomes were completed in both BASys and RAST servers, the genbank (*.gbk) files from both services were downloaded. Using the MAUVE multiple genome aligner, the 50 genbank files were aligned together in order to compare i) the BASys and RAST annotations in each genome and, ii) The BASys and RAST annotations between the 25 genomes. This allows categorization of BASys-annotated functions according to RAST specifications. Suggested genes responsible for macrolide and beta-lactam resistances were scrutinized and compared in each genome. Fluoroquinolone resistance determinants were excluded from the search as the suggested elements were all housekeeping genes typically found in bacteria.

7.2.13 wgMLST Analysis

The 25 *A. baumannii* whole-genomes were individually submitted to the online webtool provided by the Center for Genomic Epidemiology for MLST analysis (Larsen et al., 2012). The output of which was downloaded and stored locally, as the files are only temporary stored online. In order to generate the necessary sequences phylogenetic analysis, the gene sequences for each loci defined by the Oxford MLST scheme were first extracted from the BASys annotations. The gene sequences were then concatenated into a single sequence file using UGENE. The same process was repeated for the Pasteur MLST scheme. The dendrogram were generated using UGENE via the MrBayes method.

7.2.14 Submission of Genome Data to NCBI

The reads were submitted to the Short Read Archive (SRA) in the NCBI database under the submission ID SUB742814. The list of accession numbers for the submissions is as shown in **Appendix C**.

7.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

7.3.1 Sequencing Data Output

The sequencing data of the samples were converted from the basecall format (*.bcl) to the fastq format (*.fastq) using the CASAVA software and following the user manual. The quality of the fastq (*.Fastq) output of the sequencing run was checked using FastQC (**Table 7.1**).

Table 7.1

FastQC DNA Sequencing Output Summary of the 25 A. baumannii Strains

Sample	Read	Total sequences	%GC	Coverage	Sample	Read	Total sequences	%GC	Coverage
Ab00	1	3912000	41	100.4	H.Ab14	1	5574980	39	143.0
	2		42			40			
H.Ab1	1	5556684	38	142.5	H.Ab15	1	3451742	39	88.5
	2		39			39			
H.Ab2	1	3983786	38	102.2	H.Ab16	1	5605768	39	88.5
	2		39			40			
H.Ab3	1	3117664	38	80.0	H.Ab17	1	6086224	39	156.1
	2		39			40			
H.Ab4	1	3462106	39	88.8	H.Ab18	1	6343992	39	162.7
	2		40			40			
H.Ab5	1	1507612	39	38.7	H.Ab19	1	3790986	39	97.2

		2		40			2		39
H.Ab6	1	26351340	38	676.0	H.Ab20	1	7775170	39	199.5
	2		39			2		40	
H.Ab7	1	4064542	39	104.3	H.Ab21	1	4728220	40	121.3
	2		39			2		40	
H.Ab8	1	1699020	39	43.6	H.Ab22	1	10218566	39	262.1
	2		40			2		40	
H.Ab9	1	1324422	37	34.0	H.Ab23	1	5194082	39	133.2
	2		38			2		40	
H.Ab10	1	3098270	38	79.5	H.Ab24	1	10588824	39	271.6
	2		39			2		40	
H.Ab11	1	2800460	38	71.8	H.Ab25	1	12370206	39	317.3
	2		39			2		40	
H.Ab13	1	4298682	38	110.3					
	2		39						

From the sequencing output summarized in **Table 7.1**, the coverage of all the samples was noted to be above the recommended value (Sims et al., 2014).

7.3.2 Quality of Sequencing Data

The trimming results of the 25 *A. baumannii* isolates are as shown in **Figure 7.2**. Overall, the sequencing quality was observed to be above the green zone (Phred score 28), indicating quality data. As such, little to no error rate should be expected for the sequencing reads from all 25 samples. In all of the samples, the quality of the reads was observed to drop steadily in relation to the length of the reads. This is common as the reagents used during the sequencing with the GAIIX drops in quality as the run proceeds. Regardless, this is of no issue as the data is still within the desired quality. In the few samples that were observed to reach a quality below the green zone (data not shown), the reads were trimmed using the DynamicTrim perl script (Cox et al., 2010). The script parameters were set to default and the output of the trimming was used for the assembly processes.

Ab00

H.Ab1

H.Ab2

H.Ab3

H.Ab4

H.Ab5

H.Ab6

H.Ab7

H.Ab8

H.Ab9

H.Ab10

H.Ab11

H.Ab13

H.Ab14

H.Ab15

H.Ab16

H.Ab17

H.Ab18

H.Ab19

H.Ab20

H.Ab21

H.Ab22

H.Ab23

H.Ab24

Figure 7.2: Trimmed Reads of the 25 *A. baumannii* Samples

7.3.3 *De novo* Assembly of the Trimmed Reads via VelvetOptimiser

Once the *de novo* assembly of all 25 samples has been completed, the output was summarized as shown in **Table 7.2**. Sample Ab3 has the highest number of contigs, and lowest N50. At the time of the analysis, this was predicted to result in poor annotation quality. Extra scrutiny was taken in the ensuing analysis (ordering/orienting and annotation). The optimal kmer is highest in H.Ab25, and lowest in H.Ab8. N50 on the other hand is highest in samples H.Ab4, H.Ab14, H.Ab17, H.Ab20, and H.AB24. The percent reads used was noted to be higher in AB8. However, despite having a low optimal kmer, this sample is most optimal in terms of read utilization. The lowest percent reads used was observed in H.Ab6. This is despite H.Ab6 having the highest number of total reads among the 25 samples. However, the 66.15% reads used still far exceeds the number of reads used in the other samples. Once assembly has been completed, the output was used in the following ordering and orienting processes.

Table 7.2

Overview of the *de novo* Assembly Output Generated via VelvetOptimiser v2.20

Sample	VelvetOpt v2.2.0		N50	Total reads	Reads used	Reads used (%)
	optimal kmer	Contigs				
H.Ab1	53	460	23282	5556684	4268741	76.82
H.Ab2	51	729	12492	3983786	3006438	75.47
H.Ab3	45	7287	2054	3117664	2447964	78.52
H.Ab4	53	87	2708030	3462106	2458332	71.01
H.Ab5	45	988	7759	1507612	1183489	78.50
H.Ab6	61	351	33683	26351340	17430357	66.15
H.Ab7	51	575	15364	4064542	3012375	74.11
H.Ab8	27	689	23126	1699020	1492512	87.85
H.Ab9	29	982	10868	1324422	1161033	87.66
H.Ab10	51	618	16500	3098270	2279864	73.59
H.Ab11	51	733	10957	2800460	2094532	74.79
H.Ab13	51	492	18489	4298682	3290119	76.54
H.Ab14	59	77	2779644	5574980	4701113	84.33
H.Ab15	55	312	37761	3451742	3000617	86.93
H.Ab16	57	337	38002	5605768	4809767	85.80
H.Ab17	61	70	1475121	6086224	5019179	82.47
H.Ab18	59	443	40819	6343992	5358885	84.47
H.Ab19	59	432	34201	3790986	3161239	83.39
H.Ab20	61	85	2307824	7775170	6304741	81.09
H.Ab21	57	451	36356	4728220	3951543	83.57
H.Ab22	61	396	44073	10218566	8061767	78.89
H.Ab23	57	371	43186	5194082	4263021	82.07
H.Ab24	61	75	2155868	10588824	8373142	79.08
H.Ab25	65	634	44065	12370206	9486810	76.69

7.3.4 Ordering and Orienting of *de novo* Assembled Reads

Figure 7.3 shows the syntenic layout of the *A. baumannii* contigs using the aforementioned references. The optimal synteny for each of the samples is shown in Table 7.3. An overview of the dot plots generated showed that most of the syntenic layout was of acceptable quality, showing a visible linearity between the reference and query sequences. Samples H.Ab2, H.Ab5 and H.Ab9 showed the least displacement in the dot plots, exhibiting good linearity against all references. Samples H.Ab4, H.Ab14, H.Ab17 and H.Ab24 produced poor synteny, whereby no linearity was observed in any of the output. Samples H.Ab16, H.Ab18, H.Ab21 and H.Ab22 showed mostly linear synteny with the first three references and mismatches with SDF, exhibited by the white space on the upper region of the dot plot image. Samples H.Ab20, H.Ab23 and H.Ab25 showed good quality layout, with displacements against references ACICU and

ATCC17978, and mismatches against SDF. Overall, 12 out of the 25 isolates exhibited mismatches when compared with reference *A. baumannii* SDF, indicating that about half of the clinical isolates contain genetic information separate from this particular strain. Sample H.Ab3 on the other hand, when fed into OSLAy, was unable to generate a syntenic layout.

p) Ab17

q) Ab18

r) Ab19

s) H.Ab20

t) Ab21

u) Ab22

v) Ab23

w) H.Ab24

Figure 7.3: Compilation of the *A. baumannii* Syntenic Layout Using Strains ACICU, ATCC 17978, AYE and SDF as References

After screening the OSLay output, samples H.Ab3, H.Ab4, H.Ab14, H.Ab17 and H.Ab24 were first noted to have generated erroneous output. To rule out the possibility of contamination or chimeric sequences, the reads were selected at random and were blasted against the NCBI database. None of the samples indicated any signs of contamination or chimeric sequence. For further confirmation, to rule out contamination by typical contaminants *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, the synteny of the samples were tested against them. The resulting output was an error message by OSLay, indicating a complete dissimilarity with the theorized contaminants. These samples were set aside for further scrutiny. Oddly enough, most of these erroneous samples were noted to generate the highest N50 among the entire dataset. It is possible that these samples are new strains that have yet to be reported. However, it should also be noted that the structural dissimilarity between the *de novo* assembled genomes and the references is far too great to be considered a strain difference.

Table 7.3
Optimal Syntenic Layout Selected from the Synteny Screening Using Four Reference Sequences ATCC 17978, ACICU, AYE and SDF

Sample	Optimal synteny	Sample	Optimal synteny
Ab00	Ab_ATCC17978	H.Ab14	none
H.Ab1	ACICU/AYE (low)	H.Ab15	AYE
H.Ab2	ACICU/AYE	H.Ab16	ACICU/AYE
H.Ab3	OSLay failed	H.Ab17	none
H.Ab4	none	H.Ab18	ACICU
H.Ab5	ACICU	H.Ab19	ACICU/AYE
H.Ab6	ACICU/AYE	H.Ab20	AYE
H.Ab7	AYE	H.Ab21	AYE
H.Ab8	ACICU/AYE	H.Ab22	AYE
H.Ab9	ACICU/AYE	H.Ab23	AYE
H.Ab10	AYE	H.Ab24	none
H.Ab11	AYE	H.Ab25	AYE
H.Ab13	AYE		

Screening of the remaining samples revealed that they were all similar to either *A. baumannii* reference strains ACICU or AYE. Sample Ab00 however is most similar to the reference ATCC 17978, unlike the other samples.

Based on the lower quality in data processing for sample H.Ab3, it was deemed unsuitable for *de novo* assembly (and the consequent analysis). As such, it was decided that H.Ab3 be analyzed via reference-based assembly instead.

7.3.5 Analysis of Reference Assembly Synteny

Sample H.Ab3 was assembled with the Burrows-Wheeler Aligner (BWA) using the same four *A. baumannii* strains; ACICU, ATCC 17978, AYE and SDF as references. The output of the assembly (*.sam file) was then fed into UGENE, and the consensus was exported into a complete sequence. Each of the complete sequences was then compared with their respective references for optimal synteny using the UGENE dotplot plugin. The output of the dotplot generation is shown in **Figure 7.4**. The optimal synteny for H.Ab3 was determined when compared with the reference strain ACICU as it has the least number of visible gaps and “dispersed” alignments (as characterized by non-linear dots spread around the chart).

Figure 7.4: The Results of the Sample H.Ab3 Synteny Dotplot Generated via UGENE

7.3.6 Overview of Annotation Data

The ordered and oriented sequences from both *de novo* and reference assemblies were submitted to BASys and RAST for annotation. The output of both annotations was compiled in **Appendix B**. BASys produced a higher number of genes in comparison to RAST. This may be attributed by its tendency to categorize unknown genes as “putative genes” rather than excluding it from the annotation altogether. This is supported by the fact that the number of unknown protein functions (an average of 34% of total protein function) far exceeding the individual known functions. This may also lead to “fragmented” genes where a single determinant is segregated due to gaps in the assembly. Despite the evidently lower number of genes annotated in RAST, the trend is noticeably similar with BASys (**Figure 7.5**), showing little variation in the number of genes. The lack of large deviations in the gene number is likely due to the aforementioned “putative gene” annotations, leading to less than 4000 annotated genes per genome.

Figure 7.5: Overview of Annotation Results in BASys and RAST

7.3.7 Amino Acid Composition

From the BASys annotation report, the amino acid composition for all of the 25 samples were averaged and compiled into **Figure 7.6**. From the graph, leucine is shown to be the most abundant amino acid in all 25 strains, followed by alanine. With the exception of proline, the aliphatic amino acids (leucine, alanine, valine, isoleucine) appear to be more abundant than any other amino acids. This is likely due to their generally non-reactive and flexible nature, making it ideal for protein interior packing (Betts & Russel, 2003).

Figure 7.6: Average Amino Acid Composition in 25 *A. baumannii* Isolates

Conversely, cysteine is observed to be the least abundant, and tryptophan the second least. This is in contrast with recent findings stating that cysteine is among the amino acids that are present in higher abundance in host-associated environments, along with lysine, methionine and leucine (Moura et al., 2013). However, this may not necessarily signify a lower importance in said amino acid as its usage may be increased based on changes in gene expression at a given time (Das et al., 2005). Even so, the efficiency of the expression may be restricted by its limited abundance. The results are consistent with the theory that cysteine is largely underrepresented in all living

organisms. As its abundance has been theorized to be correlated with the complexity of an organism, it is therefore expected that the genome of a single-celled pathogen would be composed of a relatively smaller amount of cysteine (Miseta & Csutora, 2000). Despite this, it has been reported to commonly occur in protein functional sites, overruling any notion that abundance equates to functional significance (Marino & Gladyshev, 2010). The low standard deviation in each amino acid between the 25 strains indicates that there is little variation in the amino acid requirements across strains.

7.3.8 Protein Function

As with the amino acid composition report, each reported function generated by BASys was averaged among the strains, and then compiled into **Figure 7.7**. From the graph, it can be deduced that most of the proteins in the *A. baumannii* isolates are dedicated for inorganic ion transport and metabolism (R); 7.2% of the total protein functions. The second most prevalent proteins are devoted for transcription (K); 6.1%, and amino acid transport and metabolism (E); 6.0% of total protein functions. The least common function was identified to be for cell division and chromosome partitioning (D); 0.6%, followed by cell motility (N); 1.0% of total protein functions.

It should be noted that an average of 34% of the annotated proteins were categorized as “unknown” (data not shown), indicating that a relatively large portion of the entire proteome function is unclear due to database limitations. However, if the unknown 34% is considered to cover the 18 functions, then the significance of the “loss” of data is only approximately 2% per function.

Figure 7.7: Protein Function in the Sequenced 25 *A. baumannii* Isolates

7.3.9 Virulence and Resistance Determinants as Predicted by RAST

Following the analysis of the annotation summary, the RAST annotation report was scrutinized for both virulence and resistance determinants in each of the *A. baumannii* genome. Under the RAST Subsystem statistics report, the “Virulence, Disease and Defense” subsystem was selected and evaluated. RAST categorizes resistance determinants under the same subsystem (**Table 7.4**), and for the purpose of this analysis, the resistance features were separated from that categorization and compared side by side (**Figure 7.8**).

Table 7.4

Summary of the Features Categorized Under the “Virulence, disease and defense” Subsystem Identified in the 25 A. baumannii Genome

Sample	Virulence, Disease and Defense (Resistance features)	Sample	Virulence, Disease and Defense (Resistance features)
Ab00	84 (62)	H.Ab14	90 (66)
H.Ab1	82 (61)	H.Ab15	76 (56)
H.Ab2	77 (55)	H.Ab16	97 (72)
H.Ab3	74 (56)	H.Ab17	79 (56)
H.Ab4	75 (55)	H.Ab18	74 (56)
H.Ab5	70 (56)	H.Ab19	75 (57)
H.Ab6	103 (81)	H.Ab20	78 (56)
H.Ab7	82 (60)	H.Ab21	75 (57)
H.Ab8	101 (79)	H.Ab22	75 (57)
H.Ab9	84 (62)	H.Ab23	79 (57)
H.Ab10	85 (64)	H.Ab24	83 (60)
H.Ab11	96 (74)	H.Ab25	79 (57)
H.Ab13	103 (84)		

From **Figure 7.8**, the number of virulence determinants varies between isolates, ranging from 18 to 25 genes. The same is for the resistance determinants, although the number of genes far exceeds the aforementioned virulence features and ranges between 55 and 84 genes. When compared with the genome length, there is no correlation between the size of the genome and the number of the target determinants.

Several interesting features were identified within the 25 *A. baumannii* subsystems. The first is that RAST categorizes any and all DNA gyrase and Topoisomerase IV subunits under the “Resistance to fluoroquinolones” subsystem despite the fact that these proteins are commonly occurring housekeeping genes that do not inherently confer resistance to fluoroquinolones. However, it is possible that the RAST database targets “potential” fluoroquinolone resistances as well, since mutations

within the genes that express these proteins; *gyrA*, *gyrB*, *parC* and *parE*, are directly responsible for the acquisition of fluoroquinolone resistance.

Figure 7.8: An Overview of the Number of Virulence and Resistance Determinants, and Genome Length in the 25 *A. baumannii* Samples

In addition, several mycobacterium virulence operons were also identified within the “Virulence, disease and defense” subsystem for all the 25 samples (Table 7.5). BLAST results of these genes however returned non-mycobacterium hits, indicating a miscategorization. Regardless of this, the associated functions are still relevant. Also, in all 25 isolates, RAST consistently reports a set of seven to nine genes under the “Colicin V and bacteriocin production cluster” subsystem. Features in the subsystem include a gene responsible for encoding the colicin V production protein, a toxin that antagonizes the growth of other microbes. Evidently, each of the 25 *A. baumannii* genomes carries a single colicin V gene.

All 25 genomes essentially carry the same set of genes that were categorized under the aforementioned subsystem. A few variations were noted in samples H.Ab1,

H.Ab4 and H.Ab5 which only carry eight, eight, and seven of the features, respectively. The fewer number of determinants is due to a lack of *dedA* and “tRNA pseudouridine synthase A” gene duplicates listed under the “Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster” subsystem, unlike the other samples.

Additionally, samples H.Ab16 bears an extra three features under the “Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides” subcategory (a tier above the subsystem). These three genes are categorized under the “Tolerance to colicin E2” subsystem and include two Two-component response regulator genes; *creC* and *creB*, and a single gene encoding the inner membrane protein, CreD. RAST reports that the exact function of these genes have yet to be curated.

Table 7.5

Summarized List of Virulence and Resistance Determinants in the 25 *A. baumannii* Genome Retrieved from RAST

Sample	Number of Virulence determinants	Number of Resistance determinants
Ab00	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Genes
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3
		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
		Genes
		Copper homeostasis
		12
		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance
		13
		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases
		2
		Resistance to fluoroquinolones
		4
		Arsenic resistance
		4
		Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance
		2
		Beta-lactamase
		4
		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps
		18
		Resistance to chromium compounds
		3
H.Ab1	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Genes
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	8
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3
		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
		Genes
		Copper homeostasis
		6
		Bile hydrolysis
		2
		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance
		11
		Resistance to fluoroquinolones
		4
		Arsenic resistance
		6
		Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance
		2
		Beta-lactamase
		5
		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps
		22
		Resistance to chromium compounds
		3
H.Ab2	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Genes
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3
		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
		Genes
		Copper homeostasis
		7
		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance
		10
		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases
		2
		Resistance to fluoroquinolones
		4
		Arsenic resistance
		4
		Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance
		2
		Beta-lactamase
		4
		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps
		19
		Resistance to chromium compounds
		3
H.Ab3	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Genes
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3
		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds
		Genes
		Copper homeostasis
		6
		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance
		11
		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases
		2
		Resistance to fluoroquinolones
		4
		Arsenic resistance
		4
		Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance
		2
		Beta-lactamase
		4

		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	19
		Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab4	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	8 Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	12
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Zinc resistance	1
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	5 Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
		Beta-lactamase	3
		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18
		Resistance to chromium compounds	3
H.Ab5	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	7 Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	12
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2 Arsenic resistance	4
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
		Beta-lactamase	4
		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	19
		Resistance to chromium compounds	3
H.Ab6	Virulence, Disease and Defense (103)	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	12
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9 Bile hydrolysis	2
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	25
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2 Arsenic resistance	9
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Beta-lactamase	3
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3 Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	19
		Resistance to chromium compounds	5
H.Ab7	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	11
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9 Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	14
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2 Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Beta-lactamase	4

	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	16
			Resistance to chromium compounds	3
H.Ab8	Virulence, Disease and Defense (101)		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	14
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Bile hydrolysis	2
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	26
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	3
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Beta-lactamase	3
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	20
			Resistance to chromium compounds	5
H.Ab9	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	7
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Bile hydrolysis	3
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	12
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	5
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Fosfomycin resistance	1
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Beta-lactamase	3
			Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	19
			Resistance to chromium compounds	6
H.Ab10	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Bile hydrolysis	2
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	18
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	3
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Arsenic resistance	5
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	1
			Beta-lactamase	3
			Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	21
			Resistance to chromium compounds	3
H.Ab11	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	12
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Bile hydrolysis	2
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	18
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	5
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	9
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2

	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Beta-lactamase	3
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	20
			Resistance to chromium compounds	3
H.Ab13	Virulence, Disease and Defense (103)		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	13
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Bile hydrolysis	2
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	24
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	5
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	9
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Beta-lactamase	3
			Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	21
			Resistance to chromium compounds	5
H.Ab14	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	15
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	6	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	9
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Beta-lactamase	7
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	17
			Resistance to chromium compounds	2
H.Ab15	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Arsenic resistance	4
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Beta-lactamase	6
			Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18
			Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab16	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	13
	Tolerance to colicin E2	3	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	22
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	7	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Beta-lactamase	4

	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	16
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Resistance to chromium compounds	5
H.Ab17	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	5	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Beta-lactamase	6
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18
			Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab18	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	9
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	3
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Arsenic resistance	4
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Beta-lactamase	6
			Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18
			Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab19	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	9
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Arsenic resistance	4
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Beta-lactamase	6
			Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18
			Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab20	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Beta-lactamase	6
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18

		Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab21	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9 Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3 Arsenic resistance	4
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3 Beta-lactamase	6
		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	19
		Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab22	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9 Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3 Arsenic resistance	4
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3 Beta-lactamase	6
		Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	19
		Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab23	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9 Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	3
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2 Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Beta-lactamase	6
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3 Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18
		Resistance to chromium compounds	4
H.Ab24	Virulence, Disease and Defense	Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides	Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9 Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance	Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	2
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	5 Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2 Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolinate biosynthesis	3 Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1 Beta-lactamase	10
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3 Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18
		Resistance to chromium compounds	4

H.Ab25	Virulence, Disease and Defense		Resistance to antibiotics and toxic compounds	
	Bacteriocins, ribosomally synthesized antibacterial peptides		Copper homeostasis	6
	Colicin V and Bacteriocin Production Cluster	9	Cobalt-zinc-cadmium resistance	10
	Invasion and intracellular resistance		Aminoglycoside adenylyltransferases	3
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (SSU ribosomal proteins)	4	Resistance to fluoroquinolones	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in DNA transcription	2	Arsenic resistance	4
	Mycobacterium virulence operon possibly involved in quinolate biosynthesis	3	Copper homeostasis: copper tolerance	2
	Listeria surface proteins: Internalin-like proteins	1	Beta-lactamase	6
	Mycobacterium virulence operon involved in protein synthesis (LSU ribosomal proteins)	3	Multidrug Resistance Efflux Pumps	18

7.3.10 Multiple Genome Analysis of the 25 *A. baumannii* Genomes

From the resistance genes listed to be present in the annotated genomes, the genes of interest were narrowed down based on the mutations identified in chapter 4.

7.3.11 Beta-lactamase Resistance Determinants

In sample H.AB1, the BlaOXA-5 (BASYS03743) is most identical to blaOXA-213 when blasted against the NCBI database, which is unique from the blaOXA genes in the other samples. The multiple genome alignment using MAUVE returned only two samples; H.Ab3 and H.Ab5 bearing a homologous gene each. The genes were however annotated as *exoX*, encoding an “Exoribonuclease 10” protein. A quick BLAST search of the two gene sequences from both H.Ab3 and H.Ab5 revealed a 100% identity with the *exoX* gene.

As shown in **Table 7.6**, several homologues were identified between the clinical isolates, denoted by the colored and linked boxes. The β -lactamase gene in sample Ab00 (BASYS00234) was identified to be commonly found in all the sequenced samples, as indicated by the brown boxes in **Table 7.6**. Several blaOXA genes were also discovered and color-coded into three sets; purple, orange (β -lactamase TEM homologous to samples H.Ab15, H.Ab17, H.Ab23, H.Ab24 and H.Ab25) and black (β -lactamase TEM with no homologous sequences among the 25 sequenced isolates). The first set of homologous genes (color-coded as purple) was identified to be blaOXA-10 genes, present only in samples H.Ab14 through H.ab25. The second set (color-coded as orange) consists of a group of homologous TEM type β -lactamases, present only in samples H.Ab15, H.Ab17, H.Ab23, H.Ab24 and H.Ab25. The third set (color-coded as black) includes a group of TEM and OXA type β -lactamases with no homologous sequences in any of the other samples. A lone blaOXA-5 gene was also identified in sample H.Ab1 that did not return any homologous matches with the other samples when compared using MAUVE.

Table 7.6
 Comparison of *blaOXA* Genes in the 25 *A. baumannii* Isolates

Sample	gene	BASYS ID	Protein function	homologs	β -lactam resistance
Ab00	<i>bla</i>	BASYS02234	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	NO
H.Ab1	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS02377	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>blaOXA-5</i>	BASYS03743	β -lactamase OXA-5 [H]	Group 5	
H.Ab2	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS02170	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
H.Ab3	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01604	β -lactamase OXA-51	Group 1	YES
H.Ab4	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01236	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	NO
H.Ab5	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01505	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	NO
H.Ab6	No <i>blaOXA</i> identified			no <i>blaOXA</i>	NO
H.Ab7	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01143	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	NO
H.Ab8	No <i>blaOXA</i> identified			no <i>blaOXA</i>	NO
H.Ab9	No <i>blaOXA</i> identified			no <i>blaOXA</i>	NO
H.Ab10	No <i>blaOXA</i> identified			no <i>blaOXA</i>	NO
H.Ab11	No <i>blaOXA</i> identified			no <i>blaOXA</i>	NO
H.Ab13	No <i>blaOXA</i> identified			no <i>blaOXA</i>	NO
H.Ab14	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS00258	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	YES
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01427	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	
H.Ab15	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS02174	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03662	β -lactamase TEM	Group 3	
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS03885	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
H.Ab16	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS02251	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
H.Ab17	<i>bla</i>	BASYS00191	β -lactamase TEM	Group 3	YES
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS00695	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS03439	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
H.Ab18	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01581	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS03725	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03957	β -lactamase TEM	Group 4	
H.Ab19	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01583	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS03787	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03789	β -lactamase TEM	Group 4	
H.Ab20	<i>bla</i>	BASYS02344	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS04185	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS04259	β -lactamase TEM	Group 4	
H.Ab21	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01716	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS03840	β -lactamase TEM	Group 4	
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS03919	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
H.Ab22	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS01688	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03709	β -lactamase TEM	Group 4	
	<i>blaOXA-10</i>	BASYS04026	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
H.Ab23	<i>bla</i>	BASYS02159	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03888	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03798	β -lactamase TEM	Group 3	
H.Ab24	<i>bla</i>	BASYS00018	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 4	YES
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS01764	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03218	β -lactamase TEM	Group 3	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03956	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 4	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS04028	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 4	
H.Ab25	<i>bla</i>	BASYS02217	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS03761	β -lactamase TEM	Group 3	
	<i>bla</i>	BASYS04033	β -lactamase OXA-10 [H]	Group 2	

Table 7.7
BLAST Results of the BASys-Annotated blaOXA Genes

Group	Sample	BASysID	BLAST hit
Group 1	Ab00	BASYS02234	blaOXA-133 (99% coverage, 57% identity)
	H.Ab1	BASYS02377	blaOXA-133 (99% coverage, 57% identity)
	H.Ab2	BASYS02170	blaOXA-133 (99% coverage, 57% identity)
	H.Ab3	BASYS01604	blaOXA-133 (99% coverage, 57% identity)
	H.Ab4	BASYS01236	blaOXA-133 (99% coverage, 57% identity)
Group 2	H.Ab14	BASYS00258	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab15	BASYS03885	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab17	BASYS03439	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab18	BASYS03725	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab19	BASYS03787	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab20	BASYS04185	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab21	BASYS03919	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab22	BASYS04026	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab23	BASYS03888	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
	H.Ab25	BASYS04033	blaOXA-133 (98% coverage, 97% identity)
Group 3	H.Ab15	BASYS03662	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab17	BASYS00191	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab23	BASYS03798	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab24	BASYS03218	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab25	BASYS03761	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
Group 4	H.Ab18	BASYS03957	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab19	BASYS03789	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab20	BASYS04259	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab21	BASYS03840	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab22	BASYS03709	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab24	BASYS03218	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)
	H.Ab25	BASYS03761	β -lactamase TEM (99% coverage, 100% identity)

There appears to be a correlation between the number of β -lactamase genes present in a single genome and its antimicrobial resistance. The genes in group 1 (brown) appear to be prevalent in most of the samples, but do not seem to inherently confer meropenem resistance, as indicated by samples Ab00, H.Ab4, H.Ab5 and H.Ab7. Moreover, despite the differing phenotypic profile in H.Ab3 and H.Ab5, their β -lactamase genes, BASYS01604 and BASYS1505 were identified to be identical. This suggests that i) this group may not be functionally capable of breaking down meropenem and, ii) H.Ab1, H.Ab2 and H.Ab3 potentially possesses an intrinsically non- β -lactamase resistance mechanism unique from the other samples. In samples H.Ab14-H.Ab25 on the other hand, it is deduced that the presence of at least one gene from group 2 (purple) or group 3 (orange) is sufficient in conferring β -lactamase resistance.

Table 7.8
List of *bla*OXA Genes Flanked by Transposases in H.Ab24

Group	Start	End	Accession	Gene	Protein Function
Group 4	12503	12949	BASYS00013	-	Transposase
	13024	13593	BASYS00014	-	Transposase
	13635	14027	BASYS00015	<i>yeeA</i> [H]	Putative DNA methyltransferase <i>yeeA</i> [H]
	14035	14589	BASYS00016	<i>yeeB</i> [H]	Putative ATP-dependent helicase <i>yeeB</i> [H]
	14841	15149	BASYS00017	-	Hypothetical
	15254	16084	BASYS00018	<i>bla</i> [H]	Beta-lactamase OXA-10 [H]
	16181	16750	BASYS00019	-	Transposase
	16825	17271	BASYS00020	-	Transposase
Group 1	1841763	1842587	BASYS01764	<i>bla</i> [H]	Beta-lactamase OXA-10 [H]
Group 3	3305974	3306384	BASYS03217	<i>tmpR</i> [H]	Transposon Tn3 resolvase [H]
	3306567	3307427	BASYS03218	<i>bla</i>	Beta-lactamase TEM
	3307498	3308103	BASYS03219	-	Transposase for insertion sequence element IS257 in transposon Tn4003 [H]
	3308179	3308292	BASYS03220	-	Transposase
Group 4	4063829	4064275	BASYS03951	-	Transposase
	4064350	4064919	BASYS03952	-	Transposase
	4064961	4065353	BASYS03953	<i>yeeA</i> [H]	Putative DNA methyltransferase <i>yeeA</i> [H]
	4065361	4065915	BASYS03954	<i>yeeB</i> [H]	Putative ATP-dependent helicase <i>yeeB</i> [H]
	4066167	4066475	BASYS03955	-	Hypothetical
	4066580	4067410	BASYS03956	<i>bla</i> [H]	Beta-lactamase OXA-10 [H]
	4067507	4068076	BASYS03957	-	Transposase
	4068151	4068597	BASYS03958	-	Transposase
Group 4	4142896	4143726	BASYS04028	<i>bla</i> [H]	Beta-lactamase OXA-10 [H]

According to the multiple genome alignment output generated by MAUVE, the genes in group 4 (black) are not homologous to any of the other samples. A BLAST search of the genes however has determined that the sequences in group 4 produce the same hits as with group 3 (Table 7.7). A multiple sequence alignment was performed using UGENE, revealing a 100% identity between the group 3 and group 4 genes. The non-homologous alignment produced by MAUVE may be an error resulting from a flaw in the software. By compiling groups 3 and 4, it can be observed that sample H.Ab24 bears a several copies of TEM-type beta-lactamases, a distinctive characteristic from the other samples. This suggests a potential for a higher beta-lactam resistance in the sample. A brief screening of the genome layout of the beta-lactamase genes revealed that three of the beta-lactamase genes in H.Ab24 are flanked by transposase-encoding genes (Table 7.8), which explains the presence of the duplicate genes.

7.3.12 *mexB* Associated Beta-lactamase Resistance

As shown in Table 7.9, several homologous *mexB* genes were identified in the 25 clinical isolates. The homologous genes were divided into three groups; group 1 (brown), group 2 (purple), group 3 (orange) and group 4 (black). Several sequences in samples

H.Ab1, H.Ab2 and H.Ab7 were categorized into a “fragmented” group and color-coded as pink. The single gene categorized under group 3 in sample H.Ab9 was identified to be homologous to the *acrB* gene in samples H.Ab6, H.Ab8, H.Ab10, H.Ab11 and H.Ab13. The “fragmented” genes were reconfirmed using the NCBI BLAST tool, confirming that they originate from the same gene. The “fragmented” genes in sample H.Ab7 were all homologous to the *bepE* gene present in the other 24 *A. baumannii* isolates tested.

Interestingly, all of the *A. baumannii* isolates carry at least two genes encoding the *mexB* efflux pump component. Initially, it was theorized that this was simply the result of a duplication event. However, a multiple alignment of the genes revealed that in each sample, the two genes are similar but non-identical to one another (**Figure 7.9**). The reference gene used in the alignment was the *mexB* gene in the susceptible parent strain, Ab00 (BASYS ID: BASYS00954) where the mutation was identified and analyzed in the previous chapters. The *mexB* genes in group 1 have a dissimilarity ranging from 0% to 7% with this reference sequence. The second *mexB* gene (Ab00 BASYS ID: BASYS01040) however is either absent from some of the clinical isolates or has a hamming dissimilarity value of 43% to 45%. A BLAST search of the group 2 *mexB* gene revealed that they are 45% identical to the *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 *mexB* gene (**Figure 7.10**).

Table 7.9
Comparison of *mexB* Genes in the 25 *A. baumannii* Isolates

Sample	Gene	BASYS ID	Protein function	Homologs	Meropenem resistance
Ab00	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00954	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	NO
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01040	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab1	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01026	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01367	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02148	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 4	
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03909	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Fragmented	
	<i>mepA</i>	BASYS03910	Multidrug/solvent efflux pump periplasmic linker protein <i>mep</i>	Fragmented	
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS04253	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 4	
H.Ab2	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS00890	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS00971	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 2	
	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS01886	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Fragmented	
	<i>arpB</i> [H]	BASYS01887	<i>arpB</i> [H]	Fragmented	
H.Ab3	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02915	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02999	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab4	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01772	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	NO
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03032	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	
H.Ab5	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS02727	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 2	NO
	<i>acrF</i> [H]	BASYS02728	Acriflavine resistance protein F [H]	Group 2	
	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS02815	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 1	
H.Ab6	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00912	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	INTERMEDIATE
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00990	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03738	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 4	
H.Ab7	<i>bepE</i>	BASYS02680	<i>bepE</i>	Fragmented	NO
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02681	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Fragmented	
	<i>arpC</i>	BASYS02682	<i>arpC</i>	Fragmented	
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03062	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab8	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03144	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	NO
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02854	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab9	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02932	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	NO
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02964	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab9	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03047	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	NO
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS04196	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 3	
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03259	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab10	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03340	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	INTERMEDIATE
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00711	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	
H.Ab11	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00787	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	NO
	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS02827	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 2	
H.Ab13	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS02918	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 1	NO
	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS02918	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 1	
H.Ab14	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01816	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03480	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	
H.Ab15	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00947	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01026	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab16	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS00911	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 1	INTERMEDIATE
	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS00986	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 2	
H.Ab17	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00310	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01981	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	
H.Ab18	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS02774	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 2	YES
	<i>mexB</i> [H]	BASYS02852	MDR protein <i>mexB</i> [H]	Group 1	
H.Ab19	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02805	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02883	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	
H.Ab20	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00953	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01032	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab21	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02913	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02990	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	
H.Ab22	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02906	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS02981	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	
H.Ab23	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00833	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00913	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab24	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03536	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS03832	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	
H.Ab25	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS00953	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 1	YES
	<i>mexB</i>	BASYS01031	MDR protein <i>mexB</i>	Group 2	

Figure 7.9: Multiple Sequence Alignment of the Replicate *mexB* Genes Found in the 24 Clinical Isolates. Sequences that Yielded Greater than 10% Difference was Removed From the Overall Alignment

Alignments Download GenPept Graphics							
	Description	Max score	Total score	Query cover	E value	Ident	Accession
<input type="checkbox"/>	RecName: Full=Multidrug resistance protein MexB; AltName: Full=Multidrug-efflux transporter MexB [Pseudomonas aeruginosa PAO1]	946	946	99%	0.0	49%	P52002.2
<input type="checkbox"/>	RecName: Full=Toluene efflux pump membrane transporter TtgB [Pseudomonas putida DOT-T1E]	919	919	99%	0.0	48%	O52248.2
<input type="checkbox"/>	RecName: Full=Antibiotic efflux pump membrane transporter ArpB [Pseudomonas putida]	919	919	99%	0.0	48%	Q9KJC2.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	RecName: Full=Probable efflux pump membrane transporter TtgB [Pseudomonas putida KT2440]	919	919	99%	0.0	48%	Q88N31.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	RecName: Full=Multidrug efflux pump subunit AcrB; AltName: Full=AcrAB-TolC multidrug efflux pump subunit AcrB; AltName: Full=Acridine resistance protein B [E	917	917	97%	0.0	49%	P31224.1

Figure 7.10: BLAST Results of the Group 2 *mexB* Gene

The results from both the multiple gene alignment and BLAST search suggests that the *mexB* genes in group 1 (BASYS00954 and its equivalents) originated from *A. baumannii*, possibly via convergent evolution. The *mexB* genes categorized into group 2 on the other hand may have originated from a *Pseudomonas* species somewhere down its evolutionary path (Fournier et al., 2006). It also stands to reason that the group 2 *mexB* gene may have been a leftover sequence that has undergone multiple mutations, leading to a 50% variation from its ancestor (Lang et al., 2011).

The presence of either one of these genes however does not seem to guarantee a resistance phenotype. A total of eight out of 25 isolates exhibited a susceptibility towards meropenem despite possessing one of the *mexB* genes. When compared with **Table 7.6**, it shows that the meropenem-susceptible samples either lack a β -lactamase gene or contain a group 1 (brown color-coded) β -lactamase element. This data implies that in the absence of a functional β -lactamase gene, the *A. baumannii* isolates are incapable of expressing resistance towards meropenem.

Furthermore, the mutation in the *in vitro* generated resistant variant AbRM (542C>T) was not found in any of the other isolates (**Figure 7.11**). In addition to this, the mutation in the *epsL* gene (274G>T) in the isogenic variant was also identified to be unique among the samples tested (**Figure 7.12**). The combinatorial effect of these two mutations have shown to be effective in conferring meropenem resistance to an otherwise susceptible strain. It is possible that acquiring either one of these mutations could grant near similar level of resistance.

Figure 7.11: Multiple Sequence Alignment of the *in vitro mexB* Mutation in Variant AbRM

Figure 7.12: Multiple Sequence Alignment of the *in vitro epsL* Mutation in Variant AbRM

7.3.13 Macrolide Resistance Determinants

As shown in **Figure 7.13**, an initial screening via multiple genome alignment revealed that three of the samples; H.Ab5, H.Ab6 and H.Ab16 lack the *srrA* gene. However, H.Ab5 possesses two homologous genes encoding the phosphate regulon transcriptional regulatory protein *phoB* and the transcriptional regulatory protein *ycbL*. The others on the other hand possess a single *srrA* gene each with varying homology from one another. H.Ab1 is an exception, as it carries two copies of the *srrA* gene (BASYS02146 and BASYS03749) located at a considerable distance from one another. A pairwise alignment between the two genes shows a 60% identity, ruling out the possibility of duplication. MAUVE has grouped the H.Ab1 and H.Ab2 *srrA* homologs into group 3, while the *srrA* homologs in H.Ab7 through H.Ab13 were grouped into group 2. The remaining samples were all categorized into group 1.

To ascertain the presence of *srrA* in samples H.Ab6 and H.Ab16, the sequencing reads of each sample were aligned to the Ab00 *srrA* gene (BASYS01945) via BWA. Both reads returned a match with *srrA* and the consensus sequence for each was exported accordingly. Multiple sequence alignment via UGENE revealed these sequences to conform 100% to the reference Ab00 sequence (**Figure 7.14**). The pileup analysis of the SAM file generated from the BWA alignment also shows no indication of genetic variants that could have been missed (data not shown). This rules out the possibility that the reference assembly has removed potential variants from the H.Ab6 and H.Ab16 *srrA* consensus sequences.

After comparing the alignment score (percentage and identity) between the *srrA* sequences from the 25 genomes, there is no correlation between the MAUVE-designated homologs and the percentage similarity of the *srrA* genes. From the sequence alignment, *srrA* in samples H.Ab1 and H.Ab10 show the highest dissimilarity towards the AbRE mutant *srrA* gene. No significant differences were noted in the BLAST results of the *srrA* genes as well. The sequences returned hits to the *cheY* gene when blasted against the nonredundant database, and the transcriptional regulator protein *srrA* gene when blasted against the uniprot database at varying identity percentages. There is also no identifiable correlation between the resistance profile of the 25 isolates to the variations in *srrA* gene

sequence. This may be due to the gene function emphasizing on general chemotaxis rather than antimicrobial resistance.

Table 7.10
srrA Gene Homologs Retrieved from MUAVE

Sample	Gene	BASYS ID	Protein function	Homologs	Erythromycin resistance
Ab00	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01945	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	NO
H.Ab1	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS02146	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 3	YES
	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS03749	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 3	
H.Ab2	<i>srrA</i> [H]	BASYS01884	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i> [H]	Group 3	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab3	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01878	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab4	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS00149	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	NO
H.Ab5	<i>phoB</i>	BASYS01800	Phosphate regulon transcriptional regulatory protein <i>phoB</i> [H]	Group 1	INTERMEDIATE
	<i>ycbL</i>	BASYS01799	Uncharacterized transcriptional regulatory protein <i>ycbL</i> [H]	Group 1	
H.Ab6	no <i>srrA</i>			no <i>srrA</i>	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab7	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01424	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 2	YES
H.Ab8	<i>srrA</i> [H]	BASYS01922	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i> [H]	Group 2	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab9	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS03908	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 2	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab10	<i>srrA</i> [H]	BASYS02355	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i> [H]	Group 2	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab11	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01655	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 2	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab13	<i>srrA</i> [H]	BASYS02005	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i> [H]	Group 2	YES
H.Ab14	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01242	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab15	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01895	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab16	no <i>srrA</i>			no <i>srrA</i>	NO
H.Ab17	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS02572	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab18	<i>srrA</i> [H]	BASYS01850	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i> [H]	Group 1	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab19	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01856	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	INTERMEDIATE
H.Ab20	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS02052	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	NO
H.Ab21	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01991	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab22	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01962	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab23	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01841	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab24	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS02245	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES
H.Ab25	<i>srrA</i>	BASYS01899	Transcriptional regulatory protein <i>srrA</i>	Group 1	YES

When the Ab00 *srrA* gene was blasted using the NCBI blastx search tool on the other hand, several hits to the *adeR* and *adeS* regulatory genes were retrieved, at 100% coverage and identity. Furthermore, a sequence alignment of the *srrA* gene on the reference sequence revealed a stretch of unmatched sequence downstream of the *srrA*. As it turns out, the *baeS* gene, located immediately following *srrA* in the Ab00 genome was a perfect match to the missing sequence. It is likely that BASys opted for the uniprot annotation in the final report, resulting in the arguably inaccurate gene-calling. Analysis of the overall *srrA* multiple sequence alignment has also revealed that the mutation in the resistant variant, AbRE (272C>T) is unique from the other samples.

Figure 7.13: Multiple Sequence Alignment Performed in UGENE Showing the Percent and Number of Dissimilarities in the *A. baumannii srrA* Genes

7.3.14 wgMLST Analysis of the 25 *A. baumannii* Isolates

Using the assembled whole-genome sequences, the complete MLST profile of the 25 *A. baumannii* isolates were generated (Table 7.10) via the online webtool provided by the Center for Genomic Epidemiology. When the sequences were typed based on the Oxford scheme (abaumannii1), samples H.Ab1 through H.Ab9, H.Ab11 and H.Ab13 were identified to be of unknown sequence type, bringing a total of 11 unknowns. The Pasteur scheme (abaumannii2) on the other hand shows that samples H.Ab2, H.Ab9, H.Ab10 and H.Ab13 are of unknown sequence types, which totals up to only four. A comparison of the two schemes reveals that samples H.Ab2, H.Ab9 and H.Ab13 are unknown in both schemes.

By concatenating the allelic profiles from each MLST scheme, two phylogenetic trees were constructed via UGENE using the MrBayes method (Figure 7.15). In both dendrograms, samples H.Ab15 through H.Ab22 are shown to belong in the same clade,

although in differing subgroups. The same is for samples H.Ab3 through H.Ab5 in **Figure 7.15 (a)**. Unknown ST's are shown to be grouped a single large clade in scheme 1 (upper group), in which only sample H.Ab10 and H.Ab14 are of known ST's. Both schemes also show that samples Ab00 and H.Ab7 are outliers to the other groups.

When compared with their resistance profile, samples H.Ab15 and H.Ab17 through H.Ab25 share a common multidrug resistance phenotype. From this observation, it can be speculated that these ten strains have originated from the same MDR common ancestor. Moreover, despite sharing similar MDR profiles, H.Ab3 was not grouped into the same clade with the previous set of samples in either of the dendograms. However, the Pasteur scheme does cluster the H.Ab3 in the same larger MDR monophyletic group, unlike the Oxford scheme. It is worth noting though, that the Oxford scheme groups the H.A3 with the other unknown ST's within the same monophyletic group. This difference in grouping despite a shared phenotypic profile suggests that sample H.Ab3 may have evolved from a different ancestor from the aforementioned MDR group. The observed similarity in drug resistance profile may also be a product of convergent evolution.

In addition, sample Ab00, which is shown to be isolated from the other subgroups have also exhibited the potential for evolving resistance against antimicrobials. Due to the very minimal changes in its genome, owing to an evolution under a controlled setting, its position in the phylogenetic trees would not be affected.

From the observed data, it can be deduced that the MLST can reflect the resistance potential of certain strains to a certain extent. However, depending on the pathway of resistance acquisition, the grouping based on ST might not be entirely accurate. A whole-genome based analysis would perhaps show a more accurate representation as it puts into account other genes not included in the sequence typing.

Table 7.11

wgMLST Output of the 25 *A. Baumannii* Isolates, Generated Using Both Database Patterns 1 (Oxford) and 2 (Pasteur)

Sample	A. baumannii scheme 1						A. baumannii scheme 2					
Ab00	Sequence Type: ST-734						Sequence Type: ST-239					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_4</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-1</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_59</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-4</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_157</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_15</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-7</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_28</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-1</i>
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_45</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-4</i>	
H.Ab1	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-220					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_52</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-45</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_141</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-20</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_62</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-44</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	81.6	288	305	0	<i>gpi_164</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-16</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	99.78	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_103</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-20</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_7</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-29</i>
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_10</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-20</i>	
H.Ab2	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: Unknown ST					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_32</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-8</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_120</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-1</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_33</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-5</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_172</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-1</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_12</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-29</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_10</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-2</i>
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_5</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-3</i>	
H.Ab3	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-374					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_1</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-3</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_56</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	95.74	305	305	0	<i>gpi_108</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_15</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-3</i>

	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_1</i>		<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-4</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_26</i>		<i>rprob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rprob-4</i>
H.Ab4	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-374						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele		Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_1</i>		<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-3</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_56</i>		<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>		<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	95.74	305	305	0	<i>gpi_108</i>		<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_15</i>		<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-3</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_1</i>		<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-4</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_26</i>		<i>rprob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rprob-4</i>
H.Ab5	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-374						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele		Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_1</i>		<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-3</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_56</i>		<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>		<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	95.74	305	305	0	<i>gpi_108</i>		<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_15</i>		<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-3</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_1</i>		<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-4</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_26</i>		<i>rprob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rprob-4</i>
H.Ab6	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-279						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele		Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_25</i>		<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-22</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_99</i>		<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-26</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_27</i>		<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-47</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	99.67	305	305	0	<i>gpi_93</i>		<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-14</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_65</i>		<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-50</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_55</i>		<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-16</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_60</i>		<i>rprob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rprob-47</i>
H.Ab7	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-360						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele		Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_4</i>		<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-1</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_62</i>		<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-4</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>		<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_157</i>		<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-1</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_15</i>		<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-42</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_31</i>		<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-1</i>

	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_45</i>		<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-4</i>
H.Ab8	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-433						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_25</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-22</i>	
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_142</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-26</i>	
	<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_39</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta-29</i>	
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_114</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-14</i>	
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_65</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-27</i>	
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_30</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-16</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_28</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-47</i>		
H.Ab9	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: Unknown ST						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
	<i>cpn60</i>	99.76	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_27</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	99.75	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-59</i>	
	<i>gdhb</i>	99.42	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_93</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-26</i>	
	<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_55</i>	<i>glta</i>	99.38	483	483	0	<i>glta-54</i>	
	<i>gpi</i>	97.38	305	305	0	<i>gpi_7</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-14</i>	
	<i>gyrb</i>	99.12	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_20</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-23</i>	
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_20</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-16</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_57</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-47</i>		
H.Ab10	Sequence Type: ST-262						Sequence Type: Unknown ST						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
	<i>cpn60</i>	98.34	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_41</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	99.01	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-32</i>	
	<i>gdhb</i>	97.09	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_119</i>	<i>fusa</i>	99.68	633	633	0	<i>fusa-26</i>	
	<i>glta</i>	99.79	484	484	0	<i>glta_49</i>	<i>glta</i>	99.79	483	483	0	<i>glta-34</i>	
	<i>gpi</i>	99.67	305	305	0	<i>gpi_115</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-23</i>	
	<i>gyrb</i>	96.5	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_68</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-35</i>	
	<i>reca</i>	98.38	371	371	0	<i>reca_53</i>	<i>rplb</i>	98.18	330	330	0	<i>rplb-16</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	99.22	513	513	0	<i>rpod_58</i>	<i>rpob</i>	99.34	456	456	0	<i>rpob-34</i>		
H.Ab11	Sequence Type: Unknown ST						Sequence Type: ST-71						
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_37</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60_20</i>	
	<i>gdhb</i>	99.71	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_14</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa_26</i>	
	<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_11</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta_26</i>	
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_109</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg_14</i>	
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_37</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca_26</i>	
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_21</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb_16</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_15</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob_25</i>		

H.Ab13 Sequence Type: Unknown ST							Sequence Type: Unknown ST					
Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_37</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-20</i>	
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_14</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-26</i>	
<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_11</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta-26</i>	
<i>gpi</i>	94.1	305	305	0	<i>gpi_190</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-14</i>	
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_65</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-26</i>	
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_21</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-16</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_15</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-47</i>	

H.Ab14 Sequence Type: ST-514							Sequence Type: ST-103					
Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_18</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60_7</i>	
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_29</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa_3</i>	
<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_1</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta_2</i>	
<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_114</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg_1</i>	
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_52</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca_7</i>	
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_28</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb_1</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_7</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob_4</i>	

H.Ab15 Sequence Type: ST-195							Sequence Type: ST-2					
Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-2</i>	
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>	
<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_1</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta-2</i>	
<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_96</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>	
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-2</i>	
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-2</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-2</i>	

H.Ab16 Sequence Type: ST-553							Sequence Type: ST-193					
Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_1</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-3</i>	
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_2</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-1</i>	
<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_21</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta-7</i>	
<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_157</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-1</i>	
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_35</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-7</i>	
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_28</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-2</i>	
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_4</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-4</i>	

H.Ab17 Sequence Type: ST-208							Sequence Type: ST-2					
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Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa_2</i>
<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA_2</i>
<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_97</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg_2</i>
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca_2</i>
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb_2</i>
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob_2</i>

H.Ab18 Sequence Type: ST-425						Sequence Type: ST-2					
Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-2</i>
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>
<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-2</i>
<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_100</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-2</i>
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-2</i>
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-2</i>

H.Ab19 Sequence Type: ST-425						Sequence Type: ST-2					
Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-2</i>
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	99.84	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>
<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA-2</i>
<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_100</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-2</i>
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-2</i>
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-2</i>

H.Ab20 Sequence Type: ST-208						Sequence Type: ST-2					
Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>
<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa_2</i>
<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA_2</i>
<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_97</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg_2</i>
<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca_2</i>
<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb_2</i>
<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob_2</i>

H.Ab21	Sequence Type: ST-806						Sequence Type: ST-215					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_35</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-27</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>
	<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_21</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta-7</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_202</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_15</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-2</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-1</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_4</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-2</i>

H.Ab22	Sequence Type: ST-806						Sequence Type: ST-215					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_35</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60-27</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	421	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa-2</i>
	<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_21</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta-7</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_202</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg-2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_15</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca-2</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb-1</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_4</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob-2</i>

H.Ab23	Sequence Type: ST-208						Sequence Type: ST-2					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa_2</i>
	<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_1</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta_2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_97</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg_2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca_2</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb_2</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob_2</i>

H.Ab24	Sequence Type: ST-208						Sequence Type: ST-2					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa_2</i>
	<i>glta</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>glta_1</i>	<i>glta</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>glta_2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_97</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg_2</i>
	<i>gyrb</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrb_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca_2</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplb</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplb_2</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob_2</i>

H.Ab25	Sequence Type: ST-208						Sequence Type: ST-2					
	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele	Locus	% Identity	HSP Length	Allele Length	Gaps	Allele
	<i>cpn60</i>	100	421	421	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>	<i>cpn60</i>	100	405	405	0	<i>cpn60_2</i>
	<i>gdhb</i>	100	344	344	0	<i>gdhb_3</i>	<i>fusa</i>	100	633	633	0	<i>fusa_2</i>
	<i>gltA</i>	100	484	484	0	<i>gltA_1</i>	<i>gltA</i>	100	483	483	0	<i>gltA_2</i>
	<i>gpi</i>	100	305	305	0	<i>gpi_97</i>	<i>pyrg</i>	100	297	297	0	<i>pyrg_2</i>
	<i>gyrB</i>	100	457	457	0	<i>gyrB_3</i>	<i>reca</i>	100	372	372	0	<i>reca_2</i>
	<i>reca</i>	100	371	371	0	<i>reca_2</i>	<i>rplB</i>	100	330	330	0	<i>rplB_2</i>
	<i>rpod</i>	100	513	513	0	<i>rpod_3</i>	<i>rpob</i>	100	456	456	0	<i>rpob_2</i>

a) abumannii1 (Oxford scheme), and **b)** abumannii2 (Pasteur scheme). The dendograms are generated via MrBayes in UGENE and constructed based on the pairwise differences in the concatenated MLST allelic profiles

Figure 7.14: Phylogenetic Trees of the 25 *A. baumannii* Strains Generated using Oxford and Pasteur MLST Schemes

7.4 CONCLUSION

All 25 *A. baumannii* genomes were successfully sequenced, annotated and compared accordingly. Analysis of the whole-genome data lead to the discovery of several novel sequence types among the 25 clinical isolates. Also, the mutation profiles from the isogenic variants were successfully compared with the clinical isolates, revealing mutations unique to the *in vitro*-challenged variants. This indicates that exposure to the antimicrobials; ciprofloxacin, erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem under a controlled *in vitro* environment will incite mutations distinctive from the clinically resistant strains.

CHAPTER EIGHT

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 SUMMARY

The aim of the study was to demonstrate the genomic plasticity of *A. baumannii* when subjected to a varying set of selective pressures under a controlled environment. Although previous studies have successfully identified numerous genetic modifications resulting from induced adaptation, there is still a noticeable gap in knowledge regarding the complexity of these adaptive mechanisms as well as their chronological order. Moreover, the genomics studies currently available have constantly emphasized how convoluted these genetic modifications can be. This is made even more difficult by the fact that *in vitro* and *in vivo* adaptations tending to produce dissimilar outcomes. However, it is undeniable that findings that stem from an *in vitro* approach can aid in the understanding of real-life adaptations.

In the context of the parent strain, Ab00, it was observed that despite the presence of several genes that should theoretically confer resistance, the isolate still exhibited susceptibility towards the target antimicrobials. This was reflected in the ZOI for erythromycin, meropenem and imipenem exhibited by the parent strain in spite of the presence of macrolide efflux genes and beta-lactamase genes identified in its genome. It is arguable that this discrepancy may be due to a suppressed expression of said genes. Throughout the duration of the Ab00 resistance induction, it was clear that adaptation toward different classes of antibiotics result in differing phenotypic properties. Exposure to ciprofloxacin (AbRC) and erythromycin (AbRE) have resulted in differing turbidities, whereby the former tends to form fragile pellicles, leaving a relatively clear culture medium until disturbed, while the latter thrives without any sign of biofilm production. On the other hand, exposure to carbapenem (AbRM and AbRI) has resulted in both a reduced growth rate as well as a marked increase in biofilm production in the form of slime. Isogenic variants AbRC and AbRE showed a significantly faster rate of resistance acquisition in comparison to AbRM and AbRI; acquiring stable, high-level resistance in approximately two weeks. In contrast, the carbapenem-challenged variants failed to

achieve high-level resistance, likely attributed to its drug indifference resistance mechanism. This also puts to question the functionality of the blaOXA-10 gene that was initially identified.

When the chronological order of the identified variants were scrutinized, it was clear that under certain selective pressures, early-onset and late-onset mutations may take place at different rates. The former has been observed to occur almost immediately after being introduced to an antimicrobial, suggesting the efficiency of genomic adaptation when dictated by necessity. Certain mutations however occur much later in the induction period, indicating that even after a stable resistance has been achieved it is still possible for genetic modification to occur. However, this may simply be a by-product of the continuous selective pressure, without any significant effect on the resistance itself. In addition to the difference in mutation time points, the isogenic variants have also exhibited a brief window of heterogeneity during the induction process, each lasting no more than one to two days. Inadvertently, this indicates that the mutation selection window for *A. baumannii* is relatively short lived before a permanent shift in allele dominance. From the mutation tracking analysis, it was determined that modifications in cellular signaling may play a significant role as AbRE and AbRM were both identified to have an early-onset mutation in signaling genes *bvgS*, *srrA* and *epsL*.

It was noted that the *in vitro* resistant variants exhibited genetic variations unique to that of the other clinically resistant isolates. Moreover, MLST analysis showed that the susceptible parent strain and its isogenic variants did not belong to any monophyletic groups in the dendrogram generated via the MrBayes method. As such, it was deduced that the MLST can only be used to group clinically resistant isolates. In addition, several novel ST's were also identified in both the Pasteur and Oxford MLST schemes for *A. baumannii*.

8.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Studies pertaining to genomic modifications under non-directed approach tend to be difficult due to the stochastic nature of living organisms. Even under near identical conditions, it is still possible for slight variations to arise in the final results. However, there is reason to believe that these dissimilarities may, to a certain extent provide insight

to the complex pathways leading towards antimicrobial resistance. For instance, in this study, the observed priority placed by the isolate in its modification of signaling genes was in fact, unexpected albeit merited. Evidently, the utilization of quorum sensing is possibly as important as more direct methods of resistance such as beta-lactamase production and efflux pump upregulation and should be further studied.

Following the theme of unexpected mutations in the current study, variants were detected in genes *ftsI* and the RNase I gene, their purpose remains speculative. The modification in amino acid hydrophobicity in the FtsI protein and the truncation of the RNase I protein may result in a substantial change in protein activity. Even though the general effects of these mutations on the translated protein were stipulated, a more thorough proteomics analysis to validate these predictions is recommended.

The presence of a permanently heterogeneous *ahpF* gene detected in this study also worth investigating. This phenomenon was observed to occur in all resistant variants as well as the parent strain, suggesting the maintenance of a rescue mechanism is necessary for this *A. baumannii* lineage. Further analysis of the role of *ahpF* in stress response regulation and maintenance, as well as the role of the multiple heterogenous alleles would therefore be beneficial in supplementing the current understanding of the pathogen's reaction to carbapenems.

From the mutation tracking analysis, the selection period for each of the drugs was determined to be brief; lasting only a single day, excluding *epsL* and the aforementioned *ahpF* gene. The revamping of the dominant bacterial populace is therefore achievable within a 24-hour period, without of course ruling out the possibility of a small wild-type persister group remaining within the population. However, the results recorded under *in vitro* settings may not be entirely translated *in vivo*. As such, this approach should best be repeated in conditions where host-pathogen interactions can be recorded as well. Under circumstances involving the host factor however, the potential for emergence of sublineages bearing varied mutations is highly likely; due to the tendency of the pathogen compartmentalizing into microcolonies to ensure survival, as well as presence of nutrients and pressure not normally available under *in vitro* conditions. The brevity of this mutant repopulation period also implores further studies be carried out on the dosing of antimicrobials, as well as better antimicrobial stewardship.

Also, the early onset mutations in signaling genes observed in the mutation tracking analysis of variant AbRE reveals the preference for quorum sensing alteration as a resistance response in *A. baumannii*. This effectively shows the potential for adjuvants to be used along with macrolides in order to suppress the possibility for resistance acquisition in pathogens. In addition, the development of methods to block quorum sensing in pathogens will allow the use current generation drugs at a lower risk for resistance. This in turn, would be greatly beneficial in the post-antibiotic era.

Although most would argue that *in vivo* data would be of more use, the comparative analysis between the *in vitro* resistant variants with the clinically resistant isolates has proven that even in the absence of the host factor, acquisition of highly stable resistance is still possible. As such, the persistence of these pathogens on abiotic surfaces should be taken seriously. In addition to the hardiness exhibited in *A. baumannii* as described in the literature review, its aptitude for evolving under *in vitro* conditions makes for a dangerous combination. In effect, better care of the use and disposal of antibiotics and/or antibiotic-treated products such as soap and cleaners should be considered, be it within the hospital or domestic setting. Further study on the efficiency of resistance evolution in *A. baumannii* should also be done in order to clarify its genomic adaptability under varied abiotic surfaces.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Results of the amplicon sequencing of target genes in AbRC.

	Mutation											
Sample	C1	C2	C3	C3x	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8a	C8b	C8	C9
[conc.]	0.5	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	16.0	32.0	64.0	64.0	64.0	128.0
Gene												
gyrA	-	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	M	M	M
recB	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	-	-	WT	WT
recC	-	WT	-	WT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WT
tolA	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	WT	-	-	WT	WT
mtnN	WT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WT	WT
purM	WT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WT	WT
xcpX	WT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WT	WT
yihG	WT	WT	-	WT	-	-	-	-	WT	-	M	M

Results of the amplicon sequencing of target genes in AbRE.

Sample	E1	E2	E3	E3x	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10a	E10b	E10
[conc.]	2	4	8	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	1024	1024
Gene													
ftsI [H]	-	W	-	W	-	-	-	W	W	W	W	W	M
RNase I	-	W	-	W	-	-	-	W	W	W	W	W	M
bvgS [H]	M	M	M	-	-	M	-	-	M	-	M	M	M
rlmN	-	W	-	W	-	-	-	W	W	W	-	-	W
srrA	W	W	M	M	-	-	-	M	M	M	-	-	M

Results of the amplicon sequencing of target genes in the AbRM.

Sample	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M8x	M9
[conc.]	0.125	0.25	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0	16.0	16.0	32.0
Gene										
mexB	WT	-	-	WT	WT	M	M	M	M	M
spore Coat	WT	-	-	WT	-	-	WT	WT	-	WT
epsL	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M
atpD	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WT	-	WT
tufI	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WT	-	WT
irR	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	WT	-	WT
ahpF	M	-	-	M	-	-	M	M	M	M
Tn903	M	-	-	M	-	-	M	-	-	M

Results of the amplicon sequencing of target genes in AbRI.

Sample	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7
[conc.]	0.125	0.25	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	8.0
Gene							
ahpF	-	-	-	-	-	WT	M
yceG	WT	-	-	-	-	-	WT
acrB	WT	-	-	WT	WT	M	M
ftsI	WT	WT	-	WT	WT	WT	M
	WT	WT	-	M	M	M	M

APPENDIX B

Summary of RAST and BASys annotations on the 25 *A. baumannii* isolates

Sample	Annotation overview					
	RAST				BASys	
	Genome length	# of genes annotated	# of RNAs	# of Subsystems	Genome length	# of genes annotated
Ab00	3937175	3369	67	445	3937175	3954
H.Ab1	4452044	3961	31	439	4452044	4470
H.Ab2	4163227	3624	31	425	4163227	4326
H.Ab3	3829874	3507	37	420	3829874	3867
H.Ab4	3887368	3493	41	444	3887368	3883
H.Ab5	4015080	3535	36	426	4015080	4276
H.Ab6	4018966	3672	39	418	4018966	4033
H.Ab7	4093562	3648	44	424	4093562	4191
H.Ab8	4152413	3601	34	419	4152413	4255
H.Ab9	4204301	3625	37	423	4204301	4447
H.Ab10	4135270	3554	35	421	4135270	4163
H.Ab11	3883258	3592	33	445	3883258	3846
H.Ab13	4188648	3721	39	426	4188648	4232
H.Ab14	4042571	3743	69	452	4042571	3930
H.Ab15	4017505	3571	39	448	4017505	3885
H.Ab16	4007524	3630	37	453	4007524	4029
H.Ab17	4071780	3786	63	452	4071780	3956
H.Ab18	4130019	3731	46	450	4130019	4108
H.Ab19	4112593	3728	47	451	4112593	4079
H.Ab20	4349892	3942	37	454	4349892	4412
H.Ab21	4223022	3851	40	451	4223022	4295
H.Ab22	4246244	3875	42	451	4246244	4257
H.Ab23	4199636	3775	41	456	4199636	4152
H.Ab24	4150063	3886	68	454	4150063	4043
H.Ab25	4188920	3775	45	456	4188920	4120

APPENDIX C

BioSample Accession Numbers of the Genome Data Submitted to the NCBI Database

Accession no.	Sample ID	Accession no.	Sample ID
SAMN02471432	Ab00	SAMN03174926	H.Ab14
SAMN03174914	H.Ab1	SAMN03174927	H.Ab15
SAMN03174915	H.Ab2	SAMN03174928	H.Ab16
SAMN03174916	H.Ab3	SAMN03174929	H.Ab17
SAMN03174917	H.Ab4	SAMN03174930	H.Ab18
SAMN03174918	H.Ab5	SAMN03174931	H.Ab19
SAMN03174919	H.Ab6	SAMN03174932	H.Ab20
SAMN03174920	H.Ab7	SAMN03174933	H.Ab21
SAMN03174921	H.Ab8	SAMN03174934	H.Ab22
SAMN03174922	H.Ab9	SAMN03174935	H.Ab23
SAMN03174923	H.Ab10	SAMN03174936	H.Ab24
SAMN03174924	H.Ab11	SAMN03174937	H.Ab25
SAMN03174925	H.Ab13		

APPENDIX D

Seminars and Conferences Attended

Poster Presentations

- i. **Mohamad Izwan Ismail**, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek, Rose Iszati Ismet Nayan, Mohamad Syariful, Mohd Ikhmal Hanif, Richard Muhammad James Johari. **PROMISE MDR-AB DNA detection kit**. Invention, Innovation & Design Exposition (IIDEX) 2013. 15th-17th May 2013. UiTM Shah Alam, Selangor.

Oral Presentations

- i. **Mohamad Izwan Ismail**, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek. **SOAPdenovo Proves Lower Number of Scaffolds and Contigs: An Example of Optimum Assembly for Low Yield Sequencing Data *Acinetobacter baumannii***. 4th Australasian Metabolomics Symposium 2012. 4th-5th September 2012. UiTM Puncak Alam, Selangor.
- ii. **Mohamad Izwan Ismail**, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek. **Stability of Transient and Intrinsic Resistance in Several Laboratory-Challenged Variants of Clinically Acquired *Acinetobacter baumannii***. 2nd International Postgraduate Conference (iPoPS) 2013. 2nd-3rd September 2013. UiTM Puncak Alam, Selangor.
- iii. **Mohamad Izwan Ismail**, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek. **Tracking the genomic adaptation of *in vitro* ciprofloxacin-challenged *Acinetobacter baumannii***. 3rd International Postgraduate Conference (iPoPS) 2014. 11th-12th August 2013. UiTM Puncak Alam, Selangor.

Awards

- i. Gold award
Mohamad Izwan Ismail, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek, Rose Iszati Ismet Nayan, Mohamad Syariful, Mohd Ikhmal Hanif, Richard Muhammad James Johari. **PROMISE MDR-AB DNA detection kit**. Invention, Innovation & Design Exposition (IIDEX) 2013. 15th-17th May 2013, UiTM Shah Alam, Selangor.
- ii. Best poster award
Mohamad Izwan Ismail, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek, Rose Iszati Ismet Nayan, Mohamad Syariful, Mohd Ikhmal Hanif, Richard Muhammad James Johari. **PROMISE MDR-AB DNA detection kit**. Invention, Innovation & Design Exposition (IIDEX) 2013. 15th-17th May 2013, UiTM Shah Alam, Selangor.
- iii. Bronze Award

Mohamad Izwan Ismail, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek, Rose Iszati Ismet Nayan, Mohamad Syariful, Mohd Ikhmal Hanif, Richard Muhammad James Johari. **PROMISE MDR-AB DNA detection kit**. BioInnovation Award and BioMalaysia 2013. 21st-23rd October 2013. Persada Johor International Convention Centre, Johor.

iv. Best Oral Presenter

Mohamad Izwan Ismail, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek. **Stability of Transient and Intrinsic Resistance in Several Laboratory-Challenged Variants of Clinically Acquired *Acinetobacter baumannii***. 2nd International Postgraduate Conference (iPoPS) 2013. 2nd-3rd September 2013. UiTM Puncak Alam, Selangor.

v. Best Oral Presenter

Mohamad Izwan Ismail, Mohd Zaki Salleh, Teh Lay Kek. **Tracking the genomic adaptation of *in vitro* ciprofloxacin-challenged *Acinetobacter baumannii***. 3rd International Postgraduate Conference (iPoPS) 2014. 11th-12th August 2013. UiTM Puncak Alam, Selangor.

vi. Gold Award

Mohamad Izwan Bin Ismail, Mohammad Maaruf Bin Jaafar, Mohd Zakihalani Bin A. Halim, Lee Lian Shien, Mohd Zaki Salleh. **iPROMISE ProTASK-DNA detection kit: simultaneous detection of pathogens**. Invention, Innovation & Design Exposition (IIDEX) 2015. 27th-30th April 2015. UiTM Shah Alam, Selangor.

vii. BIMB Elevator Pitch Gold Award

Mohamad Izwan Bin Ismail, Mohammad Maaruf Bin Jaafar, Mohd Zakihalani Bin A. Halim, Lee Lian Shien, Mohd Zaki Salleh. **iPROMISE ProTASK-DNA detection kit: simultaneous detection of pathogens**. Invention, Innovation & Design Exposition (IIDEX) 2015. 27th-30th April 2015. UiTM Shah Alam, Selangor.

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Mohamad Izwan Bin Ismail completed his PhD in Microbial Genomics at the Faculty of Pharmacy, Universiti Teknologi MARA. He converted from to the PhD programme during the second year of his MSc, and was awarded a scholarship under the “Skim Latihan Akademik Bumiputra (SLAB)”. His pursuit for his MSc/PhD began immediately upon completion of his Bachelor’s degree in Biomolecular Sciences at the Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA. Throughout his postgraduate studies, he has made efforts to secure various awards for his team’s research work.

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Izwan, I., Teh, L. K., & Salleh, M. Z. (2015). The genome sequence of *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolated from a septicemic patient in a local hospital in Malaysia. *Genomics data*, 6, 128-129.

Jaafar, M. M., Halim, M. Z. A., **Ismail, M. I.**, Shien, L. L., Kek, T. L., Fong, N. Y., ... & Salleh, M. Z. (2015). Genome Sequencing and Annotation of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* PR08 strain. *Genomics Data*.

Halim, M. Z. A., Jaafar, M. M., Kek, T. L., **Ismail, M. I.**, Shien, L. L., Fong, N. Y., ... & Salleh, M. Z. (2016). Genome sequencing and annotation of multidrug resistant *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MDR-TB) PR10 strain. *Genomics Data*.